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Aim and Scope of the Journal

This is a peer-reviewed academic interdisciplinary journal. The journal aims to create a forum for researchers to publish their research works with the specific scope of religious peacebuilding, and other scholarly articles in religious studies, political science, and other disciplines in humanities and social sciences. The journal pursues to promote critical research and original scholarship on issues related to the scope of the journal theoretically empirically, and comparatively.

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From the Editors

With great excitement I am introducing to you and the academic world this new multidisciplinary journal, *International Journal of Religions and Peacebuilding (ISSN: 1595-3920)*. It is one of the journals from the stable of **AFGBOT Multidisciplinary Journals**. This is Volume 1 Number 1 of the journal. The journal came out of the passion for academic excellence among postgraduate students, upcoming scholars and already established academics. It aims at creating a platform for these aforementioned people to showcase their academic prowess and contribute to academic knowledge.

Religions and Peacebuilding are chosen as the major scope for the journal because of the interplay between the two disciplines and their roles in shaping the religious, social, political, spiritual understanding of people throughout the world. The scope is aimed at contributing to the peaceful coexistence of people thereby making the Goal 16 of the Sustainable Development Goals of the United Nations achievable by 2030 and even beyond.

I appreciate my partners and co-editors of **AFGBOT Multidisciplinary Journals**, Associate Professor Adekunle Otunla and Doctor Michael Gbadegesin, and the associate editors of this journal, Doctor Emmanuel O. Malomo, Rebecca Banjo, and Emmanuel Fasinu, for joining me in this noble task. Kudos to authors of papers in this first volume and first number of the journal for the sacrifice to be parts of this historic move. Papers in line with the scope of the journal and other cognate and related disciplines are welcome in the quarterly four-number-volume journal.

Thanks.

Adebayo Ola AFOLARANMI, PhD
Editor in Chief

Contents

1. **Towards Understanding Compromise as a Means of Conflict Resolution: An Exegesis of Genesis 13:8-9**
Adebayo Ola AFOLARANMI, PhD & Emmanuel UMAR, PhD
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14898602> 1–9
2. **Hermeneutical Approaches to Biblical Studies in African Context**
Isaac Folorunso OLUWALUSIN, PhD
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14902903> 10–24
3. **From Ethics to Sustainability: Artificial Intelligence (AI)'s Role in Transforming Christian Ministry Communication in Nigeria**
Segun Ayotunde OLULOWO, PhD & Samuel Ola OGUNJOBI, PhD
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14908090> 25–42
4. **Religious Conflicts and Their Impact on Africa's Future: Exploring the Path to Sustainable Peace and Development with the Support of Artificial Intelligence (AI)**
Olukunle Enoch OLUWARINDE, PhD
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14926778> 43–57
5. **Pastoral Pitfalls and Its Implications on Church Growth in Nigeria**
Samuel C. NWANKWO
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14965208> 58–70
6. **Congregationalism and Church Growth in the Baptist Denomination: Opportunities and Challenges**
Kayode Mike AMOLE & Adebayo Ola AFOLARANMI, PhD
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14967496> 71–81
7. **Christian Ministry in the Artificial Intelligence (AI) Era: Leveraging Digital Tools for Pastoral Care and Outreach in the 21st Century**
Stanley Osemudiamen OJIEABU & Adeniyi G. ABODUNRIN, PhD
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14968580> 82–98
8. **Reclaiming the Prophetic Mandate: Integrating the Prophetic Office within Anglican Priesthood in Ibadan South Diocese, Nigeria**
Andrew OLAJIDE
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14970339> 99–113
9. **From Shepherds to Strategists: The Intersection of Pastoral Ministry and Human Resource Management**
Samson Obaloluwa OJO
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15002879> 114–126
10. **Assessment of Socio-economic and Political Effects of 2020 and 2024 Recessions in Nigeria and their Implications for Sustainable Development**
Emmanuel Selome FASINU, John Adakole ELOCHE & Beatrice Jesutayo Titilayo OLANIYAN
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15006571> 127–146
11. **The Sacrificial Death of Jesus Christ and Its Implications for the Contemporary Church**
Peter Olanrewaju AWOJOBI & Emmanuel Olumuyiwa MALOMO
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15014645> 147–163
12. **Pentecostal Pastors' English Pronunciation Proficiency during Sermon Delivery: Youths Disposition and Engagement in Saki, Oyo State Nigeria**
Michael Olayinka GBADEGESIN, PhD
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15045605> 164–177

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**Towards Understanding Compromise
as a Means of Conflict Resolution: An
Exegesis of Genesis 13:8-9**

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Abstract

Conflict is inevitable in any society. Compromise has been identified as one of the means of conflict resolution. This paper aims at looking at compromise as a means of conflict resolution through an exegetical explanation of the event in Genesis 13:8-9. In the two biblical verses, it was discovered that Abraham (in particular) and Lot explored compromise to resolve the conflict that arose among their herders and parted ways amicably. Some supporting views of people are also presented in the paper before conclusion and some recommendations are made. It is concluded that people in conflict can explore compromise as a means of conflict resolution to reach a concession. It is, therefore, recommended that stakeholders in conflict resolution and peace study as well as other people who have an interest in resolving conflicts should always explore compromise as they explore other means of conflict resolution.

Keywords: compromise, conflict resolution, Genesis 13:8-9, Goal 16 of the Sustainable Development Goals of the United Nations, peaceful coexistence

Introduction

The term, conflict, can be described as a disagreement between two parties over an idea, ownership, or object. Conflicts are an integral part of human existence. They are inevitable, even in the case of intrapersonal conflicts, and talk less of interpersonal or intergroup conflicts. These conflicts have to be resolved to have the desirable peaceful coexistence among people. This is to achieve Goal Number Sixteen of the Sustainable Development Goals of the United Nations which has to do with “peaceful and non-violent societies.”¹ There have been many definitions of conflict resolution by many scholars. Simply, conflict resolution is a process of resolving disputes or disagreements. Conflict resolution aims at finding a peaceful solution or middle ground for warring factions. It sometimes involves compromise, negotiation, mediation, or diplomacy.

One of the means of conflict resolution is compromise. Compromise can be understood as a way of finding a consensus or reaching an agreement through mutual concessions. It entails surrendering some of one’s likings or inclinations to satisfy others. Compromise plays a significant role in resolving conflicts in that a balance is sought between conflicting parties or interests and reaching a concession that is acceptable to all parties involved in the conflict. In the words of Vojvodic, Martinovic and Pusic (2019), “people who are prone to use compromising style [of conflict resolution] believe that it is better to get something rather than nothing”.² These scholars also assert that “compromise tends to foster better relationship than competition, but not as well as it is in the case of collaboration.”²

This article aims to look at comprise as a means of conflict resolution through an exegetical explanation of the event in Genesis 13:8-9. Some supporting views of people are also presented in the paper before conclusion and some recommendations are made.

¹ O. Gaffney (2014). “Sustainable Development Goals: Improving Human and Planetary Wellbeing.” *Global Change*, 82, May 2014, 20. Available Online: <http://www.igbp.net/download/18.62dc35801456272b46d51/1399290813740/NL82-SDGs.pdf>

² Vojvodic, K., Martinovic, M., & Pusic, A. (2019). "Compromise Or Else: Managing Conflicts in the Negotiation Process." *40th International Scientific Conference on Economic and Social Development*, Buenos Aires, 10-11 May 2019, 39.

An Exegesis of Genesis 13:8-9

WTT Genesis 13:8

וַיֹּאמֶר אַבְרָם אֶל-לוֹט אֶל-נָא תְהִי מְרִיבָה בֵּינִי וּבֵינְךָ וּבֵין רַעֲיָי וּבֵין רַעֲיֶיךָ כִּי-אֲנָשִׁים אַחִים אָנֹכִנּוּ:

NAS Genesis 13:8 Then Abram said to Lot, "Please let there be no strife between you and me, nor between my herdsmen and your herdsmen, for we are brothers.

WTT Genesis 13:9

הֲלֹא כָל-הָאָרֶץ לִפְנֵיךָ הִפְרָד נָא מַעְלֵי אִם-הִשְׁמָאל וְאִמְנָה וְאִם-הַיְמִין וְאִשְׁמְאִילָה:

NAS Genesis 13:9 "Is not the whole land before you? Please separate from me: if *to the left*, then I will go to the right; or if *to the right*, then I will go to the left."

From the text above, Abraham was facing a dangerous outcome of an already existing conflict between his herdsmen and the herdsmen of his nephew, Lot. As he observed and being the head of the family, he moved into action and his actions can be seen in the choice of his words while addressing Lot from the text thus; אֶל-נָא תְהִי מְרִיבָה = "...Please let there be no strife". The combination of the two particles indicates that there is a burning issue on the ground that demands urgent action. The "אֶל-נָא" combination expresses the situation at hand as a complex one that needs urgent solution without delay. But by any means delay occurs the matter can cause unrepairable damage which may include loss of lives and properties. The particle אֶל when used alone is a negative adverbial particle used in Hebrew for request or prohibition with its object as a verb. The usage is emphatic and it goes along with an imperative verb where it becomes a command. The particle נָא is an interjection particle of homonym in Hebrew. It is also an enclitic particle of urgency. It has no specific word for its translation. It can either be translated as "please or listen to me". It also takes an imperative verb as its object. When it is attached to a verb, it expresses entreaty or admonition. It goes with an imperative verb to denote command.³

The combination of the two particles suggests that Abraham was in a tight situation that needed an urgent solution. Even though the usage of the particles appeared to look in a soft tone, both carried strong negation as well

³ BDB "אֶל-נָא" (2010 printed edition), 39 §408 II

as a persuasive command that gave no alternative to Lot other than to comply with Abraham's demand.

מְרִיבָה (*M^e ribah*) is a noun translated as "strife, quarrel, dispute, case, contentions and cause". The noun has a cognate only in Aramaic. It occurred 60 times in the bible. The noun "*riḅ*" is used for conflicts outside the realm of law cases and courts. Its first occurrence is in Genesis 13:7-8 where 'contention' occurred between the herdsmen before open fighting between the two parties. The term "*riḅ*" sometimes represents a dispute between two parties. This 'dispute' is set in the context of a mutual law structure binding both parties and a court which is empowered to decide and execute justice. This can be seen in the case of Moses and the Israelites when Israelites quarreled with Moses asserting that he did not keep his end of the bargain by adequately providing for them. Moses then appealed to the Judge, who in turn vindicated him by sending water from a rock smitten by Moses (Exodus 17:7) and decided who was the guilty party, Moses or Israelites. The contention may also be between two individuals as in Deuteronomy 25:1 where the two disputants go to court. Other passages include Isaiah 1:23 and Proverbs 25:8-9. The noun, therefore, occurs very rarely, it occurred only twice and it means "strife" in both places (Genesis 13:8; Numbers 17:14). The other rare cognate is "*yāriḅ*", it occurred three times and it means; disputant, opponent and adversary" (Psalm 35:1; Isaiah 49:25; Jeremiah 18:19)⁴.

The other phrase used by Abraham is כִּי־אָנָשִׁים אַתֶּם אֲנִי וְהוּנִי which is translated as "...we are men, brothers". This kind of expression in Hebrew is for those who are of the same family or those of the same tribe but is never used in relation to sonship. By this expression, it shows that Abraham and Lot are from the same family. This expression shows that Abraham is still showing some sort of caring for Lot despite the strife between their herdsmen and therefore was willing to bury whatever misunderstanding between their herdsmen.

הִפְרִד = this is a verb translated as "to divide, separate". It occurred twenty-five (25) times in the Holy Bible. Its first occurrence is Genesis 2:10 where it is used to denote dividing of the river in the Garden of Eden. Its second

⁴ W. E. Vine, et al. (1985). *Vine's Complete Expository Dictionary of Old and New Testament Words*. (Nashville: Thomas Nelson Publishers), 249–250.

occurrence is in the text under consideration (Genesis 13:9) where it expresses the separation of Abraham and Lot. The word often expresses separation of people from each other where sometimes it happens out of hostility as in the case of Jacob and Esau (Genesis 25:23), or as a result of economic status as the case stated in Proverbs 19:4 "...the poor is separated from his neighbor". In a general sense, the verb "pārad", "to separate" carries more negative than positive connotations.⁴ As Abraham continued with his discussion with Lot, he used another word that indicates clearly that Lot stepped on Abraham's nerves. The word לָאָבְרָם = is translated as "upon me". Abraham's choice of this word shows that from the narrator's point of view, Lot is a burden to Abraham at this point and thus separation was not simply out of convenience but out of necessity. This can be further seen in the inherent use of the negative particle and the particle of interjection of homonym as its antecedent⁵.

Even though the Bible narrative seems to be silent about the whereabouts of Lot when Abraham went to Egypt, the records of the Dead Sea Scrolls of Genesis Apocryphon (20-21) show that Lot not only went alongside Abraham to Egypt but also functioned as a spokesperson to Pharaoh's agents while in Egypt. He acted like the middle man connecting the marriage of Sarah and Pharaoh as he supported the position of Abraham when he said Sarah was his sister. While serving in that capacity, Lot acquired great wealth and he was not only given wealth but was also given an Egyptian woman as his wife as well as male and female servants. Abraham's position on letting Lot choose where he will dwell could be seen in the way he put it to Lot.

לָאָבְרָם this word is a verb derived from the noun "yāmîn" meaning "to go towards the right hand". Its usage in Genesis 13:9 signifies "direction toward". The word appeared 137 times in the Bible. In its usage in this passage, it is idiomatically used to mean 'southward' since the direction of south is on one's right hand when he faces eastward.⁴ לָאָבְרָם which is also transliterated as 'sēmōl' is translated as "to go towards the left". Here it is pointing to indicate direction which from the point of Abraham's with Lot points towards the northern part of Canaan. In this regard, Abraham might have been thinking of both of them to remain within the borders of the Promised Land.⁵ The choice of Abraham to use *Hiphil* verbs in directing Lot

⁵ Dan Rickett (2011). "Rethinking the Place and Purpose of Genesis 13." *Journal for the Study of the Old Testament*, (Sage Publication, September 2, 2011), 1 – 24.

to make a choice is to stress the fact that his message to Lot will not be misunderstood but rather it stands as a directive towards a definite point. He stressed his determination of his action to protect his interest which is peaceful co-existence. His expressions are contingent intentions but anything outside that will not be accommodated.⁶

Other Supporting Views on Compromise as a Means of Conflict Resolution

Ndung'u, Mbaro & Okumu (2021) have seen compromise as an essential element in negotiation and mediative dialogue.⁷ Compromise is a great aspect of mediation. Mediation is a process of assisting people in conflict to resolve their differences through the use of a neutral third party, which helps the conflicting parties in attaining a voluntary agreement. In pastoral counselling, the pastor is the arbiter who counsels the conflicting parties on what to do on how the conflicting would be settled. This is rather a conciliatory role. However, in mediation, the mediator assists the conflicting parties in reaching a compromise in resolving their conflict.⁸ This difference (and somehow relationship) was explained further by Nabwire (2016) in a study.⁹ In settlement mediation, disputing parties are encouraged to compromise to settle the conflicts between them and have a peaceful co-existence.¹⁰

⁶ W. Gesenius (2006). *Gesenius' Hebrew Grammar*. (Mineola: Dover Publication INC, 2006 revised), 319-320 §107-108

⁷ M. W. Ndung'u, P. Mbaro, & J. Okumu (2021). "Effectiveness of Negotiation in Resolving Family Conflict: Case of Kajiado North Sub-County, Kenya." *Journal of Research Innovation and Implications in Education*, 5(3), 215-224. Available Online: <https://jriiejournal.com/wp-content/uploads/2021/09/JRIIE-5-3-021.pdf>

⁸ A. O. Afolaranmi (2022). "Use of Social Media for Sustainable Peace by Church Pastors of the Nigerian Baptist Convention, 2010-2020." A PhD thesis submitted to the Department of Politics and International Relations, Faculty of Management and Social Sciences, Lead City University, Ibadan, Oyo State, Nigeria, 145.

⁹ C. J. Nabwire (2016). "Utilization and Effectiveness of Pastoral Counselling in the Management of Conflicts in Mainstream and Pentecostal Churches in Nakuru County, Kenya." A PhD thesis submitted to Graduate School of Egerton University.

¹⁰ A. M. Hamza & M. Todorovic (2017). "Peaceful Settlement of Disputes." *Global Journal of Commerce and Management Perspective*, 6(1), January-February 2017, 11-

In a study carried out by one of these writers,⁸ one of the respondents identified reaching compromise as an attempt to resolving conflicts among conflicting parties. In the words of this respondent, “I make efforts to let the conflicting people reach a point of ‘give and take.’”¹¹ In this situation, Howell (2014) opined that “the parties accept that there are times when one must be ready to set apart individual wants and needs in preference for others in order to find a ‘common ground’.”¹²

Although compromise as a means of conflict resolution strategy has not been giving desirable results in resolving religious conflicts in Nigeria, especially in interfaith situation as asserted by Ogbuehi (2016)¹³, compromise has been working for resolving conflicts among church members because “they share the common beliefs.”¹¹ Afolaranmi (2021) has emphasized this issue of “give and take” in asserting that “there is no conflict resolution strategy that can work in any situation where every parting in a conflict is insisting to have his/her way.”¹⁴

Conclusion

Compromise is one of the good means of resolving conflicts and promoting peaceful coexistence. As Abraham and Lot explored in the exegetical biblical verses in this paper and parted ways amicably, people in conflicts can also explore this means of conflict resolution and reach a concession as one

17. Available Online: <https://www.longdom.org/articles/peaceful-settlement-of-disputes.pdf>

¹¹ Samuel AK Olaleye, interview by one of the researchers, Ibadan, June 2, 2021.

¹² S. E. Howell (2014). “Conflict Management: A Literature Review and Study.” *Radiology Management*, September/October 2014. Available Online: http://www.ahra.org/AM/Downloads/OI/qc/RM365_p14-23_Features.pdf

¹³ F. I. Ogbuehi (2016). “Critical Appraisal of Dialogue as a Strategy for Religious Conflict Resolution in Nigeria.” *Journal of Religion and Human Relations*, 8(2), 167-168.

¹⁴ A. O. Afolaranmi (2021). “Conflict Resolution Strategies in Resolving Religious Conflict in Nigeria.” *Academia Letters*. Article 874. Available Online: <https://doi.org/10.20935/AL874>

conflicting party ‘gives’ some aspects of their interests and ‘takes’ some aspects of the interests of the other conflicting party.

Recommendations

Based on the conclusion above, it is recommended that:

1. Stakeholders in conflict resolution and peace study as well as other people who have an interest in resolving conflicts should always explore compromise as they explore other means of conflict resolution.
2. Conflicting parties should be ready to reach a consensus as they mutually agree to surrender some aspects of their interests and take some aspects of the interests of the other conflicting parties.

This will likely achieve Goal Number Sixteen of the Sustainable Development Goals of the United Nations which aims at peaceful and non-violent societies before 2030.

References

- Afolaranmi, A. O. (2021). "Conflict Resolution Strategies in Resolving Religious Conflict in Nigeria." *Academia Letters*, Article 874. Available Online: <https://doi.org/10.20935/AL874>
- Afolaranmi, A. O. (2022). "Use of Social Media for Sustainable Peace by Church Pastors of the Nigerian Baptist Convention, 2010-2020." A PhD thesis submitted to the Department of Politics and International Relations, Faculty of Management and Social Sciences, Lead City University, Ibadan, Oyo State, Nigeria.
- BDB “שְׁלָח” (2010 printed edition), 39 §408 II
- Gaffney, O. (2014). "Sustainable Development Goals: Improving Human and Planetary Wellbeing." *Global Change*, 82, May 2014, 20. Available Online: <http://www.igbp.net/download/18.62dc35801456272b46d51/139929081374/0/NL82-SDGs.pdf>
- Gesenius, W. (2006). *Gesenius' Hebrew Grammar*. (Mineola: Dover Publication INC, 2006 revised), 319-320 §107-108
- Hamza, A. M. & Todorovic, M. (2017). "Peaceful Settlement of Disputes." *Global Journal of Commerce and Management Perspective*, 6(1), January-

February 2017, 11-17. Available Online:

<https://www.longdom.org/articles/peaceful-settlement-of-disputes.pdf>

- Howell, S. E. (2014). "Conflict Management: A Literature Review and Study." *Radiology Management*, September/October 2014. Available Online: http://www.ahra.org/AM/Downloads/OI/qc/RM365_p14-23_Features.pdf
- Nabwire, C. J. (2016). "Utilization and Effectiveness of Pastoral Counselling in the Management of Conflicts in Mainstream and Pentecostal Churches in Nakuru County, Kenya." A PhD thesis submitted to Graduate School of Egerton University.
- Ndung'u, M. W., Mbaro, P., & Okumu, J. (2021). "Effectiveness of Negotiation in Resolving Family Conflict: Case of Kajiado North Sub-County, Kenya." *Journal of Research Innovation and Implications in Education*, 5(3), 215-224. Available Online: <https://jriiejournal.com/wp-content/uploads/2021/09/JRIIE-5-3-021.pdf>
- Ogbuehi, F. I. (2016). "Critical Appraisal of Dialogue as a Strategy for Religious Conflict Resolution in Nigeria." *Journal of Religion and Human Relations*, 8(2), 167-168.
- Rickett, D. (2011). "Rethinking the Place and Purpose of Genesis 13." *Journal for the Study of the Old Testament*, (Sage Publication, September 2, 2011), 1-24.
- Vine, W. E., et al. (1985). *Vine's Complete Expository Dictionary of Old and New Testament Words*. (Nashville: Thomas Nelson Publishers), 249-250.
- Vojvodic, K., Martinovic, M., & Pusic, A. (2019). "Compromise Or Else: Managing Conflicts in the Negotiation Process." *40th International Scientific Conference on Economic and Social Development*, Buenos Aires, 10-11 May 2019.

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**Hermeneutical Approaches to Biblical
Studies in African Context**

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Abstract

African biblical hermeneutics is the re-reading of the Christian scripture from a premeditatedly Afrocentric perspective. Biblical Studies in African context is an amalgamation of multiple interpretive methods, approaches and foci that reflect a creative engagement of the African cosmological reality and the bible. Majority of African Christians predominantly use Eurocentric cosmology and *anglo saxon* as an official language of interpretation of the bible to the detriment of Afrocentric hermeneutics. The onus of this paper is an evaluation of Afrocentric interpretation of the Bible in African context. Descriptive analysis method was used to carry out this research which focuses on the development of African Biblical Hermeneutics in the region of African nations, namely: Central Africa, Eastern Africa, Horn of Africa, Southern Africa and Western Africa. Findings show that, Biblical Studies in Africa is characterized as both innovative and reactionary. Conclusively, African biblical hermeneutics is contextual since interpretation is always done in a particular context. Therefore, the analysis of the biblical text should be done from the perspective of an African world-view and culture. It recommended therefore that African Biblical Scholars and Hermeneutics should lay more emphasis on the interpretation of the bible in Afrocentric cosmology and languages in textual analysis of the scripture instead of Eurocentricism.

Keywords: Africa, Biblical Studies, Culture, Eurocentricism, Hermeneutics

Introduction

African biblical hermeneutics is a methodological resource that makes African social cultural contexts the subject of interpretation. This is a methodology that reappraises ancient biblical tradition and African world-views, cultures and life experiences, with the purpose of correcting the effect of the cultural, ideological conditioning to which Africa and Africans have been subjected in the business of biblical interpretation. It is the rereading of the Christian scripture from a premeditatedly Afrocentric perspective. African biblical hermeneutics is contextual since interpretation is always done in a particular context. Specifically, it means that the analysis of the biblical text is done from the perspective of an African world-view and culture.

In the history of biblical interpretation, four major types of hermeneutics have emerged: the literal, moral, allegorical and anagogical. Literal interpretation asserts that a biblical text is to be interpreted according to the “plain meaning” conveyed by its grammatical construction and historical context. Interpretation of Scripture occurs within one's worldview and culture, which enhances our understanding and ability to apply Scripture in the world. However, few books address Bible interpretation from an African perspective and no other textbook uses the intercultural approach found here.

The term ‘hermeneutics traditionally refers to the study of how one interprets a text or work of art; while works on hermeneutics in this broader sense are helpful for reading the Bible. The Bible has been read in Africa since the apostolic age. The history of Christianity in Africa could be written as the story of African readers understanding, translating, interpreting, explaining and applying the teachings of the Bible. Nevertheless, with the exception of the section on Ethiopian hermeneutics, this article focuses on the main developments that have taken place in English-speaking African Biblical Hermeneutics since the middle of the twentieth century. This article focuses on resources that relate more directly to ‘biblical hermeneutics, that is, the study of how one interprets biblical texts. This branch of knowledge includes both the general principles that guide biblical study and the specific methods that are used.

Most of the biblical interpretation in Africa is done by ordinary Christians or church leaders at the ‘grassroots’ level, for example, in worship, prayer

and preaching. Thus, biblical hermeneutics is not limited to academic study or even written forms of interpretation, it encompasses both verbal and non-verbal communication. Given the variety of resources available, this article uses the term biblical hermeneutics to refer to both theories of interpretation, such as inculturation hermeneutics, and the principles and methods implicit in practices of interpretation, such as those found in African Independent Churches. With the exception of the Ethiopian tradition, which traces its origins back to the early church, African biblical interpretation is characterised by a strong awareness of the distance between imported readings of the biblical text and the African reader. Western missionaries brought their own Western readings of the Bible to African contexts, with the result many African readers faced a 'double' hermeneutical gap when approaching the biblical text: between ancient texts and the contemporary situation and between Western readings and African realities.

In response, African biblical interpreters have developed their own readings of the Bible to better address the lives of African Christians. Comparative approaches have emphasised the similarities between biblical and African cultural contexts. Furthermore, the African cultural context has come to be seen as a valuable resource for biblical study. These developments have been accompanied by a growing realisation of the importance of the cultural and social location of the reader in biblical interpretation. In a number of ways, African readers may be much better placed than Western readers to understand the Bible in African context.

The word Bible is derived from the Greek word *Biblion* meaning *a book*. This is the name used in describing the holy book of the Jews and Christians containing the word of God recorded by Holy men inspired by the Holy Spirit. The Holy Bible is known by other titles such as *the scripture*, *the writing*, *The Word of God*, etc Luke 4:17, Mark 12:10 and Hebrew. 4:12. In fact, there are some unique features that distinguish the Bible from other type of books, source and authorship reasons for various translations and some other books are not included in the common versions of the Bible.

Facts about the Bible

Bible, although it is a library, (as Jerome) named the Bible as the divine library in 4th Century A. D. The Bible is a story, a grand story that moves on from commencement to the end. In the Bible all together, these subjects are found:

- (a) Law – in the books of Moses called Pentateuch
- (b) History – in Samuel, Kings, Chronicles and other books
- (c) Philosophy – in the books of Job and Ecclesiastics
- (d) Poetry – in the Psalms and Songs of Solomon
- (e) Prophecy – in Isaiah, Jeremiah, Ezekiel and the Minor Prophets
- (f) Doctrine – in the Epistles
- (g) Revelations – in the Apocalypse and Daniel
- (h) Geography – in the book of Acts, etc.

The Bible unlike others books, a divine revelation, a progressive revelation, a revelation of God to man, communicated through men, moves on smoothly from its beginning to its great end. The Bible history takes one back to the unknown past of eternity, and its prophecies takes us into the otherwise unknown future.

The Bible represents the word of God to the world but came in culture of a particular people who got the message and expressed it in ways intelligible to them. It is necessary to find relevant ways of bringing the Bible message to the African languages. This enables the gospel of Jesus to be expressed and applied in a variety of ways using African languages to the Africans. Christian message provides the answer to the questions implied in human existence.

African Countries with Christianity as the Religion of the Majority

Rank	Country	Region	% of national population affiliated to Christianity
1	Sao tome and Principe	Central Africa	97.0
2	Democratic Republic of the Congo	Central Africa	95.8
3	Angola	Central Africa	95.0
4	Rwanda	East Africa	93.6
5	Seychelles	East Africa	93.1
6	Equatorial Guinea	Central Africa	93.0
7	Lesotho	Southern Africa	90.0
8	Namibia	Southern Africa	90.0

9	Swaziland	Southern African	90.0
10	Zambia	East Africa	87.0
11	Republic of the Congo	Central Africa	85.9
12	Liberia	West Africa	85.5
13	Cape Verde	West Africa	85.0
14	Reunion	East Africa	84.9
15	Uganda	East Africa	84.0
16	Zimbabwe	Southern Africa	84.0
17	Central African Republic	Central Africa	80.3
18	Malawi	East Africa	79.9
19	South Africa	Southern Africa	79.7
20	Kenya	East Africa	78.0
21	Burundi	East Africa	75.0
22	Gabon	Central Africa	73.0
23	Botswana	Southern Africa	71.6
24	Ghana	West Africa	71.2
25	Cameroon	Central Africa	69.2
26	Ethiopia	Horn of Africa	62.8
27	Eritrea	Horn of Africa	62.5
28	Tanzania	East Africa	61.4
29	South Sudan	East Africa	60.5
30	Nigeria	West Africa	58.0
31	Mozambique	East Africa	56.1

Source: Parrinder 1969

Biblical Inculturation

According to Omoyeni and Arthur (2013), Biblical Studies in Africa does not simply take the questions, methods, presuppositions and interpretations that have been arrived at in the western world and uncritically appropriate them in African biblical settings. Rather, Biblical studies in Africa is borne out of the African biblical scholar engaging the Bible free (or as free as possible) of any trappings of western hermeneutical presuppositions and interests. Dube and West (2000) noted that Nigerian Justin Ukpong

characterizes the lynchpin of African biblical interpretation as ‘an encounter between the Biblical text and the African context’ that is not hesitant to address the past, present and future in light of the biblical text. So, Biblical studies in Africa takes both the African and the biblical realities as equal partners in *dialogue*, resulting in a distinctive juxtaposition of questions, approaches and interpretations.

Gerald West, a South African biblical scholar, agrees and is emphatic that Biblical Studies in Africa remain integral to the larger discipline of African theology: ‘The separation of biblical studies from other theological disciplines, so common elsewhere, cannot be allowed to happen in an African biblical study.’ West noted that Africa was on the verge of an African biblical scholarship discipline that he maintained would and should look distinct from the biblical studies that has been predominant in the west.

The intent would not be to reject the grammatical-historical and literary studies that have dominated biblical studies in the west, but to recognize that, as African theologians have said, western theological education remains fairly sterile in addressing African concerns. Therefore, even when western methods are utilized by African biblical scholars, they are incorporated into a creative impulse that even original proponents may never have envisioned.

Paradoxically, majority of the African biblical scholars in the last half century or so have been trained in western academies. When Norwegian K. (2002) analysed 87 Old Testament/Hebrew Bible dissertations written by African scholars between 1967 and 2000, the majority of those written in western institutions did not bring the African backgrounds or contexts to bear on the writing.

G. West’s sentiments echo perspectives proposed by earlier African theologians, probably best articulated by Kwesi Dickson of Ghana (1984). While Dickson wants to separate ‘culture’ and ‘religion’, it seems unnecessary, since in both the biblical and the African worldviews the cultural and the religious are so closely entwined that all aspects of life have religious meaning. Biblical Studies in Africa thus incorporates all spheres of life in its purview (Meenan 2014). To this, West (2008) adds the need to have a live African interpreter (African-ness unspecified), and also the need to distinguish between the scholar and the ‘ordinary’ reader who in essence is any African person, not a fictive personality, and who reads beside the trained African biblical scholar. According to Loba-Mkole and Wendland (2005), this distinction is important for West as he points out the fact that

under South African apartheid, the African communities were denied a hearing, formal education and political rights, which effectively silenced them. This is a reading 'with' the ordinary reader, and not reading 'on behalf of' the ordinary reader.

Overall, then, Biblical Studies in Africa refuses to deal with the Bible simply as an ancient text and demands that it be engaged to deal with present concerns, addressing issues that resonate with African (and world) realities. Accordingly, Biblical Studies in Africa embraces more than just exegetical interests but privileges hermeneutical concerns (Villa-Vicencio 1992). For example, Musa Dube's (2000) groundbreaking study, *Postcolonial Feminist Interpretation of the Bible*, while classified as biblical studies, draws from a wide array of disciplines including African philosophy, African literary studies, and study of African religions, and unapologetically incorporates them under the rubric of a new discipline, Postcolonial Feminist Biblical Studies. This process has remained constant in Biblical studies in Africa, having been christened initially more positively as *inculturation* (Ukpong 1995), and more recently as *decolonization* (Abogunrin, 2005) of the biblical text from western imperialism.

According to Ukpon (1999) African biblical scholars have a tendency to gravitate to texts that are not only relevant to their African reality, but which may not usually be in the purview of western biblical scholars (e.g., texts on polygamy, healing, spirits, etc.). As African philosophers Mudimbe and Kilonzo (2012) explain, this process of 'Africanization is a post-colonial phenomenon concerned with adapting modalities of belief and rethinking of rituals. Christian independency challenges colonial representations of ways of believing'.

Furthermore, African biblical scholars perceive a deeper paradigm: in the same way that Christianity was shaped by its encounter with the Gentile Greco-Roman world (Acts 15; Galatians) from its origins as a Jewish sect called 'the Way' (Acts 9.2), African biblical scholars see the encounter with African contexts as a watershed moment in the shaping of Christianity beyond the African context (Mofokeng 1987). Some of the western scholars who have seen potential benefit of this aspect of Biblical Studies in Africa reckon a possibility of 'a reading with ethical accountability' in biblical studies fostered by African Biblical Studies' demand to emphasize the present (Burridge 2007).

Nevertheless, this argument has not gone without detractors who have felt that perhaps the African background was being uncritically and

overzealously appropriated by African theologians. In this camp, Nigeria's Byang Kato's writing is probably the best known, even though there are others like Burkina Faso's Tite Tienou (1984), who also offer similar criticism. In his strongly dissenting *Theological Pitfalls in Africa*, Kato bemoaned what he saw as too much exultation of 'African culture, philosophy and religion beyond proportion'. Such criticism, however, fails to perceive the fact that it perpetuates the colonialist negative evaluation of the ways that African religious cosmology communicates realities about the Christian God. It also fails to be cognizant of the fact that the African religious reality is entrenched in the entirety of the African reality and inevitably seeps through any African theological construction, inadvertently or otherwise.

The issue of inculturation of Biblical studies in Africa and who can do the inculturation is a question that lingers. For instance, can non-Africans do African biblical interpretation? Ukpong (1999) has rightly maintained that the incorporation of African elements into the historical and literary readings of the Bible is what allows for African biblical interpretation to arrive at distinct conclusions from those made by western counterparts on the same texts. In this regard, then, it would seem that it is the African content that determines whether a writing is engaging in African biblical interpretation.

Historic Overview of Biblical Studies in Africa

Biblical Studies in Africa is connected in complex ways to Christianity in Africa. The origins of Christianity in Africa remain debated. Some scholars point to its biblical beginnings (e.g., the conversion of the Ethiopian eunuch in Acts 8.26-39), while others identify Christianity's origins with the arrival of European missionaries in the African continent, south of the Sahara, starting in the fifteenth century (Isichei 1995). The former see a tradition running through such significant Christian figures as Augustine, Origen and Tertullian, among others, as the true fathers of Biblical Studies in Africa (Ngong 2012). Opponents point out that this form of Christianity never spread beyond Egypt, Ethiopia, and Nubia in northeastern Africa.

Either way, current African biblical scholarship is neither simply a product of western missionary evangelizing in Africa nor a totally independent African formulation (Ngong 2012). The development of a distinctly scholarly African theological reflection in the last fifty years of post-colonialism has been primarily driven by African theologians grappling with concerns in

their specific African contexts, utilizing scholarship learned in or borrowed from the west. There are two primary streams that have developed in this process: (1) reclaiming of positive values of African religious realities as foundations of an authentic African Christianity, and (2) construction of a biblical response to contemporary concerns of African communities.

According to Gerald West, African biblical Scholars have turned tools acquired from the west 'against the damage done by western missionary and colonial forces.' The arrival of missionaries in Africa, while crucial for the growth of Christianity in Africa, was also inextricably bound to European imperialism and colonialism (Sanneh, 1989). And even though the wave of European missionary activity in Sub-Saharan Africa, with their Christian schools, church plantings, and Bible translations into local African languages, no doubt helped establish Christianity in the continent over time, perhaps the most portent instruments of Christian expansion were primarily African converts who evangelized other Africans (Oliver, 1992).

The following thematic and periodic outline is not meant to imply that these were the only methods in their respective time spans or that there are no overlaps. Rather, it is a heuristic tool for sorting through the diverse field of methods and foci that have characterized Biblical Studies in Africa. The interplay between Biblical Studies in Africa and the historical and political realities, especially of the post-independence periods, is meant to highlight the tendency of Africa Biblical Studies to focus on the present in contrast to the ancient.

Impositions of Colonizers Interpretations

The colonial period is between 1880s and 1980s. The beginning of colonization on the African continent is usually set around the infamous Berlin conference of 1884 that saw European powers (largely Holland, Belgium, England, France, Portugal, and Spain) subdivide among themselves the African continent for European conquest and occupation. Musa Dube maintains that at the core of both the imposition of colonialism and the subsequent work for African political independence was a struggle founded on the appropriation, interpretation and application of the Bible. Colonial formal education was subsequently set up to do two things through two mechanisms: (1) missionary schools aimed to provide the African converts with the ability to read the Bible for themselves (or so they claimed), and (2) government schools sought to produce a colonial workforce only at the clerical level at best.

The Bible was viewed by Africans as complicit in the colonial process in at least two ways: (1) as official religion of the colonizers, it provided the grounds for an African religious genocide, and (2) it gave theological support to military subjugation of Africans in the guise of Christianization. The collusion (intentional or not) of European missionaries and colonial administrators solidified, for the colonized, the imperializing role of the Bible as part of the colonial project, even as, paradoxically, the Africans converted to Christianity (Mbuvi, 2014).

A statement of unclear origin, but attributed to Kenya's first president Mzee Jomo Kenyatta, encapsulates this interplay between the Bible and colonialism in Africa: 'When the Missionaries arrived, the Africans had the Land and the Missionaries had the Bible. They taught us how to pray with our eyes closed. When we opened our eyes, they had the land and we had the Bible' (Walker, 2002). Thus, the general perspective of the European missionaries to Africa was a kind of schizophrenia between a deep 'Christian' compassion for the Africans as peoples (or a hoodwinking of the people using the Bible), and a deep disdain and judgment, based on the same Christian convictions, of Africa cultural religious reality. The latter was judged to be evil, satanic, primitive, and so on.

Conversion to Christianity for Africans under European missionaries, as a result, usually meant abandonment of everything African and an embrace of everything European (Anderson, 1970). And even the most sympathetic of European missionaries to African cultures seemed only to find the redeemable elements in African communities to be those that could find parallel or resemblance in the Bible or western philosophical structures (Tempels, 1959).

The colonial period's subjugation of African peoples involved indoctrination of the African subjects to European methodologies that aligned with the European interpretations of the Bible. Not only was the Bible used as a means of justifying the presence of the missionaries (and subsequently colonialists), it was also used to pacify the colonized (Memmi, 1965). As J.B. Stanfield explains, 'while academic education was to be given to European and Asian children, African children were to receive industrial and agricultural training. Christian teaching became compulsory and African customs and traditions were subsequently neglected'. When, in response, Africans formed African independent schools that would allow aspects of African culture and realities to be part of education, they were promptly shut down by the colonialists on the pretext that Africans did not have the

financial and organizational skills to run educational institutions (Stanfield, 2005). The result was a systemic erosion and exorcising of African cultural and religious reality from among the early converts to Christianity, essentially forcing them to adopt European languages, cultures and values as a means of becoming Christians. In essence, the early African convert to Christianity could only read and interpret the Bible from the standpoint of the European colonizer, resulting in awkwardly Europeanized renditions of Bibles, hymnbooks, catechetical material, ecclesiastical groups and forms of worship (Baeta 1968).

Translations of Bible into African Languages

Bible translations into African languages started with European missionaries in the 1800s and continue today with such organizations as a global faith none profit that works with local community around the world to develop language solution that expand possibility for a better life, largely run by a mix of local native translators with some support from nonnative 'experts' (Noss, 2007). The driving force was a desire to have the Bible available in the African languages for the new converts. African biblical scholars have highlighted some of the problems caused by cultural blindness that early translations created in African theological thinking (Mbuwayesango, 2001). On the other hand, Lamin Sanneh's (1989) has argued that there were fortuitous and unforeseen benefits of European led Bible translations into African languages, maintaining that the translations formed the nexus of independent theological formulations that were eventually to result in both indigenous African Churches and a distinct African theology.

Building on Sanneh's propositions, Bible translation has been shown to have generated authentic African biblical interpretations by allowing the reading of the Bible in African mother-tongues and within the sphere of African cosmological reality (Bediako, 1996; Gathogo and Kinyua, 2010). Translations into African languages allowed the African reader freedom to make associations with their African linguistic and social realities in interpretation of the Bible independent of the encumbrances of reading it in a foreign language thus arriving at authentically African biblical readings (Mojola, 2007).

Construction of African Christian Identity

It is no surprise that following the political independence of African countries from European colonialism starting in the late 1950s through the 1980s, recovery/ redemption of the African cultural-religious past became the primary focus of African theologians (Idowu, 1962). Political independence seemed to motivate African theologians to construct an African Christian identity that not only removed the stigma placed on African religious reality by European missionaries but also make it foundational in formulating an African Christianity that was also both uncompromisingly African and authentically Christian (Bediako, 1996).

Consequently, African theological projects sought to establish the inherent compatibility of African religious reality to the Bible message by arguing that African concepts of God were intrinsically monotheistic (Idowu 1962), theorizing that the concept of life after death (the living-dead) in African religions was compatible with the Christian concept of resurrection (Mbiti, 1975), maintaining that the African belief in spirits was consistent with the biblical belief in spirits and demons (Green, 1995), and more. This 'hermeneutic of rehabilitation', or 'hermeneutic of resonance', between African realities and the biblical text (Green, 1995) became a primary occupation of the African theologians from then on.

The different emphases in interpretation, are not merely due to personal situatedness, but also stem from deep theological beliefs about God, creation, humanity, revelation and salvation. Grouping the approaches according to interpretive tradition or movement helps to make these theological assumptions more explicit. First, there are sections on the Ethiopian tradition and the African Independent Church movement. Next, there are 'classic' approaches in African Christian Theology, including Inculturation and Intercultural hermeneutics, Liberation and Black hermeneutics, Feminist and Women's hermeneutics, and Contextual Bible Study and Ordinary Readers' hermeneutics. These are followed by a section on the Pentecostal movement. The article concludes with more recent approaches, such as Reconstruction, Postcolonial and Mother Tongue hermeneutics.

For some of the luminaries of African theological scholarship such as John Mbiti and Mulago gwa Cikala (followed by Bediako 1996), it became fundamentally crucial to not only recover African religions as complex and sophisticated systems in and of themselves, but also to show their preparatory nature for the Gospel message. In this regard, African religions

were perceived as equivalents of the Old Testament, preparing the African for the arrival of the Gospel of Jesus Christ (*praeparatio evangelica*) (Cikala 1965): 'In missiological jargon, these [African] Traditional Religions will have been a real *praeparatio evangelica* (preparation for the Gospel); and it is now up to African theologians to interpret the meaning of that preparation for the Gospel in the African context of not only the past, but today and tomorrow' (Mbiti 1970b: 36).

Conclusion

Biblical Studies in Africa is a product of biblical compilation. This survey began from the bible. The bible represents the word of God sent to the world of which the African Biblical scholars expressed and applied in African languages to the African Christian.

Biblical Studies in Africa grows in its adherents and increasingly gain credence with biblical scholars beyond African biblical scholarship. Its contributions become more apparent. This article highlights the contributions it adds to Biblical Studies by challenging certain Western readings of the Bible and shows distinctive interpretive approaches that introduce new perspectives in interpreting the Bible.

This paper recommends that the Biblical Studies in Africa should be more encouraged among the African Bible scholarship. African church denominations also need to be deeper in interpreting biblical messages in their local tongues. The focus on the present in Biblical Studies in Africa should be seen as complimentary, pushing for all-round exegesis and hermeneutics.

References

- Abogunrin S.O. (2005). *Decolonization of Biblical Interpretation in Africa*, Ibadan, Nigeria Association of Biblical Studies.
- Anderson J. (1970). *The Struggle for the School: The Interaction of the Missionary, Colonial Government and Nationalist Enterprise in the Development of Formal Education*. Kenya, London, Longman
- Baeta C.G. (1968). *Christianity in Tropical Africa*, Oxford, Oxford University Press.
- Bediako K. (1996). *Christianity in Africa: The Renewal of Non-Western Region*, Maryknoll, NY: Orbis.
- Burridge R.A. (2007). *Imitating Jesus: An Inclusive Approach to New Testament Ethics*, Grand Rapid, Eerdmans
- Cikala M. (1965). *Un Visage Africain du Christianisme: L'union Vitale Bantu a l'union Vitale Ecclesiale*, Paris Presence Africaine.

- Dickson K. (1984) *Theology in Africa*, Maryknoll, NY: Orbis.
- Dube M.W., and G. West (2000). *The Bible in Africa: Translations, Trajectories and Trends*, Leiden, Brill.
- Green J.B. (1995). *Hearing the New Testament: Strategies for Interpretation*, Grand Rapids, Eerdmans.
- Holter K. (2002). *Old Testament Research for Africa: A Critical Analysis and Annotated Biography of Africa Old Testament Dissertation, 1967-2000*, New York, Peter Lang.
- Idowu E.B.E. (1962). *Oludumare: God in Yoruba Belief*, London, Longmans.
- Isichei E. (1995). *A Story of Christianity in Africa: From Antiquity to the Present*, Grand Rapids, Eerdmans.
- Kato B. (1975). *Theological Pitfalls in Africa*, Nairobi, Evangel Publishing House.
- Loba-Mkole J.C. and E.R. Wendland (2005) *Interacting with Scriptures in Africa*, Nairobi, Acton
- Mbiti J.S. (1970). *The Future of Christianity in Africa*, *Communio Viatorum-Theological Quarterly* 13: 19-38.
- Mbiti J.S. (1975). *Introduction to African Religion*, London, Heinemann.
- Mbuvi AM. (2014). *Christology and Cultus in 1Peter: An African (Kenya) Appraisal, in G.L. Green, S.T. Pardue and K.K. Yeo(ed), Jesus without Borders: Christology in the Majority World*, Grand Rapids, Eerdmans.
- Mbuwayesango D. (2001). *How Local Divine Powers were Suppressed: A case study of the Mwari of The Shona*, Dube (ed)
- Meenan A.J., (2014). Biblical Hermeneutics in an African Context, *Journal of Inductive Biblical Studies*
- Memmi A. (1965). *The Colonizer and the Colonized*, Miami, Orion.
- Mofokeng T.A. (1987). *A Basis for a Relevant Theology for Botswana*, Mission Studies 4
- Mojola A.O. (2007) *Bible Translation in Africa*, in P.A. Noss(ed), *A History of Bible Translation*, Rome, Edizioni di Storia e Letteratura
- Mudimbe V. and S.M. Kilonzo (2012). *Philosophy of Religion on African Ways of Believing in E.K. B. Bonggmba (ed), The Wiley-Blackwell Companion to African Religion*, West Sussex, Blackwell
- Ngong D.T. (2012). *Christianity in Africa*, in E.K. Bonggmba (ed), *The Wiley-Blackwell Companion to Africa Religions*, West Sussex, Blackwell
- Noss P.A. (2007). *A History of Bible Translation*, Rome, Edizioni di Storia e Letteratura
- Oliver R., *The African Experience*, New York, Harper Collins, 1992
- Omenyo C.N. and W.A. Arthur (2013) *The Bible Says! Neo-Prophetic Hermeneutics in Africa*. Studies in World Christianity
- Sanneh L. (1989). *Translating the message: The Missionary Impact on Culture*, Maryknoll, NY: Orbis

- Stanfield J.B. (2005). *Kenya's Forgotten Independent School Movement, Economic Affairs 25:82-84.*
- Temples P. (1959). *Bantu Philosophy trans from La Philosophie Bantoue*, Paris, Presence Africaine,
- Tienou T. (1984). *The Church in African Theology: Discription and Analysis of Hermeneutical Presuppositions*, in D.A. Carson (ed), *Biblical Interpretation and the Church: Text And Context*, Exeter, Paternoster
- Ukpong J.S. (1995). *Rereading the Bible in African Eyes: Inculturation and Hermeneutics*, JTSA.
- Ukpong J.S. (1999). *Can African Old Testament Scholarship Escape the Historical Critical Approach?* Newsletter on African Old Testament Scholarship 7:2-5, 1999
- Villa-Vicencio C. (1992). *A Theology of Reconstruction Nation Building and Human Rights*, Cambridge, Cambridge University Press.
- Walker J.F. (2002) *A Certain Curve of Horn: The Hundred-year Quest for the Giant Sable Antelope of Angola*, New-York, Groove Press.
- West G.O. (2008). *Biblical Hermeneutics in Africa*, London, SPCK.

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**From Ethics to Sustainability:
Artificial Intelligence (AI)'s Role in
Transforming Christian Ministry
Communication in Nigeria**

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Abstract

Situated within Nigeria's dynamic Christian landscape, this study examines how Artificial Intelligence (AI) is transforming communication in Christian ministry. It focuses on AI's potential to enhance outreach, engagement, and sustainability within Nigerian churches. Employing the Social Shaping of Technology (SST) framework alongside Theological Ethics, the research explores how AI tools interact with Nigeria's social, ethical, and theological values. Using a library-based methodology, the study evaluates practical AI applications—such as chatbots for personalized pastoral care and virtual reality for immersive worship—to demonstrate their capacity to streamline operations and foster inclusivity. Theological Ethics is applied to address challenges like fairness, transparency, and inclusivity, ensuring AI aligns with core Christian values. The SST framework highlights the dynamic relationship between technological innovation and human agency, emphasizing the need for responsible AI integration. The study fills a gap in the literature on ethical and sustainable AI use in

Nigerian Christian ministry, suggesting that, when implemented thoughtfully, AI can improve communication and accessibility without replacing essential human interaction. This research offers actionable insights for church leaders, guiding them to balance innovation with ethical principles and to pursue collaborative innovation and ethical oversight, ensuring that AI serves as a transformative tool aligned with Christian mission and values.

Keywords: Artificial Intelligence, Christian Ministry, Ethical Innovation, Theological Ethics, Sustainable Practices

Introduction

In Nigeria, the rapid advancement of Artificial Intelligence (AI) is transforming how Christian ministries communicate and engage with their congregations. AI is built to work like an intelligent human using power tools like chatbots, language translators, and content creators. These tools help people communicate faster, making it easier and more inclusive for everyone (Campbell 2019:45). Artificial Intelligence (AI) in Nigerian ministries, will be essential for sharing the Gospel, providing spiritual guidance, and building community, now have new opportunities to extend their outreach. For example, virtual sermons, social media campaigns, and personalized emails enable ministries to reach even remote or underserved regions (Smith and Jones 2021:112). However, these benefits come with ethical challenges. Issues such as privacy, algorithmic bias, and the need for AI tools to reflect core Christian values are significant, since technology is not neutral and can shape societal interactions (Brown 2020:67).

AI's potential to bridge language and cultural barriers is particularly valuable in Nigeria, a country of diverse languages and cultures. AI-powered translation services and virtual platforms can help ensure that all community members—especially those from marginalized groups—are included (Verbeek 2011:54). Nonetheless, ministries must use these technologies responsibly, safeguarding personal privacy and addressing biases inherent in AI systems (Coeckelbergh 2020:29).

Sustainability is also a major concern. Traditional ministry communication methods often demand considerable time, money, and resources, and can negatively impact the environment. AI offers a way to streamline processes, reduce costs, and lessen environmental impact, allowing ministries to operate more sustainably (Smith and Lee 2022:88). This study investigates how AI is reshaping ministry communication in Nigeria by enhancing inclusivity—through multilingual support and accessibility for people with

disabilities (Smith 2022:45)—and by promoting sustainability in ministry operations.

The ethical ramifications of AI adoption are critical, particularly for ministries that aim to maintain authenticity and trust. Challenges such as algorithmic bias, data privacy issues, and the risk of dehumanizing spiritual engagement must be carefully managed (Anderson 2020:45; Johnson 2021:123). For instance, while AI-powered chatbots can streamline pastoral care, they must be designed to demonstrate empathy and relational depth. Moreover, transparency in how AI tools are deployed is essential to preserve stakeholder trust (Smith and Green 2021:47).

Despite the many benefits of AI, its current use in Nigerian Christian ministries is not without limitations. There is often an overreliance on established technologies, potentially overlooking emerging tools (Miller 2023: 112), and the rapid pace of AI evolution means that ethical concerns may change over time. Nonetheless, by aligning AI integration with Christian values and prioritizing ethical practices, inclusivity, and sustainability, Nigerian ministries can harness technology to deepen connections, foster trust, and truly reflect the love and justice central to the Christian faith (Brown 2020:67).

Methodology

This study employs a library-based research methodology to investigate the topic, “From Ethics to Sustainability: Artificial Intelligence (AI)’s Role in Transforming Christian,” with a focus on the Nigerian context. Relying exclusively on secondary sources—books, journal articles, reputable online materials, and theological texts—the research emphasizes critical analysis and interpretation over primary data collection methods such as interviews or surveys. This approach ensures a thorough and academically rigorous examination of how AI is influencing ministry communication in Nigeria (Okafor 2020, 75).

The research concentrates on three key areas: advancements in AI technologies relevant to communication, the application of AI in Nigerian Christian ministry, and the ethical challenges these developments present. Data were drawn from credible academic databases such as JSTOR, Google Scholar, and theological libraries, using search terms like “AI in communication,” “Christian ministry and technology,” and “AI ethics.” Sources are carefully selected based on relevance, credibility, and recent

publication to reflect contemporary ethical debates and technological progress (Adeyemi 2021, 130).

The analysis identifies recurring patterns, themes, and gaps in the literature, using a comparative perspective to assess divergent viewpoints. Foundational frameworks from theological ethics and sustainable innovation theories guide the evaluation of how AI aligns with Christian values and ministry objectives in Nigeria, particularly in terms of fairness, accountability, and sustainability.

Theoretical Frameworks

The Social Shaping of Technology (SST) framework, introduced by Donald MacKenzie and Judy Wajcman in the 1980s, challenges the idea that technology is neutral, arguing instead that it is deeply influenced by social, cultural, and political factors. SST suggests that human values, choices, and contexts significantly shape the development, deployment, and interpretation of technology. This perspective is particularly useful for this study as it highlights the potential for aligning AI tools with Christian ethics rather than merely accepting them as they are (MacKenzie & Wajcman, 1999).

Similarly, Theological Ethics—a discipline within Christian theology that applies moral principles to practical decision-making based on God’s word—provides another important framework. Scholars such as Paul Ramsey and Stanley Hauerwas advocate for ethical decisions that reflect Christian virtues like love, justice, and inclusivity. In this study, Theological Ethics ensures that AI technologies, including chatbots and virtual reality tools, are employed in ways that support the mission and values of the church (Ramsey, 1974).

Together, these frameworks offer a comprehensive lens to examine how AI can be adapted to meet Christian priorities while upholding moral integrity. This integrated approach empowers church leaders to use AI tools innovatively and responsibly, fostering trust, inclusivity, and spiritual alignment within their communities.

The Intersection of AI and Christian Ministry

Artificial Intelligence (AI) is revolutionizing ministry communication in Nigeria, offering innovative tools to enhance outreach and engagement within its vibrant Christian communities. As digital adoption increases

across the country, Nigerian churches are leveraging AI to make their ministries more accessible, efficient, and impactful.

One prominent application is the use of chatbots for pastoral care and evangelism. These AI-driven tools provide real-time responses and spiritual guidance, offering comfort and addressing spiritual inquiries through automated text or voice interactions. For example, Nigerian churches integrate chatbots into their websites and social media platforms to help individuals explore Bible verses, answer questions, or connect with pastoral staff for deeper support (Smith 2023:45). Operating 24/7, these chatbots ensure consistent support, making them especially valuable for evangelism, particularly for those hesitant to engage directly with a pastor.

Another transformative use of AI in Nigerian ministry is content creation for sermons, worship services, and social media. AI tools assist ministry leaders in generating sermon outlines, suggesting scripture passages that align with specific themes, and creating engaging posts or videos. These tools analyze trends to help Nigerian churches maintain an active online presence by generating timely posts about upcoming events, Bible studies, or inspirational quotes, thereby ensuring consistent engagement with their audience (Johnson and Lee 2022:88).

Additionally, Virtual Reality (VR) technology, powered by AI, offers immersive worship experiences that transcend physical boundaries. In Nigeria, VR enables individuals to participate in worship services, prayer sessions, or Bible studies from anywhere, making it especially beneficial for those in remote areas or with limited mobility. VR-based worship ensures inclusivity by mirroring in-person participation while removing location-related barriers (Williams 2021:74).

AI is transforming ministry communication in Nigeria by providing essential tools such as chatbots, content creation software, and VR platforms. These innovations enhance pastoral care, foster engagement, and ensure inclusivity, allowing Nigerian churches to effectively share their message and address the diverse needs of their communities.

Review of Theological Perspectives on Technology in Ministry

Biblical perspectives on innovation and stewardship offer valuable guidance for Nigerian Christian ministries as they adopt new technologies. The Bible presents innovation as a neutral concept meant for God's glory and the good of creation. For instance, Proverbs 2:6 reminds believers that God is the source of boundless wisdom and understanding, a principle that Nigerian

churches apply as they integrate digital tools into ministry. Genesis 1:28, which commands humanity to “fill the earth and subdue it,” is interpreted as a call to responsible stewardship, managing technological resources wisely to promote goodness, justice, and love rather than harm or exploitation (Beale 2017:23).

In Nigerian ministry, technological advancements must be managed in line with biblical stewardship. The Bible urges believers to responsibly use all gifts—whether natural or man-made—to serve others and honor God (1 Peter 4:10). Accordingly, Nigerian churches leverage technology not for personal gain but to fulfill their mission of spreading the gospel, caring for the needy, and enhancing communal worship (Ward 2019:71). Moreover, Christian ethics emphasize values such as love, justice, and the common good, guiding the ethical use of technology. The command to “love your neighbor as yourself” (Matthew 22:39) compels Nigerian ministries to use technology as a means of connection and service rather than division or harm, with AI chatbots, for example, expected to reflect compassion and understanding (Johnson 2020:114). Justice requires that technological tools promote fairness and inclusivity, ensuring that marginalized groups in Nigeria are not excluded from spiritual care or church services (Miller 2018:88). In summary, Nigerian Christian theology advocates for a thoughtful, ethical engagement with technology that mirrors God’s creativity, fosters justice, and serves humanity in accordance with biblical principles.

Ethical Challenges of AI in Ministry

Biblical Views on Innovation and Stewardship: AI's Role in Transforming Nigerian Christian Ministry Communication

In Nigeria's rapidly digitizing landscape, Artificial Intelligence (AI) is increasingly shaping Christian ministry. Nigerian churches are adopting AI technologies—such as chatbots and automated systems—to enhance communication and spiritual engagement. However, while AI brings numerous benefits, it also raises critical concerns about data privacy and confidentiality. Churches in Nigeria routinely collect sensitive information including names, contact details, and details of members' spiritual journeys, which may involve personal confessions, struggles, or prayer requests. AI tools process and store this data, necessitating stringent measures to prevent unauthorized access or misuse (Calder, 2021:102).

To address these challenges, AI systems in Nigerian ministry must adhere to robust data protection laws and ethical standards. Key strategies include encrypting sensitive data, using secure servers, and ensuring individuals maintain control over the information they share. Moreover, churches must guarantee that personal details are neither stored nor shared without explicit consent (Calder, 2021:102). These practices foster an environment where data privacy is prioritized.

Equally important is transparency to build trust in AI systems. Nigerian church members are more likely to share personal information if they view these systems as reliable and secure. Transparency involves clearly communicating what data is collected, its intended use, and the protection measures in place. Additionally, members should understand how AI-driven recommendations—such as spiritual content suggestions or prayer resources—are generated. By fostering openness and trust, Nigerian churches can create a secure environment where congregants feel safe engaging with AI tools (Binns, 2018:10).

Bias and Inclusivity in AI for Christian Ministry Communication

Artificial Intelligence (AI) technology offers promising advancements for Christian ministry in Nigeria, yet it raises significant ethical concerns regarding bias, inclusivity, and fairness. In the diverse cultural landscape of Nigeria, these challenges are critical. They stem from the data-driven nature of AI systems, which can perpetuate existing inequalities in their training data. Guszczka (2020:11) highlights that biases in AI algorithms may unintentionally favor certain demographics, such as white, urban, or English-speaking groups, thereby marginalizing Nigeria's diverse racial, cultural, and socioeconomic communities. Such biases undermine the Church's commitment to inclusivity and emphasize the need for diverse datasets for equitable representation.

Equitable access to AI-powered ministry tools is also essential in Nigeria. Schafer and Stol (2021:16) emphasize that these tools—such as chatbots, virtual services, and translation systems—must serve all congregants, including those with disabilities, non-English speakers, and individuals in underserved areas. For example, an AI-driven sermon translation service should include Nigeria's less commonly spoken languages and offer sign language options to ensure accessibility for the hearing impaired.

Transparency and fairness are equally vital. Guszczka (2020:13) underscores the importance of monitoring AI algorithms for fairness and involving

communities in decision-making processes. By developing ethical guidelines in collaboration with technologists, Nigerian ministries can align AI systems with Christian principles of equality, justice, and care, fostering trust and inclusivity in ministry practices across the nation.

Accountability and Moral Decision-Making in AI-Driven Ministry Communication

In Nigeria, the use of artificial intelligence (AI) in Christian ministry is rapidly expanding, prompting complex ethical questions about accountability and moral decision-making. Nigerian churches are increasingly turning to AI for tasks such as counseling and prayer support, yet this shift raises concerns about whether AI can fully address the unique spiritual needs of congregants. While AI may offer efficiency and practical suggestions, it often lacks the emotional and spiritual intelligence essential for genuine ministry. Schwartz (2020:45) emphasizes, “AI should be viewed as a tool that assists in spiritual guidance rather than replacing the wisdom and understanding of human pastors.” Thus, human pastors remain critical to ensuring that AI complements, rather than undermines, the relational aspects of ministry.

Moreover, the use of AI to generate sermons and prayers further complicates the ethical landscape. Although AI can streamline content creation, its outputs may lack the personal reflection and spiritual insight necessary for authentic spiritual messages. Accountability for AI-generated content remains unclear, and Schwartz (2020:48) notes, “When AI produces spiritual content, accountability becomes unclear. Leaders must ensure the technology aligns with the core values of the church and does not lead to misleading or unbiblical teachings.” In a Nigerian context, where cultural values and community bonds are vital, addressing these ethical challenges is essential to maintaining genuine and effective Christian ministry communication.

Sustainable Communication Practices Using AI

In Nigeria, AI has significantly improved ministry accessibility by enabling effective communication across diverse audiences, particularly through multilingual communication and outreach to underserved or remote populations. In a country marked by rich linguistic diversity and vast rural areas, language barriers have long hindered ministry work. AI tools such as Google Translate and DeepL now provide instant translations of sermons,

Bible texts, and worship songs (Smith 2020:112). For example, an English-speaking pastor in Nigeria can use AI-powered software to generate subtitles in languages like French, Spanish, or Swahili during live-streamed services, while also producing multilingual devotionals and newsletters at lower costs (Brown 2021:45).

Moreover, AI facilitates outreach to hard-to-reach populations. Chatbots like Bible Ask and spiritual guidance apps offer 24/7 support, providing answers and encouragement in areas where physical churches are scarce (Jones and Carter 2022:78). Platforms such as WhatsApp and Facebook Messenger further enhance ministry efforts by enabling Nigerian churches to share worship services, prayers, and study materials with individuals in remote villages. Ultimately, AI empowers ministries in Nigeria to transcend language and distance, ensuring that the church's mission reaches broader and more diverse audiences.

Reducing Resource Consumption in Christian Ministry Using AI

Within Nigeria, AI is revolutionizing ministry communication by enhancing accessibility, particularly through multilingual communication and reaching underserved or remote populations. In a country marked by linguistic diversity, language barriers can hinder the expansion of ministry work. AI-powered tools such as Google Translate and DeepL enable instant translation of sermons, Bible texts, and worship songs, overcoming these challenges (Smith 2020:112). This technology allows Nigerian ministries to reach diverse language groups by providing real-time subtitle translation during live-streamed services or publishing materials in multiple languages without incurring high translation costs (Brown 2021:45).

Moreover, AI technologies empower ministries in Nigeria to serve remote or underserved regions. Chatbots like Bible Ask and various spiritual guidance apps offer continuous support by providing answers and encouragement even in areas without physical church infrastructure (Jones and Carter 2022:78). Platforms such as WhatsApp and Facebook Messenger further enable churches to distribute prayers, services, and educational resources to distant villages, effectively bridging geographical and resource limitations.

AI helps Nigerian ministries reach more people by breaking language and distance barriers. This allows them to connect spiritually with a wider audience.

Building Resilient Ministry Models

In Nigeria's rapidly evolving digital landscape, Christian ministries must adapt to remain relevant by equipping church leaders and members with the necessary skills to use artificial intelligence (AI) effectively and develop strategies for future communication challenges. Johnson and Phillips (2020, p. 78) emphasize that effective AI training not only enhances operational efficiency but also empowers ministry leaders to stay ahead of technological changes. In Nigerian churches, such training should include accessible AI tools and workshops that assist pastors in managing administrative tasks, creating sermon outlines, and improving online worship, while members can leverage AI to share the gospel and engage with their communities.

Additionally, Nigerian ministries must develop adaptive communication strategies to address challenges like demographic shifts, rapid technological advancements, and crises that impact local communities. Brown (2022, p. 45) asserts that flexible communication methods are essential for ministries to remain relevant in a changing society. This involves using AI-powered tools such as chatbots for spiritual support and language translation services to reach Nigeria's diverse audiences. By prioritizing inclusivity and accessibility, Nigerian ministries can ensure that everyone, regardless of location or language, engages with their programs. Building resilient ministry models through AI training and adaptive communication strategies will enable churches in Nigeria to thrive in the modern era, overcoming challenges and positively impacting lives.

Case Studies and Practical Examples

In Nigeria, as in other parts of the world, churches are increasingly adopting artificial intelligence (AI) to boost their digital outreach and engagement. For instance, Life.Church employs AI-driven chatbots that engage online visitors by answering spiritual queries, providing Bible verses, and connecting them with pastors—ensuring 24/7 availability and personalized assistance (Smith & Jones, 2021, p. 45). Additionally, Life.Church's YouVersion Bible App utilizes AI for sermon translations into multiple languages, overcoming language barriers and promoting inclusivity (Brown, 2020, p. 67).

During the COVID-19 pandemic, Elevation Church leveraged AI to optimize live streaming, achieving high-quality broadcasts and tailoring online worship services to maintain community bonds despite physical distancing (Green, 2022, p. 89). Furthermore, Saddleback Church uses AI-powered

predictive analytics to analyze survey data and attendance patterns, which helps in planning events, targeting outreach efforts, and addressing community needs effectively (Johnson, 2021, p. 112).

These examples illustrate how AI is transforming ministry communication by enabling churches to adapt to modern trends while upholding their mission. In Nigeria—where there is a burgeoning tech scene alongside a vibrant religious community—similar AI strategies are being explored to enhance ministry engagement. However, as Nigerian churches adopt these innovations, they must also address ethical concerns to ensure that AI tools are implemented with transparency, fairness, and a commitment to serving the community faithfully (Smith & Jones, 2021). AskKumuyi.ai is an AI-powered platform launched by the Deeper Christian Life Ministry to enhance access to the biblical teachings of Pastor W.F. Kumuyi. This tool allows users to search, summarize, and develop outlines from his extensive teachings, promoting deeper spiritual engagement. Notably, it supports translation into over 108 languages, making the gospel message accessible to a global audience (*AskKumuyi.ai*, n.d.).

The platform is available via its website and WhatsApp, offering a user-friendly experience for individuals seeking spiritual guidance. It provides both free and subscription-based services, with the free version allowing up to 20 queries, while premium plans grant unlimited access and additional resources (*Legit.ng*, 2024).

By launching AskKumuyi.ai, Pastor Kumuyi and the Deeper Christian Life Ministry demonstrate their commitment to leveraging technology for evangelism, broadening their outreach, and fostering deeper spiritual connections (*The Nation*, 2024).

Lessons from Failures or Ethical Missteps

AI technology holds great potential to enhance communication within the Christian ministry in Nigeria. In a country with a rapidly expanding digital landscape and a vibrant Christian community, many churches are integrating AI tools to improve outreach, engagement, and overall ministry communication. However, the improper application of AI or its use in ways that contradict Christian values poses significant challenges, particularly in maintaining trust.

One major ethical concern is data privacy violations. For instance, Jones (2023) highlighted an incident where a church's AI chatbot shared private prayer requests with third parties, causing public outrage and severely

damaging the church's credibility (p. 89). In Nigeria, where community trust is vital, such breaches can have lasting negative impacts.

Another challenge is the automation of content. When sermons or prayers are entirely AI-generated, they may lack the personal touch that congregants expect. Miller and Adams (2022) noted that one ministry experienced backlash after revealing its sermons were entirely AI-generated, with members questioning the authenticity of the pastor's spiritual guidance (p. 45). This issue is particularly sensitive in Nigerian contexts, where personal connection and pastoral authority are central to church life.

Moreover, algorithmic biases can inadvertently exclude certain groups. Smith (2021) cited an example where an AI outreach tool unintentionally marginalized low-income communities, resulting in accusations of favoritism and undermining the church's mission to serve all people equally (p. 102). In Nigeria's diverse socio-economic environment, such biases can exacerbate existing inequalities.

These ethical missteps underline the importance of applying AI within frameworks that prioritize transparency, consent, and inclusivity, aligning technological practices with core Christian ethical principles. As Nigerian churches continue to embrace digital transformation, ensuring ethical AI practices will be crucial for sustaining trust and supporting a ministry that truly serves its community.

Impact on Ministry Trust

In Nigeria, the integration of artificial intelligence (AI) into Christian ministry communication is advancing rapidly, yet ethical lapses in its implementation can severely undermine trust between church leaders and members. When members believe that their personal information is inadequately protected or that AI-generated spiritual content lacks genuine human warmth, they may feel alienated and choose to disengage from the church (Okafor 2020, 75). Moreover, public scandals stemming from AI misuse can tarnish the credibility of Christian ministries across Nigeria, fostering widespread skepticism toward the adoption of new technologies in faith-based contexts (Adeyemi 2021, 130). Learning from these challenges, ministries must prioritize transparency, informed consent, and rigorous ethical oversight when employing AI. Church leaders should actively involve their congregations in decision-making processes regarding AI

adoption to ensure that these technologies reflect shared Christian values and meet community expectations.

Situated within Nigeria—a nation known for its vibrant Christian communities and rapid technological adoption—this study underscores the transformative potential of artificial intelligence (AI) in ministry communication. In Nigerian churches, AI-powered tools such as chatbots and social media algorithms are increasingly used to enhance engagement with congregants (Brown, 2022, p. 34). Additionally, AI can assist in sermon preparation by offering research support and tailoring messages to meet the diverse needs of different audiences (Smith & Lee, 2021, p. 90). However, it remains essential to exercise caution to preserve the personal and spiritual connections that are fundamental to Christian ministry in Nigeria (Johnson, 2023, p. 58). Ethical concerns, such as ensuring data privacy and avoiding biases in AI systems, are prominent. Consequently, churches are encouraged to train leaders on AI's limitations and align its use with Biblical values—particularly when using AI to predict attendance (Brown, 2022, p. 45; Taylor, 2023, p. 14). Establishing ethical guidelines tailored to the ministry context is critical (Johnson, 2023, p. 64). Furthermore, Nigerian churches can guide society toward ethical AI use by forming partnerships with technologists and promoting AI tools that are grounded in Christian principles (Smith & Lee, 2021, p. 115). Through workshops and discussions, churches can further explore AI's role in spiritual development (Taylor, 2023, p. 19). Embracing ethical AI practices offers promising opportunities for ministry, improving outreach, resource management, and personalized spiritual experiences, but it requires a careful balance between technology and human-centered worship (Johnson, 2023, p. 72; Brown, 2022, p. 49).

Conclusion

This study has shown that Artificial Intelligence (AI) can be a powerful tool for churches in Nigeria, helping them improve communication, engage with their communities, and reach more people online. AI can assist ministries in sending personalized messages, preparing sermons, and expanding their outreach in today's digital world. However, it is important to use AI in a way that does not replace human connection but instead supports it.

One of the key takeaways from this study is that churches must use AI responsibly. There are ethical concerns, such as privacy issues and potential bias, that need to be carefully managed. Church leaders should lead by example, showing their members how to use AI wisely and teaching them

about both its benefits and risks. Ministries should also support research into AI solutions that can help with real-world challenges like poverty, education, and spiritual growth.

Additionally, AI should be used in ways that align with Christian values, such as love, humility, and responsibility. By taking a balanced approach, churches can use AI to enhance their mission while maintaining the personal care that is essential to ministry.

Ultimately, this study highlights the importance of combining technology with faith. AI should not replace the role of pastors, counselors, and church members, but it can be a helpful tool for spreading the gospel, building stronger communities, and making ministry more effective in today's fast-changing world.

Recommendations for Ethical and Effective Use of AI in Ministry

1. We recommend that ministries in Nigeria should develop well-defined rules to ensure AI aligns with Christian values such as love, honesty, and fairness (Johnson 2023).
2. We recommend that Churches must implement AI solutions that respect privacy, eliminate bias, and complement human connections rather than replacing them, ensuring alignment with Biblical teachings and core Christian values (Brown 2022, 45; Johnson 2023).
3. We recommend that ministries should form partnerships between theologians, technologists, and educators to create ethical AI guidelines and ensure AI supports ministry objectives (Smith & Lee 2021).
4. We recommend that Nigerian ministries should use AI for personalized messaging, expanding online outreach, and assisting with sermon preparation while maintaining responsible usage (Johnson 2023, 68).
5. We recommend that Church leaders should be trained through workshops, online courses, and user-friendly guides to integrate AI effectively while preserving human interaction (Brown 2022).
6. We recommend that Local ministries should support AI research to address societal challenges such as poverty, education, and spiritual outreach through collaboration with experts (Smith & Lee 2021).
7. We recommend that Ministries should adopt long-lasting and environmentally responsible AI technologies to ensure sustainability in digital operations.

8. We recommend that Churches should collaborate with AI firms that share their ethical and faith-based values, ensuring responsible and value-driven AI use.
9. We recommend that Dedicated teams should be formed to assess AI tools regularly, ensuring they remain ethical, effective, and beneficial for ministry communication in Nigeria.

References

- Adeyemi, Akin. 2021. "Digital Transformation in Nigerian Christian Ministry Communication." *Journal of African Church Studies* 8, no. 2 (Spring 2021): 123–145.
- Anderson, M. 2020. *Artificial Intelligence and the Church: Navigating Technology and Theology*. New York, NY: Faith & Tech Press.
- Anderson, Michael. 2020. "Privacy and Bias in AI: A Christian Perspective." *Journal of Ethics and Technology* 7, no. 2: 40–50.
- AskKumuyi.ai. (n.d.). About AskKumuyi. Retrieved from <https://askkumuyi.ai/about>
- Beale, G. K. 2017. *A Biblical Theology of the Church: God's Plan for His People from Creation to Consummation*. Baker Academic.
- Binns, J. R. 2020. *Ethics and Technology in Ministry: A Guide to Ethical AI Use in Church Communication*. Christian Publishing.
- Binns, Mark. 2020. "Sustainable AI: Reducing Costs in Digital Ministry." *Journal of Sustainable Practices* 3, no. 2: 35–40.
- Binns, R. 2018. *Understanding AI Transparency: Ethics in Machine Learning*. Cambridge University Press.
- Brown, A. 2022. *Artificial Intelligence in Ministry: A Practical Guide for Church Leaders*. Christian Tech Press.
- Brown, David. 2020. "Ethical Considerations in the Digital Age of Ministry." *Journal of Religious Ethics* 12, no. 1: 65–75.
- Brown, J., and M. Taylor. 2021. *Technology and the Church: A Modern Approach to Ministry*. New York, NY: HarperFaith.
- Brown, L. 2021. *Artificial Intelligence in Faith Communities: Practical Applications for Today*. New York: FaithTech Press.
- Brown, L. M. 2022. *Technology and the Church: Bridging the Gap Between Faith and Innovation*. New York: FaithWorks Press.
- Brown, M. 2020. *Technology and the Church: Bridging Gaps in Modern Ministry*. New York, NY: FaithTech Press.
- Brown, R. 2020. *Technology and the Church: Ethics for the Digital Age*. Grand Rapids, MI: Zondervan.
- Calder, A. 2021. *AI Ethics in the Age of Information: Securing Personal Data*. Digital Press.

- Campbell, H. 2019. *Digital Religion: Understanding Religious Practice in Digital Media*. New York, NY: Routledge.
- Campbell, John. 2019. "The Future of Communication: AI and Digital Innovation." *Journal of Digital Transformation* 5, no. 2: 40–55.
- Coeckelbergh, M. 2020. *AI Ethics*. Cambridge: MIT Press.
- Green, T. 2022. *Innovations in Worship: The Role of AI in Ministry Transformation*. Los Angeles, CA: WorshipTech Publications.
- Guszcza, J. 2020. "The Hidden Biases of AI: How Algorithms Can Reinforce Inequality and What We Can Do About It." *Harvard Business Review* 98, no. 4: 10–13.
- Johnson, A., and M. Lee. 2022. *Digital Tools in Modern Ministry: The Future of Faith Communication*. Christian Publishing.
- Johnson, D. 2020. *Ethics and Technology: An Introduction to the Moral Issues of Technology and Human Development*. Wiley-Blackwell.
- Johnson, Emily. 2021. "Navigating AI in Pastoral Care." *Ministry Technology Review* 9, no. 1: 120–130.
- Johnson, P. 2022. *AI and Faith: Navigating Innovation in Christian Ministry*. Chicago, IL: FaithWorks Press.
- Johnson, R. 2021. *Data-Driven Discipleship: The Power of Analytics in Ministry*. Chicago, IL: Ministry Insights Press.
- Johnson, R. 2021. *Ethics in the Age of AI: A Guide for Christian Ministries*. Grand Rapids, MI: Ministry Insights.
- Johnson, R. 2023. "Ethics in Technology: A Christian Perspective." *Faith & Innovation Journal* 12, no. 4: 56–72.
- Johnson, T. 2021. *The Digital Ministry Revolution: AI in the Church*. Church Press.
- Johnson, T., and R. Phillips. 2020. *AI for Ministry: Practical Tools for Digital Evangelism*. Grand Rapids, MI: Ministry Solutions Press.
- Jones, R. 2023. *Ethics in Digital Ministry: Protecting Data and Building Trust*. New York, NY: Faith Tech Press.
- Jones, R., and M. Carter. 2022. *Technology and Theology: Bridging the Gap*. Chicago: MinistryTech Publications.
- Lee, R., S. Kim, and G. Thomas. 2023. *Stewardship in Action: Sustainable Practices for Church Leaders*. San Francisco, CA: Grace Publications.
- Legit.ng. (2024). Ask Kumuyi AI: 5 things to know about Deeper Life's search engine. Retrieved from <https://www.legit.ng/people/1635253-ask-kumuyi-ai-5-deeper-life-search-engine-answers-christian-questions>
- MacKenzie, D., and J. Wajcman. 1999. *The Social Shaping of Technology*. Open University Press.
- Miller, D. 2022. *Sustainability in Church Operations: Integrating AI for Long-Term Growth*. Theological Press.

- Miller, D., and J. Adams. 2022. *The Human Touch: Balancing Technology and Authentic Ministry*. Chicago, IL: Grace Publications.
- Miller, R. 2023. *AI and Ethics in Faith-Based Organizations*. Ethics in Technology Publishing.
- Miller, Steven. 2023. "Emerging AI Trends in Ministry Communication." *Journal of Emerging Technologies* 4, no. 1: 110–120.
- Miller, V. 2018. *Technology and Christian Ethics: A New Way Forward for the Church*. Zondervan.
- Okafor, Emeka. 2020. "Emerging Digital Trends in Nigerian Churches." *Nigerian Journal of Media and Communication* 12, no. 1 (Winter 2020): 67–80.
- Ramsey, P. 1974. *The Ethics of Fetal Research*. Yale University Press.
- Schafer, A., and Y. Stol. 2021. "AI and Inclusive Digital Transformation: Fostering Fairness and Access in Christian Ministry." *Journal of Ethics in AI* 3, no. 2: 14–18.
- Schwartz, A. 2020. *Artificial Intelligence and Ethical Decision-Making in Ministry: Balancing Faith and Technology*. Religious Ethics Press.
- Smith, Alan, and Brian Jones. 2021. "Virtual Ministries: Enhancing Outreach with AI." *Journal of Ministry Communication* 8, no. 3: 110–125.
- Smith, Carol, and James Lee. 2022. "Sustainable Communication: AI in Ministry Practices." *Journal of Environmental Communication* 10, no. 2: 85–95.
- Smith, J. 2020. *AI in the Church: Opportunities and Challenges*. London: Christian Ethics Press.
- Smith, J. 2023. *AI in the Church: Embracing Technology for Spiritual Growth*. FaithTech Books.
- Smith, J., and C. Lee. 2021. *Theology and Technology: Building Ethical Bridges*. Cambridge University Press.
- Smith, J., and K. Lee. 2022. *Sustainable Ministry: Balancing Innovation and Tradition in the Digital Era*. London, UK: Church Sustainability Publishers.
- Smith, J., and L. Jones. 2021. *AI and the Church: Redefining Digital Discipleship*. San Francisco, CA: TechFaith Publishers.
- Smith, J., and P. Jones. 2021. *Artificial Intelligence and Christian Ethics*. London, UK: Bloomsbury Academic.
- Smith, L. 2020. *Sustainable Ministry: Embracing Eco-Friendly Practices in Worship*. Boston, MA: GreenFaith Press.
- Smith, L. 2021. *AI and Inclusion in Faith-Based Outreach: Addressing Algorithmic Bias*. Boston, MA: Ministry Innovations Press.
- Smith, L. 2022. *Artificial Intelligence in Ministry Communication: A Transformative Tool*. FaithTech Press.
- Smith, L., and K. Green. 2021. *Artificial Intelligence and Inclusivity in Religious Outreach*. University Press.

- Smith, Laura, and Michael Green. 2021. "Transparency in AI Tools: Ensuring Trust in Ministry." *Journal of Church Communication* 11, no. 1: 45–50.
- Smith, R. 2022. "AI for Inclusive Ministry Communication." *African Journal of Religious Studies* 15, no. 1: 40–50.
- Taylor, M. 2023. "Sustaining Faith Through Innovation: AI's Role in Modern Ministry." *Religious Technology Review* 9, no. 1: 10–20.
- The Nation. (2024). Kumuyi launches AI tech to revolutionize gospel outreach. Retrieved from <https://thenationonlineng.net/kumuyi-launches-ai-tech-to-revolutionise-gospel-outreach>
- Verbeek, P. P. 2011. *Moralizing Technology: Understanding and Designing the Morality of Things*. University of Chicago Press.
- Verbeek, Peter-Paul. 2011. *Mediation and Materiality: Philosophy of Technology*. Stanford: Stanford University Press.
- Ward, G. 2019. *Faith and Technology: Bridging the Gap Between Innovation and Scripture*. Oxford University Press.
- Williams, D. 2021. *Virtual Worship and the Future of Church Experiences*. Ministry Tech Press.

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**Religious Conflicts and Their Impact on
Africa's Future: Exploring the Path to
Sustainable Peace and Development with
the Support of Artificial Intelligence (AI)**

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Abstract

Religious conflicts in Africa have significantly hindered peace, stability, and development. These conflicts, often fueled by ethnic, political, and economic factors, have led to loss of lives, displacement, and economic decline. This study explores the impact of religious conflicts on Africa's future and examines how Artificial Intelligence (AI) can support sustainable peace and development. AI technologies, including data analytics, machine learning, and predictive modeling, can help in early conflict detection, misinformation control, and promoting interfaith dialogue. The methodology of this study involves a qualitative approach, including content analysis of existing literature, case studies of religious conflicts in Africa, and expert interviews. By analyzing historical patterns and the role of AI in conflict resolution, the study provides insights into effective strategies for peacebuilding. The study recommends the integration of AI-driven solutions in peacebuilding initiatives, strengthening policies for interfaith harmony, and promoting education on religious tolerance. Governments, religious leaders, and international organizations should collaborate in leveraging AI for conflict prevention and resolution. By adopting technology-supported peace strategies, Africa can foster long-term stability and sustainable development.

Keywords: Religious Conflicts, AI in Peacebuilding, Sustainable Development

Introduction

Religious conflicts have long posed significant challenges to peace and development across Africa. These conflicts often stem from deep-seated historical grievances, ethnic divisions, and socio-economic disparities, leading to cycles of violence and instability. The repercussions are profound, affecting not only the immediate communities involved but also the broader socio-economic fabric of nations. Understanding the root causes and exploring sustainable solutions is imperative for the continent's future. In Nigeria, for instance, the interplay between religious tensions and socio-economic factors has been a catalyst for prolonged unrest. Research indicates that religious conflicts in the country have led to significant loss of lives, destruction of property, and political instability, thereby hindering national development (Jegade, 2019, p. 53). Similarly, studies have shown that ethno-religious conflicts in Kaduna have adversely affected residential property development, leading to economic downturns in affected areas (Bello, Nwosu, & Orji, 2023, p. 65).

The role of religious leaders in mitigating these conflicts cannot be overstated. They possess the moral authority to influence their followers and promote messages of peace and reconciliation. By actively engaging in dialogue and community-building initiatives, religious leaders can address misconceptions and foster mutual respect among different faith groups. Their involvement is crucial in transforming religious institutions into agents of peace and security, contributing to sustainable development (Osajie, 2021, p. 260). Advancements in artificial intelligence (AI) offer new avenues to support peacebuilding efforts in Africa. AI can enhance conflict analysis and early warning systems, enabling more proactive and effective interventions. By analyzing patterns and predicting potential flashpoints, AI tools can assist policymakers and peacekeepers in deploying resources more efficiently and preventing escalation. Integrating AI into peace and security frameworks presents a promising path toward achieving lasting stability and development on the continent (Amani Africa, 2024).

Methodology

This study adopts a qualitative research design to explore religious conflicts in Africa and their impact on sustainable peace and development. Qualitative research is appropriate for understanding social and cultural

phenomena through in-depth analysis (Creswell, 2018, p. 32). The study relies on secondary sources, including books, journal articles, and reports from international organizations. These sources provide historical and contemporary perspectives on religious conflicts, their causes, and their consequences. Data collection also involves thematic analysis, which helps identify recurring patterns and key themes related to religious conflicts and AI-driven solutions (Bryman, 2016, p. 45). The study employs a comparative approach by examining case studies of religious conflicts in different African countries. This method allows for an understanding of how various regions have been affected and the unique strategies used to address these conflicts (Gerring, 2017, p. 58). Case studies from Nigeria, Sudan, and the Central African Republic offer insights into the socio-political and economic implications of religious tensions. Additionally, an AI-driven conflict resolution model is reviewed to determine how technological advancements can contribute to peacebuilding (Smith, 2020, p. 74).

To ensure credibility and reliability, data triangulation is applied by cross-referencing multiple sources. This process helps validate findings and minimize biases in data interpretation (Denzin & Lincoln, 2018, p. 91). The study also integrates insights from local scholars and policymakers who have extensively researched religious conflicts in Africa. For instance, Okonkwo (2019, p. 112) emphasizes the role of historical grievances in religious tensions, while Adebayo (2021, p. 67) highlights the socio-economic factors that fuel conflicts in the region. Their perspectives offer localized context, complementing global analyses. Ethical considerations are also taken into account by ensuring that all sources are properly cited and acknowledged. Since this research is based on secondary data, there is no direct engagement with participants, reducing ethical concerns related to privacy and consent. However, the study remains conscious of presenting balanced perspectives and avoiding biased interpretations. Ultimately, by leveraging AI tools for data analysis and conflict resolution, this research aims to offer innovative solutions for fostering sustainable peace and development in Africa.

In summary, this mixed-method study combines qualitative analyses of historical and socio-political factors with quantitative assessments of conflict data to provide a nuanced understanding of religious conflicts in Africa. By investigating the potential of AI technologies in this domain, the research aims to contribute to the development of effective strategies for achieving sustainable peace and development on the continent.

Theoretical Framework

This study is based on two key theories: the Conflict Theory and the Technological Determinism Theory. Conflict Theory, developed by Karl Marx, explains that religious conflicts arise due to power struggles and inequalities within society (Marx, 1848, p. 23). In Africa, religious conflicts are often driven by historical injustices, political marginalization, and economic disparities, making this theory relevant for understanding the root causes of tensions. The study examines how these power struggles influence religious conflicts and the potential pathways to sustainable peace. The Technological Determinism Theory, proposed by Marshall McLuhan, suggests that technology shapes societal development and interactions (McLuhan, 1964, p. 56). In the context of this research, AI is seen as a transformative tool that can support peacebuilding and conflict resolution. AI-driven systems, such as early warning mechanisms and predictive analytics, can help identify conflict hotspots and mediate disputes before they escalate. By integrating AI solutions, this study explores how technology can play a role in reducing religious conflicts in Africa.

These two theories provide a strong foundation for analyzing religious conflicts and potential AI-based solutions. Conflict Theory helps explain why religious conflicts persist, while Technological Determinism highlights how AI can be used to address these challenges. The combination of these perspectives ensures a comprehensive understanding of the issue and paves the way for sustainable peace and development.

The Intersection of Conflict Theory and Technological Determinism Theory

The intersection of Conflict Theory and Technological Determinism Theory in this study is evident in how artificial intelligence (AI) can be leveraged to mitigate religious conflicts in Africa. Conflict Theory explains that power struggles, economic disparities, and social inequalities are primary drivers of religious conflicts (Marx, 1848, p. 23). Religious groups often find themselves in opposition due to historical grievances and unequal access to resources, which fuels tensions and violence (Okonkwo, 2019, p. 112). However, with AI's ability to process large amounts of data and detect patterns, it can serve as a tool for conflict prevention by identifying potential triggers before they escalate into violent confrontations (Smith, 2020, p. 74). Technological Determinism Theory suggests that technology shapes social structures and interactions, making AI a crucial factor in peacebuilding

(McLuhan, 1964, p. 56). AI-driven solutions such as predictive analytics, automated conflict resolution systems, and digital communication platforms can foster dialogue between conflicting religious groups (Adebayo, 2021, p. 67). For example, AI-powered mediation systems can analyze past conflicts, predict future disputes, and offer unbiased recommendations for resolution, thus reducing human biases in conflict resolution (Bryman, 2016, p. 45). These technological tools align with Conflict Theory by addressing structural inequalities that contribute to religious conflicts.

By combining the insights from both theories, this study highlights how AI can be a transformative force in addressing the root causes of religious conflicts in Africa. While Conflict Theory provides a framework for understanding why religious conflicts persist, Technological Determinism illustrates how AI-driven solutions can help mitigate these tensions and promote peace (Denzin & Lincoln, 2018, p. 91). The integration of AI in conflict resolution not only helps in identifying and managing disputes but also contributes to long-term sustainable peace and development in the region.

Case Studies of Religious Conflicts in Africa

Religious conflicts in Africa have been extensively studied by both foreign and local scholars. Some of these religious conflicts are:

1. ***The 1992 Zangon Kataf Crises in Nigeria***: In 1992, Zangon Kataf, a town in Kaduna State, Nigeria, experienced violent clashes between the Atyp (a Christian ethnic group) and the Hausa-Fulani (a Muslim ethnic group). The conflict arose over disputes concerning land ownership and market relocation. The violence resulted in significant loss of life and property. According to Falola (2001), the crisis was deeply rooted in historical grievances and competition over resources (p. 85).
2. ***The 2002 Miss World Riots in Nigeria***: In November 2002, Nigeria was set to host the Miss World beauty pageant. *ThisDay* newspaper suggesting that the Prophet Muhammad might have approved of the event sparked outrage among the Muslim population. This led to violent riots in Kaduna, resulting in over 200 deaths and extensive property damage. Human Rights Watch (2003) reported that the violence was a manifestation of underlying religious tensions between Muslims and Christians in the region (p. 12).

3. *The 2010 Jos Riots in Nigeria:* Jos, the capital of Plateau State in Nigeria, has been a hotspot for religious conflicts. In 2010, clashes erupted between Muslim and Christian communities, leading to significant casualties and displacement. The violence was attributed to competition over political and economic resources, as well as deep-seated religious animosities. According to Human Rights Watch (2013), both communities suffered heavy losses, and the conflict further deepened the religious divide (p. 45).
4. *The Herder-Farmer Conflicts in Nigeria:* In Nigeria's Middle Belt region, conflicts between predominantly Muslim Fulani herders and predominantly Christian farmers have escalated over the years. These clashes are primarily over land and water resources but are often framed in religious terms. Blench (2010) notes that environmental changes and competition for resources have intensified these conflicts, leading to loss of lives and livelihoods (p. 23).
5. *The Boko Haram Insurgency in Nigeria:* Boko Haram, an Islamist militant group, has been responsible for numerous attacks in Nigeria, particularly targeting Christian communities. Their insurgency, which began in 2009, aims to establish an Islamic state and has led to widespread violence, including bombings, assassinations, and abductions. According to the International Crisis Group (2014), the group's activities have exacerbated religious tensions and have resulted in thousands of deaths and displacements (p. 27).
6. *“Lukarawa” (or “Lakurawa”) Terrorist Group in Nigeria:* This group recently emerged in the northwest Nigeria with the main interest of imposing “strict Islamic law on the people” (Afolaranmi, 2024, p. 4).

These case studies illustrate the complex interplay of religious, ethnic, and socio-economic factors contributing to conflicts in Nigeria.

Expert Interviews on Religious Conflicts in Africa

Religious conflicts in Africa have been a subject of extensive study by both foreign and local experts. These conflicts often stem from a complex interplay of political, economic, and social factors, rather than purely religious differences.

Dr. Ludovic Lado, a scholar from Côte d'Ivoire, emphasizes that the rise in religious violence in sub-Saharan Africa is influenced by feelings of political

and economic marginalization among northern populations. He notes that "religious violence is increasing on the continent and is going to become one of the major sources of instability in the future" (Wilson Center, 2014, p. 1). Lado warns that if policymakers do not address these concerns, it may alter the dynamics of relationships between Christians and Muslims long-term. Similarly, Ms. Tiffany Lynch, a Senior Policy Analyst at the U.S. Commission on International Religious Freedom, identifies two primary forms of religious violence: communal violence and religious extremism. She explains that communal violence involves clashes between different communities based on religion, tribe, or language, as seen in Nigeria's northern regions. Religious extremism, on the other hand, is perpetrated by groups like Boko Haram and al-Shabaab, aiming to impose specific religious ideologies through violent means (Wilson Center, 2014, p. 2).

Religious discrimination has been identified as a significant factor contributing to armed conflicts in sub-Saharan Africa. Local researchers have observed that systemic discrimination against certain religious groups often leads to social marginalization, which can escalate into violent confrontations. For instance, in Nigeria, discriminatory practices against minority religious communities have been linked to recurring conflicts in regions like Jos and Kaduna. These findings underscore the need for policies that promote religious tolerance and equal rights to mitigate conflict (Akanji, 2022, p. 15). The introduction of Christianity in various parts of Africa has sometimes led to tensions with indigenous religious practices. In Nigeria, particularly among the Igbo community, local scholars have documented conflicts arising from differing belief systems. These conflicts often manifest in social ostracism and disputes over cultural practices. For example, the denouncement of traditional rituals by Christian converts has led to community divisions and, in some cases, violent clashes. Understanding these dynamics is crucial for developing strategies that foster inter-religious dialogue and coexistence (Okafor, 2017, p. 42). Despite the prevalence of religious conflicts, there are notable efforts by local leaders to promote peace through interfaith initiatives. In Kaduna, Nigeria, Imam Muhammad Ashafa and Pastor James Wuye, once adversaries, have collaborated to establish the Interfaith Mediation Center. Their work focuses on mediating conflicts and fostering understanding between Muslim and Christian communities. Their approach includes joint community projects and dialogue sessions aimed at addressing misconceptions and building trust. Their efforts have been instrumental in reducing religiously

motivated violence in the region (Eteng, 2020, p. 58). Local researchers also emphasize that religious conflicts in Africa are often intertwined with socio-economic issues. Poverty, unemployment, and political marginalization can exacerbate religious tensions. For instance, in regions where resources are scarce, competition can take on a religious dimension, leading to conflicts. Addressing these underlying socio-economic disparities is essential for sustainable peace. Programs that provide economic opportunities and inclusive governance can help alleviate the conditions that fuel religious conflicts (Adebayo, 2018, p. 73).

These insights suggest that addressing religious conflicts in Africa requires a multifaceted approach that includes political reforms, economic development, and robust interfaith dialogue. By understanding the underlying causes and promoting collaborative efforts, sustainable peace can be achieved.

The Intersection Between Religious Conflicts and Their Impact on Africa's Future

Religious conflicts have profoundly impacted Africa's socio-economic development, leading to loss of life, displacement, and economic downturns. In Nigeria, for instance, ethno-religious clashes have resulted in thousands of deaths and the displacement of hundreds of thousands, fostering instability in regions like Jos, Plateau State (Kwaja, 2011, p. 1). These conflicts often stem from systemic issues, including statutory frameworks that grant local officials the power to extend or deny basic rights, thereby politicizing ethnicity and escalating intercommunal violence (Kwaja, 2011, p. 1). The repercussions of such conflicts extend beyond immediate violence, affecting various sectors critical to sustainable development. In Nigeria, religious conflicts have been found to negatively impact election processes, governance, security, migration, education, and economic development (Kenti-Udom, 2023, p. 149). The resultant effect is a strain on the human, social, economic, and environmental pillars essential for sustainable development. For example, the destruction of educational infrastructure during conflicts hampers learning opportunities, while displacement disrupts economic activities and exacerbates poverty.

Additionally, AI can support peace-making and mediation efforts by addressing information asymmetry and enabling more effective conflict analysis and early warning systems (Amani Africa, 2023).

However, the integration of AI into peacebuilding efforts must be approached with caution. While AI has the potential to foster peace and democracy, it also carries risks that could fuel violence, inequality, polarization, and authoritarianism if not properly managed (Ashby, 2023). Therefore, it is imperative to develop ethical frameworks and policies that guide the deployment of AI in conflict-prone areas, ensuring that its application promotes social cohesion and sustainable development.

Effects Of Religious Conflicts and Their Impact on Africa's Future

Religious conflicts have serious effects on Africa's development, leading to loss of lives, destruction of properties, and economic instability (Okonkwo, 2019, p. 87). Many African countries, such as Nigeria and Sudan, have suffered from prolonged religious tensions that have weakened their political and social structures. When communities are divided along religious lines, it becomes difficult to build a unified society that fosters peace and development (Adebayo, 2021, p. 56). Additionally, religious conflicts have contributed to massive displacement of people, leading to refugee crises in various African regions (Bryman, 2016, p. 102). Displaced individuals often face challenges such as lack of access to basic needs, healthcare, and education, which further deepens poverty and suffering (Smith, 2020, p. 134). With many people unable to return to their homes due to religious tensions, long-term instability continues to threaten the continent's future.

The impact on Africa's economy is also significant, as religious conflicts disrupt businesses, deter foreign investments, and weaken national economies (McLuhan, 1964, p. 67). Many industries are forced to shut down in conflict-prone areas, leading to job losses and reduced economic opportunities (Denzin & Lincoln, 2018, p. 89). Moreover, governments are compelled to allocate more resources to security and conflict resolution instead of investing in essential sectors such as education and healthcare. To secure Africa's future, addressing religious conflicts through sustainable peace strategies is essential. AI-driven solutions can play a key role in predicting conflicts, promoting interfaith dialogue, and supporting peacebuilding efforts (Creswell, 2018, p. 54). By utilizing AI for conflict resolution, African nations can work towards achieving lasting peace and stability, ultimately fostering economic growth and social development.

The Bias Raise by Concerned Scholars on the Effectiveness of AI on the Path to Sustainable Peace and Development

Artificial Intelligence (AI) has been heralded as a transformative tool for achieving sustainable peace and development. However, scholars have raised concerns about inherent biases in AI systems that may undermine these objectives. One significant issue is the potential for AI to perpetuate existing social inequalities. Buolamwini (2018) demonstrated that facial recognition technologies often misidentify individuals with darker skin tones, leading to discriminatory practices (p. 8). This misidentification can result in unjust surveillance and policing, disproportionately affecting marginalized communities.

In the context of Nigeria, the integration of AI into security frameworks has sparked debate. Nsude (2022) explored the deployment of AI in combating insurgency and highlighted challenges such as the potential for AI systems to misinterpret data, leading to wrongful targeting and escalation of conflicts (p. 15). These inaccuracies not only jeopardize peace efforts but also erode public trust in technological interventions. Moreover, the global development of AI technologies often overlooks the unique needs of the Global South. Okolo (2024) emphasized the disparities in AI development between Silicon Valley and African nations, cautioning that without inclusive strategies, AI could exacerbate existing inequalities and hinder socioeconomic progress. This technological divide may lead to solutions that are misaligned with local contexts, thereby impeding sustainable development.

Ethical considerations also play a crucial role in the discourse on AI and sustainable development. Ajunwa (2023) discussed the implications of AI in workplace settings, noting that biased algorithms can lead to discriminatory hiring practices and surveillance, which undermine social equity (p. 102). Such practices can entrench systemic biases, making it challenging to achieve inclusive development goals. To address these concerns, scholars advocate for the development of AI systems that are transparent, accountable, and inclusive. Effoduh (2024) called for a Global South perspective in AI development, urging for policies that consider local contexts and promote equitable access to AI technologies. By incorporating diverse perspectives and ensuring community involvement, AI can be harnessed effectively to promote sustainable peace and development.

The Path to Sustainable Peace and Development with the Support of AI

Artificial Intelligence (AI) has emerged as a powerful tool in promoting sustainable peace and development worldwide. By leveraging AI's capabilities, societies can address complex challenges related to conflict prevention, economic growth, and social equity. In Nigeria, integrating AI into various sectors offers promising avenues to enhance national development and stability. One significant application of AI is in conflict analysis and early warning systems. AI can process vast amounts of data to identify patterns indicative of potential conflicts, enabling proactive measures to prevent violence. For instance, AI-driven technologies can monitor social media and other communication channels to detect escalating tensions, allowing for timely interventions (Amaniacfrica-et.org, 2023, p. 2). This approach is particularly relevant in regions prone to communal clashes, where early detection and response are crucial.

In the realm of economic development, AI contributes to optimizing resource allocation and enhancing productivity. By analyzing market trends and consumer behavior, AI systems can provide insights that inform policy decisions and business strategies. In Nigeria, AI has been utilized to improve agricultural practices, leading to increased yields and food security. For example, AI-powered tools can predict weather patterns and recommend optimal planting times, benefiting smallholder farmers (Data Science Nigeria, 2024, p. 5). AI also plays a role in promoting social inclusion and reducing inequalities. Through personalized education programs, AI can cater to diverse learning needs, ensuring that marginalized communities have access to quality education. In Nigeria, initiatives like Data Science Nigeria aim to train a significant number of AI talents, fostering a more inclusive digital economy (Data Science Nigeria, 2024, p. 3). Such efforts not only empower individuals but also contribute to national development by building a skilled workforce.

However, the integration of AI into peace and development strategies must be approached with caution. Concerns regarding data privacy, algorithmic bias, and the potential for AI to exacerbate existing inequalities need to be addressed. Collaborative efforts between governments, civil society, and the private sector are essential to establish ethical guidelines and regulatory frameworks that ensure AI is used responsibly and equitably (Ashby, 2023, p. 4). In conclusion, AI offers transformative potential for advancing sustainable peace and development in Nigeria and beyond. By harnessing AI's capabilities in conflict prevention, economic growth, and social

inclusion, societies can address complex challenges more effectively. Ensuring that AI integration is conducted ethically and inclusively will be key to realizing its full benefits for all members of society.

Conclusion

Addressing religious conflicts in Africa requires a multifaceted approach that combines traditional peacebuilding methods with modern technologies. Artificial intelligence offers promising tools to enhance early warning systems, promote interfaith dialogue, and develop culturally sensitive solutions. By investing in AI education and infrastructure, and by establishing robust ethical guidelines, African nations can harness AI's potential to foster sustainable peace and development. Collaborative efforts between governments, religious leaders, and local communities are essential to ensure that AI technologies are leveraged effectively and ethically in the pursuit of harmony and progress.

Recommendations

1. **Promote Interfaith Dialogue and Collaboration:** Encourage open communication between different religious groups to foster mutual understanding and respect. This can be achieved through community forums, joint projects, and educational programs that highlight shared values and common goals (Afunugo & Molokwu, 2024, p. 98).
2. **Implement AI-Driven Early Warning Systems:** Utilize artificial intelligence to monitor and analyze data for potential conflict indicators. AI can process large datasets to identify patterns and provide timely alerts, enabling proactive measures to prevent escalation (Amaniafrica, 2024).
3. **Develop Inclusive AI Policies:** Ensure that AI technologies are designed and implemented in ways that respect cultural and religious sensitivities. This includes involving local communities in the development process to address specific needs and concerns (Deloitte, 2024, p. 12).
4. **Invest in AI Education and Infrastructure:** Governments and organizations should prioritize building the necessary infrastructure and providing education to develop local AI expertise. This investment will empower communities to create solutions

tailored to their unique challenges (Policy Center for the New South, 2023, p. 12).

5. ***Establish Ethical Guidelines for AI Use:*** Develop and enforce ethical standards for AI applications, particularly in sensitive areas like religious practices and conflict resolution. These guidelines should emphasize transparency, accountability, and the protection of human rights (UNESCO, 2021).

References

- Adebayo, R. I. (2018). *Religion and Conflict in Nigeria: The Role of Socio-Economic Factors*. Ibadan: University Press.
- Adebayo, T. (2021). *Socio-economic perspectives on religious conflicts in West Africa*. Lagos Academic Press.
- Afolaranmi, A. O. (2024). Emergence of a New Terrorist Group "Lukarawa" in Northwest Nigeria and Its Implications on the Peaceful Coexistence and Religious Harmony of People in the Region. *Lead City Journal of Religions and Intercultural Communication*, 2(2), 1–8.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14194481>
- Afunugo, K. N., & Molokwu, G. C. (2024). *Artificial Intelligence (AI) and Effective Evangelization of the Nigerian Church Mission: A Socio-Religious Evaluation*. *Journal of African Studies and Sustainable Development*, 7(2), 86–102. Retrieved from
<https://acjol.org/index.php/jassd/article/download/5115/4964>
- Ajunwa, I. (2023). *The Quantified Worker*. Cambridge University Press.
- Akanji, I. A. (2022). *Understanding Religious Conflict in Contemporary Nigerian Society*. Lagos: Harmony Publishers.
- Amani Africa. (2024). *Artificial Intelligence and Its Impact on Peace and Security in Africa*. Retrieved from <https://amaniafrica-et.org/looking-into-the-future-artificial-intelligence-and-its-impact-on-peace-and-security-in-africa/>
- Ashby, H. (2023, December 6). *A Role for AI in Peacebuilding*. United States Institute of Peace. Retrieved from
<https://www.usip.org/publications/2023/12/role-ai-peacebuilding>
- Bello, V. A., Nwosu, A. E., & Orji, E. E. (2023). *Ethno-religious Conflict in Kaduna, Nigeria: Perceptual Implications for Residential Property Development*. *Environmental Technology and Science Journal*, 14(2), 65.
- Blench, R. (2010). *Conflict between pastoralists and cultivators in Nigeria*. Retrieved from
<https://www.rogerblench.info/Development/Nigeria/Pastoralism/Fadama%20II%20paper.pdf>
- Bryman, A. (2016). *Social research methods* (5th ed.). Oxford University Press.

- Buolamwini, J. (2018). *Gender shades: Intersectional accuracy disparities in commercial gender classification. Proceedings of the 1st Conference on Fairness, Accountability and Transparency*, 77–91.
- Creswell, J. W. (2018). *Research design: Qualitative, quantitative, and mixed methods approaches* (5th ed.). SAGE Publications.
- Data Science Nigeria. (2024). *Data Science Nigeria Annual Report*. Retrieved from <https://www.data4sdgs.org/partner/data-science-nigeria>
- Deloitte. (2024). *AI for Inclusive Development in Africa – Part II: Data and Digital Infrastructure*. Retrieved from <https://www2.deloitte.com/content/dam/Deloitte/us/Documents/public-sector/ai-adoption-in-africa-part-ii-data-and-infrastructure-2024-dec.pdf>
- Denzin, N. K., & Lincoln, Y. S. (2018). *The SAGE handbook of qualitative research* (5th ed.). SAGE Publications.
- Effoduh, J. O. (2024). *A Global South Perspective to Explainable Artificial Intelligence*. Carnegie Endowment for International Peace.
- Eteng, I. (2020). *Imam Ashafa and Pastor Wuye: Collaborative Peacebuilding in Nigeria*. Abuja: Peaceworks Publications.
- Falola, T. (2001). *Violence in Nigeria: The Crisis of Religious Politics and Secular Ideologies*. University of Rochester Press.
- Gerring, J. (2017). *Case study research: Principles and practices* (2nd ed.). Cambridge University Press.
- Human Rights Watch. (2003). *The "Miss World Riots": Continued Impunity for Killings in Kaduna*. Retrieved from <https://www.hrw.org/reports/2003/nigeria0703/nigeria0703.pdf>
- Human Rights Watch. (2013). *"Leave Everything to God": Accountability for Inter-Communal Violence in Plateau and Kaduna States, Nigeria*. Retrieved from <https://www.hrw.org/report/2013/12/12/leave-everything-god/accountability-inter-communal-violence-plateau-and-kaduna>
- International Crisis Group. (2014). *Curbing Violence in Nigeria (II): The Boko Haram Insurgency*. Retrieved from <https://www.crisisgroup.org/africa/west-africa/nigeria/curbing-violence-nigeria-ii-boko-haram-insurgency>
- Jegede, O. P. (2019). *Implications of Religious Conflicts on Peace, National Security and Development in Nigeria. Ilorin Journal of Religious Studies*, 9(1), 53-70.
- Kenti-Udom, D. D. (2023). *Information dissemination: Implications for religious conflicts in Nigeria and sustainable development agenda. Niger Delta Journal of Library and Information Science*, 4(1), 149. Retrieved from <https://ndjilis.fuotuoke.edu.ng/index.php/ndjilis/article/download/50/48/96>
- Kwaja, C. (2011, July 31). *Nigeria's Pernicious Drivers of Ethno-Religious Conflict*. Africa Center for Strategic Studies. Retrieved from

<https://africacenter.org/publication/nigerias-pernicious-drivers-of-ethno-religious-conflict/>

- Marx, K. (1848). *The Communist Manifesto*. Penguin Classics.
- McLuhan, M. (1964). *Understanding Media: The Extensions of Man*. MIT Press
- Nsude, I. (2022). *Artificial Intelligence (AI), the Media and Security Challenges in Nigeria. Communication, Technologies et Développement, 11*.
- Okafor, E. E. (2017). *Conflicts Between African Traditional Religion and Christianity in Igboland*. Enugu: Cultural Heritage Press.
- Okonkwo, C. (2019). *Religious Conflicts and Peacebuilding in Africa*. University of Ibadan Press.
- Osajie, J. N. (2021). *Religious Leaders as Agents of Peace and Security for Sustainable Development in Nigeria. UJAH: Unizik Journal of Arts and Humanities, 21(4)*.
- Policy Center for the New South. (2023). *Artificial Intelligence Revolution in Africa: Economic Opportunities and Legal Challenges*. Retrieved from https://www.policycenter.ma/sites/default/files/2023-07/PP_13-23%20%28Jaldi%20%29.pdf
- Smith, M. (2020). *Artificial Intelligence in Conflict Resolution: Emerging Trends and Future Prospects*. Springer.
- UNESCO. (2021). *Recommendation on the Ethics of Artificial Intelligence*. Retrieved from <https://unesdoc.unesco.org/ark:/48223/pf0000380455>
- Vermeer, A. (2020, March 12). *Artificial Intelligence Creeps on to the African Battlefield*. Brookings. Retrieved from <https://www.brookings.edu/articles/artificial-intelligence-creeps-on-to-the-african-battlefield/>
- Wilson Center. (2014, June 17). *Religious Violence in Sub-Saharan Africa and the Future of the Secular State*. Retrieved from <https://www.wilsoncenter.org/event/religious-violence-sub-saharan-africa-and-the-future-the-secular-state-0>

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**Pastoral Pitfalls and Its Implications on
Church Growth in Nigeria**

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Abstract

This work accentuated that the moral and spiritual virtues of many pastors in Nigeria have deteriorated in recent times, and this has dire consequences on the life of the Church. The research is aimed at unravelling the implications of pastoral pitfalls on Church growth and to proffer possible solutions to the menace. Using descriptive phenomenology, the study uncovered that lack of proper theological training and formation, distractions and discouragement, self-control, adherence to biblical virtues, spiritual laziness, and giving in to societal pressure and standard, are some of the reasons why pastors stray from the main calling into the ministry. Consequently, these have negatively affected the general spirituality of the society; stunted church growth, and brought about personal and family reproaches. The work recommended that obedience to the word of God, self-control, discipline, mentoring and openness to the Holy Spirit and personal spiritual development can go a long way in addressing pitfalls among pastors. The pastor should be a man of secret prayer and exacted piety, a man of sound Biblical principles and strong persuasion about his ministry and that the family of the pastor should be contented with the resources available to them. The church, the family of the pastor, as well as the entire society should play a supportive role to pastoral ministry to avoid the temptation of falling away. This way, the life of Church will be restored and growth will be seamless.

Keywords: Pastors, Pitfall, Christianity, Church Growth, Nigeria

Introduction

One of the major news headlines that floods our national dailies and other social media platforms, is the news related to pastoral misdemeanour. While other incidents may attract less attention, that of a pastor may not. It is usually hyped, and sometimes beyond proportion. This is so, because pastors are expected to maintain high moral and spiritual standard and integrity in the society. While not justifying pastors' moral ineptitude, pastoral pitfalls go to affirm that they too are vulnerable to error and temptations. It is out of place (though it ought to be so) to think that pastors are free from sexual temptation, fear of man, envy, greed, pride, anger, bitterness, and idolatry, among others. However, when a pastor is involved in any of the mentioned misconducts, the impact is usually devastating on the congregation, as it retards growth. His family and the entire society, are badly affected. Asserting the above views, Hull (2007) opined that, "in far too many instances, clerics in privileged positions to shepherd the sheep themselves flounder in aimlessness and frustration."

The pastor has as his sole business, the responsibility to expand the Kingdom frontiers. This mandate of the Church, which the pastor is charged to carry out is to, 'make disciples of all nations' (Matthew 28:19). On this, Maxey (1987) postulated that:

The foremost responsibility of a pastor, is to keep clear in his own heart what it takes to produce a spirit-filled Church: a Church devoted to prayer, intercession, thanksgiving, praise, witnessing boldly at home, schools, and shops, devoted to sacrifice of time, money and talents; a membership with missionary vision and burden for the lost, heeding the admonition, 'Go ye into all the world and preach the gospel.'

Unfortunately, there is a total deviation from the main objectives of the ministry mandate by many pastors today. It is this shift from the core mandate that has resulted in the many pitfalls witnessed among pastors in Nigeria. For the pastor to perform the function of producing a spirit-filled congregation, his life and character must conform to his preaching and pastoral activities.

Today, many pastors in Nigeria, are enmeshed with myriads negative trends of immorality, idolatry, financial impropriety, drunkenness, pride,

disobedience and all forms of rivalry and competitions. Thus, many shades of worldly conformity most detrimental to the spiritual influence have infiltrated the ranks and files of the clergy and corrupted the dignity and integrity of ministry and mission work (Bridges, 1980). The result of pastoral pitfalls includes but not limited to, division in the church, dwindling membership, lukewarmness, spiritual lethargy, loss of confidence in the Church, family problems, among others.

The aim of this research is to examine the implications of pastoral pitfalls on Church growth in Nigeria and to proffer possible solution on how this menace can be mitigated. The methodology adopted was that of descriptive phenomenology. Secondary sources of data collection were used in gathering necessary information relevant for this work. The work affirmed that a healthy growing Church is a replica of the life and ministry of her pastor. When the opposite is the case, then, the life of the pastor should be checked. In the next sub-heading, the researcher will consider few salient concepts that formed the nexus of the study.

Delineating the Key Concepts

Under this subheading, the concepts of pastor, pitfall and Church growth, shall be examined. The word 'pastor' from Greek etymology is known as *poimen* (Eph. 4:11). It simply means to care, shepherd or someone who keeps animals. Sometimes, it is used to indicate those chosen by God to feed, lead, and care for the "flock" of Christ (Brand, Draper, and England, 2003). Furthermore, Youngblood (1995), and Still (1996), noted that the pastor is one who feeds, protects, and guides or shepherds the flock of God's people. Thus, going by this positions, one can conveniently say that pastors are shepherds, ministers of the Word, feeders, guides, protectors, leaders, and caretakers of the flock of Christ (Abafi, 20020).

On the other hand, pitfall by definition, means a hidden danger or trap. It is often used to denote situations or temptations that could mislead one if care is not taken. When applied to pastors, it relates to the idea of one not comprehending the context or meaning of Scriptures, which can lead to misinterpretations and wrong application (Bible.org, 2010). To Adoyi (2022), pitfall means, a danger or difficulty, especially one that is not obvious at first and can cause havoc. It is an invisible pit figuratively dug spiritually or emotionally, targeting the down fall of its victims, in this context, the pastor.

Church growth, according to Igboin and Adedibu, (2020), “is that science which investigates the nature, function and health of the Christian church in terms of expansion.” Nmah and Otubah (2024) citing Hunter (1983), maintained that the church is a living organism. It is a community of saints, a “communion sanctorum.” Not just a building or resting place but a people and as a living organism, it is expected to grow, all things being equal (Uka, 1995, Nmah and Otubah, 2024). Thus, church growth is a historical process examining how the church has fared in terms of growth and in its attempt to spread the gospel, since the early times till today. Christianity has grown so widely that it has reached every continent of the world (Falk, 1997).

An Overview of Pitfalls among Pastors Today

There is plethora of pastoral pitfalls in the contemporary society, but a few of them shall be suffice in what follows:

1. ***Sexual Immorality:*** Sexual immorality is one of the key dangers that pastors fall into. This pitfall, has done a lot of damage to pastoral ministry today. Sexual misconduct includes both sexual abuse and sexual harassment. Akerele (2022), observed that a lot of pastors are using sex as a church growth ritual. Some are trapped in it as a work of the flesh because of the distorted doctrine they have been fed with. Adedoyin (2015), noted that pastors involved in sexual misdemeanour take advantage of their position to indulge in sexual misconduct with their female congregations or even with a minor. Kane (2013), said that, it includes sexual malfeasance, which means any voluntary sexual activity in which there is a breach of trust between clergy and member within a professional relationship. The consequences of sex scandals involving the pastors in the church have been lethal and fatal, cutting across all segments of the society (Akerele, 2022).
2. ***Pride:*** Pride, according to Jamieso (2022), is one common pitfall for pastors today. Pride simply means one thinking too highly of oneself. Lewis (2001) argues that pride is the “essential vice,” leading to enmity with God, whether pastors or anyone. Mathis (2019) affirmed that one of the few things that poison the church, and sully her reputation in the world, is arrogance of pastors. It is a great blight on the church and in the community where the church is to shine as the light of the world. *Swelling pride in a leader endangers the whole church.* Crouse (2020) described some enabling factors that can subtly lead to this kind of

pastoral pitfall. Pastors' gifts, eloquence, and position are perfect subtle factors that can lead to pride.

3. ***Professionalism:*** Battzig (2017) noted that the mentality of professionalism, is one of the problems pastors face today. This should not be associated with the pastor, as they are servants of God. Professionalism has nothing to do with the essence and heart of the Christian ministry. The more professional pastors long to be, the more spiritual death they will experience. Thus, thinking professionalism by pastors is a pitfall. (Ministry Magazine, 1961). When pastoral ministry is compared to business outfit, the problem associated with it is endemic. The church is not a business like any other, despite its organizational and financial aspects. The church does not sell products. The minister is not a business man. He is a servant of God with the mandate to represent God on earth. The professionalizing of pastoral work in any form or shape the bane of the church's existence (Batzig, 2017).
4. ***Impatience and Desire to Make Change:*** Segal (2021) said that, impatience is a dark and prevalent sin among pastors that is usually explained away. It is a product of human pride and unbelief, seen in most pastors, as a result of frustration that one does not control what happens in one's life. In the same vein, Jamieso (2022), noted that, plenty of God's work often carried out in human lives takes time. Sometimes God uses setbacks, detours and sufferings to achieve His aims in human lives and pastors should not think that God is delaying their process. So, waiting on the Lord is part God's plan and programmes for pastors. Moses spent forty years in the wilderness twice, to have God's commandment delivered to the Israelites.
5. ***Lack of Accountability and Self-control:*** Another pastoral pitfall witnessed today is that of lack of accountability and self-control. This menace has really pervaded the church ministry. French (2014), lamented in expectation that, there should always be pastors and leaders who can tell the truth. Running from accountability is a sure sign of spiritual turmoil on the part of a pastor. Self-control is a vital ability the ministry should exhibit even in areas that may or may not be classified as sinful. Impulsiveness may be charming, but it is also dangerous, especially when pastors are tasked with caring for the well-being of others. Finance and temper are two areas that are often

troublesome for ministers who struggle with self-control. Furthermore, self-control is a fruit of the Spirit (Galatians 5:22-23). If self-control is not evident in the pastor's life, it is symptomatic of deeper problems lurking under the surface.

Factors Responsible for Pastoral Pitfalls

Some factors can be adduced as reasons why pastors derail from their calling in ministry. Few of such reasons include: lack of proper training for the ministry, abuse of authority, corruption, financial issues, distraction and discouragement and neglecting personal spiritual development.

1. ***Lack of Proper Training:*** Tribune (2017), asserts that lack of proper ministerial training has the tendency of affecting the effectiveness of pastoral agents in serving their congregations and navigating complex situations within the church community. Those seeking to occupy the pastoral roles, are expected to receive basic training and skills development necessary for effective functioning. Lack of it could lead to pitfalls. Akin-John (2017), emphasized that pastors who desire to eschew pitfalls in ministry should be trained on biblical interpretations, pulpit mannerism and pulpit delivery and communication. Pastors should have insight on social media and internet usage, church planting, leadership, relationship, dispute resolution and crises management among others. Pastors aspiring healthy output, should undergo training that develops character, knowledge, personality, communication, relationship and congregation. Lack of these will land such pastors into avoidable challenges and pitfalls (Akin-John, 2017).
2. ***Abuse of Pastoral Authority and Influence:*** Many pastors today are culpable of this pitfall. Abuse of pastoral authority occurs when pastors use their influence to inflict pains on their members. This is in form of psychological, spiritual and emotional damage suffered by members of authoritarian communities of faith, using unethical, cruel and damaging means (Essien, 2010). Sometimes these may be physical or sexual in nature, but much more often, it is seen in the many various forms of mental and spiritual trauma that are inflicted upon church members. The truth remains that pastors who act as dictators are not fulfilling a calling of God but are instead elevating themselves into a position to serve their own self-interests and

- ambitions. They go outside of the biblical teachings for the purpose of fulfilling their desires to control the lives of others (Essien, 2010).
3. **Corruption:** Another important factor responsible for pastoral pitfalls is the prevalence of corruption in the land. Familusi (2010), asserted that corruption in Nigeria, has pervaded the religious environment tremendously. He went on to affirm that people even worship in a corrupt Church, and to an extent, by corrupt pastors. Consequently, the socio-religious implications of corruption in Nigeria becomes innumerable. This has cast some doubts about the future of the Church in Nigeria today and beyond (Oluwatusin, 2020). It is pathetic to remark that a major contemporary manifestation of corruption is schism, which has been taken to a ridiculous extent. Members of the church are usually exploited, impoverished, by the commercialization of spiritual items like anointing oil and others. It has become a scenario where ministries are registered in family names, with the family members overseeing the entire successive leadership of the church. This has become a soft point for pastoral pitfalls in Nigeria (Familusi 2010).
 4. **Materialism and Money Matters:** The love of money has unduly swayed the messages of many pastors, damaged their credibility, or even sunk their ministry entirely, because they failed to pay close attention to money matters in ministry. Pastors should not be focused on financially profiting from ministry. This is a trap that has caught many unaware and ruined their pastoral vocation (Bredenhof, 2021). Paul was mindful of how the love of money can have a corrupting influence on a pastor's ministry. He warned the Church and her pastors to be mindful of it. He went ahead to denounce those who peddle the Word of God for personal profit (2 Cor. 2:17). It is still incumbent on churches today to faithfully support the gospel ministry being done in their midst. Such assistance allows pastors to devote much of their time to the task of serving the church. They can do so without being distracted by material cares or occupied with labours that are unrelated to ministry. While the Church is encouraged to support her pastors financially, pastors should avoid the temptation of embezzling or siphoning church fund for personal aggrandizement.
 5. **Distractions & Discouragement:** Discussing the error of distraction and discouragement, Harvey (2024), said that pastors have more tasks, communication, and job expectations to carry out today, than

ever before. This makes distractions and discouragement two of the most significant mental challenges and pitfalls in ministry. *Postell (2022)*, noted that pastors often face myriads of challenges related to distraction and discouragement, coming from the demanding nature of their job, this includes constant pressure to perform, deal with complex interpersonal issues, and navigate the expectations of a diverse congregation, often leading to feelings of overwhelm and a lack of focus on their core ministry work. All these can weigh the pastor down and lead him to committing error while discharging his duties. To avoid this, churches should encourage and support their pastors. Pastors as well should be intentional with their schedules, willing to delegate auxiliary tasks, and creating a working environment that promotes encouragement (Harvey, 2024).

6. ***Neglecting Personal Spiritual Development:*** One significant danger in ministry is that some pastors channel their energy on studying and building others up spiritually; thus, neglecting to work on their personal spirituality. This naturally creates a weak spiritual framework for pastor's lives, where others are fed spiritually, while they remain hungry. To avoid this weakness, pastors must maintain personal Bible study directed towards their needs. They are to do away with the chasm of prayerlessness (French, 2014). DeYoung (2013), noted that when pastors neglect their personal devotion, it means they are failing to prioritize regular, dedicated time alone with God through prayer and Bible study. This can lead to a decline in their own spiritual health and ability to effectively minister to others in their congregation. In order to fight this particular temptation, pastors should devote time to study and pray regularly.

Pastoral Pitfalls Impinging Church Growth

Churches rise and fall on her pastors. The lifestyle of pastors plays a crucial role in shaping the dynamics of church communities and influencing congregational growth. Various studies have highlighted that the personal conduct, spiritual integrity, and overall lifestyle of pastors significantly affect the faith and commitment of church members, leading to overall growth.

One of the major indices of Church growth is evangelism. When this is affected by pastor's lifestyle, it brings stunted growth for the church. Adedoyin (2015), noted that pastoral pitfall makes the evangelistic effort of

the church unfruitful. When a pastor commits adultery or fornication, it will be difficult for such a church to evangelize. People always find it difficult to attend or listen to churches whose pastors are enmeshed in any form of scandal and this is not healthy for church growth (Job Adeyemo, oral communication, 15th September, 2014).

HI Writers (n.d), observed that the prevalence of immorality among pastors in Nigeria has become alarming. It has grown to a level that creates fear and tension in the heart of anyone who has concern for the future church growth in Nigeria. According to New Testament of the Holy Bible, jealousy, killing, lies, adultery, fornication, theft, heresies, pride and several immoral acts are against the will of God and hinder the progress of church mission. The bastardisation, abuse and mismanagement of wealth among ministers through ostentatious lifestyle, has given reasons for concern in Nigerian churches today. This act has created unhealthy competitions among several ministers that the gospel being preached in most churches today are one sided (anchoring more on prosperity) and no longer balanced with godly and righteous living with self-discipline, which is the hallmark of Christian faith (Omenazu, 2022).

Another critical ethical issue of church growth in Nigeria borders on the fact that church leadership and membership do hardly bother about public perception of the church, and their relationship with outsiders. This is critical because one of the criteria used by the early church to appoint leaders is that they must have honest report among the people (Acts 6:3). Paul also elaborates the criteria and expectations (Tit. 1:5-9; 1 Tim. 3:1-13), emphasizing good report even from people outside the church. Little attention has actually been given to this very important criterion in church growth discourse. The consequence of this has been well articulated by Kinnaman (2012), who concludes that it is unchristian. Studies show that many people outside of Christianity, especially younger adults, have little trust in the Christian faith, and esteem for the lifestyle of Christ's followers is quickly fading in the society. The fact is that the lifestyle of pastors in churches has become a barrier for many people who would have loved to be converted, thereby disrupting church growth (Igboin and Adedibu, 2020).

Mitigating Pastoral Pitfalls

The need to mitigating pastoral pitfalls has become very essential for Church growth. Steps towards ameliorating this hinge on a lot factors,

ranging from the formative stage in ministry to daily personal spiritual development of pastoral agents.

Abafi (2020), emphasized the importance of proper pastoral training, as this will help pastors avoid error capable of destroying their ministry. Pastors are expected to be trained to ensure that the right message is passed on to their congregations in order to build them up and help them stand against pitfalls that are virtually bedeviling the church today. To be a good pastor, one's life must be spent in knowing the truth of God's word, not only verbally, propositionally, and theologically, religiously, devotionally, morally, and otherwise (Abafi, 2020). Prime (1995), suggests that formal training is part of the preparation for the ministry and must be put to the test by those responsible for the training.

Another area of great importance is the worship life of a pastor. The ministers themselves must make sure that they cast their trust in God and live by example. Pastors who are involved in sin cannot give God true worship; neither can they promote it, because no one can give what he or she does not have (Abafi, 2020).

To mitigate pastoral pitfalls, prayer and fasting are key. Aransiola (1999), noted that the major reason why a lot of pastors, including other believers today are unsuccessful, stagnant and amount to nothing in life, is because they do not have altar of prayer. A pastor is not greater than his altar. The success, advancement, increase and consequent breakthrough in every area of life of a pastor is dependent upon his altar of prayer.

Thompson (1995), noted that fasting is cleansing. It cleans out the bodies. It lays bare the souls. It leads the pastors into the arms of God and draws them nearer to Him. When this happens, there is hunger and thirst for justice, for goodness and holiness, for Church growth. Through fasting, pastors put to death earthly desires and long only for the heavenly.

Constant engagement in evangelism can help pastors avoid pitfalls in many respects. In Matthew 5:16, Jesus told His disciples to allow their light shine before men so that they can see their good deeds and praise God, their Father in heaven. Pastors must show the light of God for others to see. The lives of pastors must be a natural overflow of the Christian life. Whitney (1991), noted that evangelism is a discipline and that pastors must discipline themselves to get into the context of evangelism, as this will go a long way in assisting them overcome temptations to sin.

Conclusion and Recommendations

The fact of pastoral pitfall is really evident among members of the clergy in Nigeria. When pastors fall or indulge in any form of crime and immoral behaviour, the attention it draws sometimes outweighs the crime itself. This is because of the high moral, ethical and spiritual integrity expected of pastors in the society. Lack of proper training and formation, misuse of power and authority, distraction and discouragement, not paying attention to spiritual development among others, can lead pastors to various degrees of misconduct.

The impact of pastoral pitfalls is usually germane. It is very endemic and negatively affects the entire society, not excluding the family of the pastor, but more regrettably, retards Church growth. To mitigate this menace, the pastors have to be focused on the essence of their calling, develop a level of spiritual exercise capable of helping them avoid hidden error in their pastoral carrier.

The work further recommends that: Pastors should consciously place self under solemn obligation to live exacted life of piety. By this he should be a man of transparent honesty and purity. Pastors should be men of sound Biblical principles, studious and prayerful. Contentment on the part of the family of the pastor will encourage calmness. Pastors should have a strong persuasion and should receive a strong backing from the family. The church and the society should play a supportive role to pastoral ministry. This way, the pastor will be on his way to fulfilling his calling into the ministry; and the church of God will grow naturally.

References

- Abafi, A.M.G. (2020). Effects of pastors' lifestyle on church members: case study of GYEL local church council of evangelical church winning all. D.Min Thesis Submitted To Asbury Theological Seminary
- Adedoyin, A.D. (2015). Sexual immorality among pastors and its implications to the local church: A case study of Ogbomosho Baptist conference. https://www.Academia.Edu/113399088/Sexual_Immorality_Among_Pastors_And_Its_Implications_To_The_Local_Church_A_Case_Study_Of_Ogbomosho_Baptist_Conference?AutoDownload
- Adoyi, G.O. (2022). Examination of the causes and effects of pastoral pitfalls in Methodist church Nigeria, Zonkwa circuit, Kaduna state. DMin Thesis submitted to Wesley University Ondo

- Akerele, A. (2022). Sexual immorality and the church.
<https://www.Premiumtimesng.Com/Opinion/508738-Sexual-Immorality-And-The-Church-By-Ayo-Akerele.Html?Tztc=1>
- Akin-John, F.B. (2017). Why we need to train, retrain pastors.
<https://Tribuneonlineg.Com/Need-Train-Retrain-Pastors/>
- Aransiola, M. O. (1999). *The secrets of breakthrough prayers*. Ibadan: Gethsemane Publication. Ibadan.
- Batzig, N.T (2017). Being professional in ministry? <https://Feedingonchrist.Org/A-Professional-Ministry/>
- Brand, C.; Draper, C. & England, A. (2003). General Editors. Holman Illustrated Bible Dictionary. Nashville, Tennessee: Holman Bible Publisher.
- Bredenhof, B. (2021). Churches, pastors, and money.
<https://Www.Modernreformation.Org/Resources/Articles/Churches-Pastors-And-Money>
- Bridges, C. (1980). *The Christian ministry*. Pennsylvania: The Banner of Truth Trust.
- Crouse, P. (2020). Pastors, beware of pride https://Ftc.Co/Resource-Library/BlogEntries/Pastors-Beware-Of-Pride/#_Ftn1
- Deyoung, K. (2013). The Danger Of Neglecting Word And Prayer In Gospel Ministry <https://Guardthedeposit.Com/2013/01/Danger-Neglecting-Word-Prayer-Gospel-Ministry/>
- Essen, A.M. (2010). Proliferation of Churches: A leeway to commercialization of religion. *European Journal of Scientific Research* 4(4).
- Familusi. O.O (2010). Corruption and pastoral ministry in the 21st century.
- Falk, P. (1997). *The growth of the church*. Bukuru: Acts
- French, R.A. (2014). 5 ministry pitfalls. <https://Ryanafrench.Com/Ministry-Pitfalls/>
- Harvey, J (2024). Top 10 challenges facing pastors.
<https://www.Subsplash.Com/Blog/Pastor-Problems>
- HI writers (n.d) Immorality in the church and its effects on church growth.
<https://Hiwriters.Com.Ng/Product/Immorality-In-The-Church-And-Its-Effects-On-Church-Growth/>
- Hull, B. (2007). *The disciple-making pastor*. Michigan: Grand Rapids.
- Hunter, K.R. (1983). *Foundations for church growth*. New Haven: Leader Publishing Company.
- Igboin, B. and Adedibu, B.A. (2020). Christian ethics and sustainable church growth in Nigeria. *Journal of African Interdisciplinary Studies (Jais)*: Issn 2523-6725 (Online) May 2020 Vol. 4, No. 5
- Jamieson, B. (2022). Common pitfalls on the path to becoming a pastor.
<https://www.Crossway.Org/Articles/Common-Pitfalls-On-The-Path-To-Becoming-A-Pastor/>
- Kane, M. (2013). Catholic priests' knowledge of pastoral codes of conduct in the United States. *Ethics & Behaviour* Volume 23, Issue 3.

- Mathis, D. (2019). Pride disqualifies a pastor.
<https://www.Desiringgod.Org/Articles/Pride-Disqualifies-A-Pastor>
- Maxey, I. P. (1987). *Ministerial ethics and etiquette*. Ohio: Schmul Publishing Co. Inc.
- Ministry Magazine, (1961) Pitfalls of the ministry.
<https://www.Ministrymagazine.Org/Archive/1961/09/Pitfalls-Of-The-Ministry>
- Nmah, P.E. and Otubah, G. I. (2024). The pathology of church growth in Igbo land, Nigeria: an antidote to the symptoms. *Acjol.Org*
- Omenazu, E. (2022). Impact of gospel ministers' lifestyles on church growth in Nigeria. <https://Independent.Ng/Impact-Of-Gospel-Ministers-Lifestyles-On-Church-Growth-In-Nigeria/>
- Oluwatusin, C.O. (2020). An examination of corruption in Nigeria and the prospect of pastoral ministry. *Light in a once-dark world* Volume 3, November.
<https://www.Biblicaltheology.Com/Light/An%20examination%20of%20corruption%20in%20nigeria%20and%20the%20prospect%20of%20pastoral%20ministry.Pdf>
- Oyetade, M. (2013). The abuse of pastoral authority in some churches in Nigeria today. In *Uma Journal of Philosophy & Religious Studies*.
<https://www.Academia.Edu/103265169/The-Abuse-Of-Pastoral-Authority-In-Some-Churches-In-Nigeria-Today?Auto=Download>
- Postell, M. (2022). Stress tops mental challenges pastors face.
<https://Research.Lifeway.Com/2022/04/26/Stress-Tops-Mental-Challenges-Pastors-Face/>
- Prabhudas, K., (2014). Church leaders' pitfall –part 1.
<https://Gethsemaneipc.Com/Pastoral/Church-Leaders-Pitfalls-1/>
- Prime, D. (1995). *Pastors and teachers*. Glasgow GB: Harper Collins.
- Still, W. (1996). *The work of the pastor*. Edinburgh, GB: Paternoster.
- Thompson, M. J. (1995). *Soul feast: An invitation to the Christian spiritual life*. Louisville, KY John Knox Press
- Whitney, D. (1991). *Spiritual discipline for the Christian life*. Colorado Springs: Navpress.
- Williams, D. (1997). *New concise bible dictionary*. Leicester, England: IVP.
- Youngblood, R. F. (1995). *New illustrated bible dictionary*. Oxford: Thomas Nelson Publishers

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**Congregationalism and Church Growth
in the Baptist Denomination:
Opportunities and Challenges**

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Abstract

Congregationalism emphasises autonomy, participatory governance, and community involvement, potentially influencing church growth. This study explores the relationship between congregationalism and church growth, examining the opportunities and challenges that arise when Congregationalist principles are implemented in local churches. This research analyses Congregationalist theory and church growth research through a mixed-method approach, combining systematic case study and survey. It was found from the study as opportunities that congregationalism fosters ownership and commitment; congregational autonomy encourages creative outreach. In addition, among other challenges, it was discovered that congregational processes can be slow, and balancing individual freedom with collective vision is quite tricky. In conclusion, congregationalism offers opportunities for church growth through empowered membership, contextual relevance, and innovative ministry. However, challenges arise from leadership tensions and resource constraints.

Leadership development, participatory decision making, strategic planning, evaluation, collaboration and partnership are recommendations raised in this work.

Keywords: Participatory Governance, Community Engagement, Autonomy, Leadership, Decision-Making, Ecclesiastical Polity, Discipleship

Introduction

The modern church landscape is characterised by diverse expressions of faith, shifting cultural contexts, and an increasing emphasis on community engagement. Amidst this complexity, congregationalism has emerged as a significant factor in church growth and development. Congregationalism, with its emphasis on local church autonomy, participatory governance, and community involvement, presents both opportunities and challenges for churches seeking to grow and thrive. On the one hand, congregationalism offers a unique potential for church growth through empowered membership, contextual relevance, and innovative ministry. By harnessing the collective wisdom and resources of the congregation, churches can respond effectively to community needs, foster meaningful relationships, and cultivate spiritual vitality. On the other hand, congregationalism also poses significant challenges, including leadership tensions, decision-making inefficiencies, and resource constraints. The delicate balance between individual freedom and collective responsibility can lead to conflicts, while the lack of centralized authority can hinder strategic planning and coordination.

As churches navigate to the intricacies of congregationalism, it is essential to explore the interplay between this governance model and church growth. This study investigates the opportunities and challenges associated with congregationalism, examining its impact on numerical growth, spiritual growth, and community engagement. This research aims to provide insights and recommendations for church leaders, scholars, and practitioners by analysing the theoretical foundations, practical applications, and real-world examples of congregationalism.

Aim and Objectives of the Study

This research aims to explore these dynamics that can inform both theory and practice in Congregational practice. The study is to bring to bear the different opportunities and challenges that are embedded in the

congregational system of church administration. The objectives of this study are to:

1. Examine the relationship between congregationalism and church growth.
2. Identify the opportunities and challenges that arise when Congregationalist principles are implemented in local churches.
3. Analyse the impact of congregationalism on church growth, including numerical growth, spiritual growth, and community engagement.

Statement of the Problem

The relationship between congregationalism and church growth presents a complex and multifaceted issue within contemporary religious studies. Congregationalism, characterised by its emphasis on local church autonomy and democratic governance, raises concerns. Despite the historical significance of congregationalism in promoting community engagement and participation, many congregations face stagnation or decline in membership. This problem is exacerbated by cultural shifts, changing demographics, and competition from alternative forms of spiritual expression. Addressing these questions is essential for understanding how congregationalism can adapt to promote vitality in church growth, ensuring congregations remain relevant and responsive to their communities.

Concept of Congregationalism

Congregationalism is a Christian ecclesiastical governance model emphasising local church autonomy, participatory governance, community involvement, member empowerment, and decentralised authority. According to Beebe (2023), present-day Protestantism, including the Congregational Church, has long roots in the religious and political history of the 16th century. Martin Luther, considered an early founder of Protestantism, while ordained to the priesthood in 1507, was excommunicated in 1521 for his writings challenging the practices of the Catholic Church. Some of his concerns, as seen in his "Ninety-five Theses," included his objection to the corruption of the Church as found in the practice of selling indulgences or guarantees that one could gain salvation if one literally paid the price. German peasants could ill afford this requirement for themselves or their loved ones to enter the kingdom of Heaven.

Luther's teachings instead said that salvation was possible through faith in Jesus, as written in the Bible. His translation of the Bible from Latin into German, the language of his world, was significant not only in that it provided non-clergy access to the teachings, challenging the absolute authority of the Church, but also by allowing the laity to further interpret the Word of God for themselves without the need for a priest. Furthermore, he taught that all baptized Christians were part of the "priesthood," as taught by the apostle Peter in the Bible. This would have a particular influence on the Congregationalists to come.

The significance of Congregationalism lies in its breakaway from the Church of England in the 16th century and its continuing evolution according to Beebe (2023). Congregationalism continues to provide ways by which its members can organize their churches and determine their methods and practices of relating to their faith in God and the teachings of the Bible.

Congregationalism is one of the Protestant traditions. Individual churches and their congregations can be found in Europe, Africa, Asia, Central and South America, the Middle East, Australia, and the United States. Congregational churches believe that God is the only true head of the church. Members, or congregants — hence the name — are free to interpret the Bible on their own without priests or ministers around matters of belief and understanding of the Divine

Congregationalist Theory

Congregational theory according to Bellah (2008) is a model of church governance that emphasizes the autonomy of individual congregations. It posits that each local church is self-governing and has the authority to make decisions without external interference from higher church authorities or denominational structures.

Key features of congregational theory include:

1. **Autonomy:** Each congregation operates independently, determining its own policies, practices, and leadership.
2. **Democratic Governance:** Decisions are often made through congregational meetings where members vote on key issues, promoting a sense of community and shared responsibility.
3. **Biblical Basis:** Proponents often cite scripture to support the idea that early Christians organized themselves in local assemblies, reflecting the model of congregational governance.

4. **Accountability:** While congregations are independent, they are typically accountable to their members, fostering a commitment to transparency and mutual support.

This theory is commonly associated with Baptist, Congregationalist, and some other Protestant traditions.

Concept of Church Growth

Church growth refers to the quantitative and qualitative expansion of a church. It is the process by which a church increases its membership, attendance, and overall influence within a community. It involves several key aspects:

1. **Numerical Growth:** This refers to the increase in the number of people attending services or becoming members of the church.
2. **Spiritual Growth:** Beyond just numbers, church growth also encompasses the deepening of faith and spiritual maturity among congregants.
3. **Community Engagement:** Effective church growth often involves outreach programs and services that positively impact the local community.
4. **Discipleship:** Churches focus on nurturing individuals in their faith journey, equipping them to become active participants in the church and their communities.
5. **Sustainability:** Ensuring that growth is healthy and sustainable over time, rather than just a temporary increase in numbers.

Church growth can be pursued through various strategies, including evangelism, enhancing worship experiences, and fostering a welcoming church environment. Church growth can be measured according to Rainer (2013) through various indicators beyond numerical attendance. Here are some key indicators;

Indicators of church growth can vary widely depending on the context and goals of the congregation. Here are some common indicators:

1. **Attendance:** one of the indicators to assess the growth of a church using attendance.
2. **Worship Services:** An increase in the number of attendees at weekly services.
3. **Special Events:** Higher participation in events such as holidays, baptisms, and community gatherings.

4. *New Members:* Growth in the number of new members joining the church.
5. *Membership Retention:* The ability to retain existing members over time.
6. *Volunteer Participation:* An increase in the number of members involved in church ministries and activities.
7. *Small Groups:* Growth in participation in small groups, Bible studies, and fellowship activities.
8. *Community Involvement:* Increased engagement in community service and outreach programs.
9. *Evangelism Efforts:* Success in reaching new people and converting them to faith programs.
10. *Diversity and Demographic Variety:* A growing diversity in age, ethnicity, and socioeconomic status within the congregation.
11. *Facilities and Resources (Space Utilization):* Increased use of church facilities for various programs and events.
12. *Ministry Expansion:* Development of new ministries and programs to meet the needs of the congregation.
13. *Online Presence (Digital Engagement):* Growth in online attendance and engagement through social media, live streams, or church apps.

Feedback and Surveys

1. *Congregational Surveys:* Positive feedback from members regarding their church experience and satisfaction. Monitoring these indicators can help church leaders assess growth and make informed decisions about future directions and strategies.
2. *Evangelism:* The number of new commitments to Jesus Christ through the church strongly indicates growth. Effective evangelism efforts often lead to an increase in church membership.
3. *Assimilation:* How well new members are integrated into the church community is crucial. This includes participation in small groups, volunteer activities, and other church functions.
4. *Discipleship:* Growth in programs is aimed at developing spiritual maturity among members. Growth in discipleship programs, such as Bible studies and small group involvement, indicates members' deepening faith. This often leads to more mature and committed believers.

5. **Community Engagement:** Active involvement in community service and outreach programs shows that the church is positively impacting its local area. This can attract new members passionate about social justice and community work.
6. **Spiritual Growth:** Indicators such as increased prayer, worship attendance, and personal life change testimonies reflect the congregation's spiritual growth.
7. **Leadership Development:** The emergence of new leaders within the church, including those who take on ministry roles or start new initiatives, is a sign of a healthy and growing church.
8. **Financial Health:** Consistent and generous giving by members can indicate their commitment in the following areas
9. **Tithe Giving Trends:** An increase in tithes and offerings, indicating financial support for the church's mission.
10. **Budget Growth:** Expansion of the church budget to support new initiatives and the church's ability to sustain and expand its ministries.
11. **Baptism:** An increase in the number of baptisms, both water and Holy Spirit baptisms, signifies that people are making public declarations of their faith and experiencing spiritual renewal.

By focusing on these indicators, churches can comprehensively understand their growth and areas that may need more attention.

This study explores these questions through a comprehensive literature review, Survey research and case studies, providing a nuanced understanding of the complex relationship between congregationalism and church growth.

How Congregationalism Enhances Church Growth

Congregationalism, according to Armstrong (2010), emphasizes the autonomy and independence of local congregations, which has played a significant role in the growth of churches. Here are a few key ways in which congregationalism contributes to church growth:

1. **Local Autonomy:** This is anchored on these three principles; Self Government, Self-propagating and Self-financing. Each congregation governs itself, making decisions that best suit its community's needs and context. This flexibility allows churches to be more responsive and adaptive to local issues and cultural dynamics, fostering growth.
2. **Active Participation:** Congregationalism encourages active participation from all members. Since decisions are made collectively,

members feel a stronger sense of ownership and responsibility towards their church, which can lead to increased engagement and growth. The process of involvement and inclusion of every legible member to take part in the decision making of the church is simply called Church Business meeting.

3. **Leadership Development:** With the responsibility to choose their leaders, congregational churches often invest in developing leadership within their community. This focus on nurturing local leaders can lead to more effective ministry and outreach efforts. A succession plan to groom future leaders right from childhood is part of the beauty of leadership development procedures.
4. **Community Focus:** Congregational churches often engage in community service and social justice, aligning their mission with the needs of their local context. This community-oriented approach can attract new members who are passionate about making a difference. The immediate community of churches practicing congregationalism is always a first point of contact in both social responsibility and mission outreaches.
5. **Innovation and Adaptability:** The lack of a rigid hierarchical structure allows congregational churches to innovate and adapt more quickly to changing circumstances. This adaptability can be crucial for growth, especially in rapidly changing social and cultural environments. This flexibility and adaptation mechanism gives each individual church the latitude to operate a model that best fit and prefer either long-term or short-term solution to the challenges facing a particular church.

The principles of congregationalism—local autonomy, active participation, leadership development, community focus, and adaptability—create a fertile ground for church growth by making churches more responsive, engaged, and relevant to their communities.

Methodology

A mixed-methods approach was adopted, specific case study (utilising literature review) and Survey through the distribution of questionnaires to analyse the relationship between congregation and church growth. The works of Hopewell (1989) on congregational studies and Wigner (1987) on the church growth movement were carefully reviewed.) Additionally, data gathered from five selected Baptist churches in Cornerstone Baptist association in Olodo area in Ibadan, Egbeda Local Government area of Oyo

State were analysed using questionnaires (distributed via Google Forms) to gather opinions from active members of these churches.

Analysis and Findings

The following were the findings made during the study after careful analyses of the responses had been gathered. Questionnaires (Google Forms) were distributed on the MMU cornerstone Baptist Association platform with a total of seventy-three (73) members and approximately forty-seven (47) forms were completed. Among the respondents, about thirty-seven (37), representing 78.7%, indicated that properly applying the principle of congregationalism significantly affects and determines the growth rate in a local church. In contrast, the remaining respondents, representing 21.3%, saw no relationship between congregationalism and church growth.

Additionally, thirty-five (35) respondents, representing 74.4% of the total number of the respondents agreed that effective participation of members not only influences church growth but also impacts the rate of community engagement and encourages creative outreach to a large extent. Further findings were discovered while systematically reviewing and analysing the works of Hopewell (1989) on congregational studies and Wigner (1987).

Opportunities of Congregationalism in a Local Church

Congregationalism offers several opportunities for a local church, fostering a vibrant and participatory community. Here are some key benefits derived from the responses and review:

- 1. Empowerment of Members:** Congregationalism emphasises the role of each member in the decision-making process, allowing everyone to have a voice in important matters. This can lead to a greater sense of ownership and responsibility among the congregation.
- 2. Local Church Autonomy:** Each congregation operates independently, making decisions that best suit their specific context and needs. This autonomy allows for flexibility and responsiveness to local issues.
- 3. Enhanced Accountability:** With the congregation having a say in church governance, leaders are held accountable to the members. This can foster transparency and trust within the church community.
- 4. Diverse Perspectives:** Congregationalism encourages a diversity of opinions and ideas, which can lead to more innovative and effective solutions to challenges the church faces.

- 5. *Community Building:*** By involving members in various aspects of church life, congregationalism helps build a strong sense of community and fellowship. This can enhance spiritual growth and mutual support among members.

Challenges of Congregationalism in a Local Church

These were also the cumulative submission of the opinion of members as regards the challenges encountered in a Congregationalist Church:

- 1. *Decision-Making Difficulties:*** With every member having a voice, reaching a consensus can be time-consuming and sometimes contentious. This can slow down decision-making processes and lead to frustration among members.
- 2. *Risk of Division:*** The emphasis on local autonomy can lead to divisions within the church. Differences in opinions on doctrine, governance, or other issues can result in splits and the formation of new congregations.
- 3. *Leadership Challenges:*** Congregationalism can sometimes lead to a lack of clear leadership. Without a hierarchical leadership, which may affect the church's stability and direction.
- 4. *Resource Limitations:*** Independent congregations may struggle with limited resources, both financially and in terms of human resources. This can impact their ability to undertake large projects or provide extensive community services.
- 5. *Accountability Issues:*** While local autonomy is a strength, it can also lead to a lack of accountability. Without oversight from a higher authority, there is a risk of mismanagement or unethical behaviour going unchecked.
- 6. *Balancing Tradition and Innovation:*** Congregational churches may find it challenging to balance respect for tradition with the need for innovation. This can create tension between different groups within the church.

Conclusion

Congregationalism offers a unique framework for the church, emphasising local autonomy and participatory decision-making frame work for the church, emphasizing local autonomy and participatory decision-making. By understanding the opportunities and challenges, the church can harness congregationalism's potential for growth, discipleship and effective ministry.

Recommendations

1. **Leadership development:** Churches should invest in leadership training and development programs. Learning and skill-building should be encouraged among members as mentorship breeds effective leadership.
2. **Participatory Decision-making:** Churches should implement inclusive decision-making processes; Churches should implement inclusive decision-making and promoting open communication and feedback. Equal representation from diverse groups should be ensured.
3. **Prioritise spiritual growth and discipleship** by encouraging small groups, fostering a culture of prayer and worship.
4. **Strategic Planning:** Churches should develop a growth strategy by setting measurable goals and objectives and regularly reviewing and adjusting plans.
5. **Evaluation, collaboration and partnership:** Ensure regular assessment of Church growth and collaborates with denominational organisations by engaging in community development initiatives.

References

- Ammerman, N. T. (1997). *Congregation and Community*. New Brunswick, NJ: Rutgers University Press.
- Armstrong, K. R. (2010). *The Relationship between Congregationalism and Church Growth*. *Journal of Church Growth*, 11(1).
- Beebe J. (2023). *Congregationalism, definition, History and Beliefs*. www.study.com 06/21/24
- Bellah R. (2008). *Denominationalism and congregationalism*. <http://us.sagepub.com>
- Carson, D. A. (2003). *Congregationalism and Church Growth*. *Journal of Evangelical Theological Society*, 46(2).
- Hopewell, J. F. (1987). *Congregational Studies*. Philadelphia, PA: Fortress Press.
- McGavran, D. A. (1970). *Understanding Church Growth*. Grand Rapids, MI: Eerdmans.
- Rainer, T. (2013). *Breakout Churches*. Grand Rapids, MI: Zondervan.
- Schaller, L. E. (1997). *The Interventionist*. Nashville, TN: Abingdon.
- Stetzer, E. (2004). *Planting a Missional Churches*. Nashville, TN: B&H.
- Terry, J. M. (2015). *Congregationalist Polity and Church Growth*. *Review and Expositor*, 112(2).
- Wagner, C. P. (1984). *The Church Growth Movement*. Nashville, TN: Broadman.
- Warren, R. (1995). *The Purpose Driven Church*. Grand Rapids, MI: Zondervan.

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**Christian Ministry in the Artificial
Intelligence (AI) Era: Leveraging Digital
Tools for Pastoral Care and Outreach in the
21st Century**

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Abstract

In the 21st century, artificial intelligence (AI) is increasingly shaping various sectors, including religious practices, by offering transformative possibilities for Christian ministry. As churches navigate a rapidly digitalizing world, AI provides powerful tools to enhance pastoral care and outreach. However, the integration of AI into ministry raises important questions regarding human connection and ethical considerations. This qualitative study examines the role of AI in modern ministry by analyzing existing literature and digital tools. Findings indicate that AI-driven applications can support pastoral counselling, foster prayer networks, and expand evangelism efforts, making spiritual care more accessible. Additionally, AI assists pastors in automating routine tasks, providing personalized support to congregants, and optimizing outreach strategies. However, challenges such as potential loss of human connection, privacy concerns, and algorithmic biases must be addressed. The study concludes that while AI enhances efficiency and reach, it cannot

replace the relational aspects central to Christian ministry. A balanced approach is necessary to ensure AI complements rather than substitutes human interaction. This paper proposes a framework for integrating AI into ministry while upholding core Christian values of empathy, equality, and care.

Keywords: Christian Ministry, Artificial Intelligence (AI), Digital Tools, Pastoral Care, 21st Century.

Introduction

The 21st century has ushered in a period of unprecedented technological progress, transforming many aspects of life, including outreach and pastoral care. Digital tools now provide religious leaders with expanded opportunities to connect with followers, offer support, and reach wider audiences (Campbell, 2021). This introduction discusses the significance of digital tools in pastoral care, the historical context of their adoption, and the practical and theological implications of this digital shift. The use of technology in ministry is not new; religious organizations have historically employed various tools to enhance communication and outreach, as seen with the printing press—which revolutionized access to the Bible (Eisenstein, 1980)—and later with radio and television broadcasts reaching larger audiences (Campbell, 2021).

The advent of the internet and digital technologies in the late 20th and early 21st centuries, as explained by Bingaman (2018), has exponentially expanded the possibilities for pastoral care and outreach. The rise of social media, mobile apps, and live-streaming platforms has enabled real-time interaction between religious leaders and congregants, regardless of distance. This shift was further accelerated by the COVID-19 pandemic, which required rapid adoption of online platforms for worship and community support (Allred, 2024).

Integrating digital tools into pastoral care raises significant theological questions regarding presence, community, and the role of technology in spiritual practices (Campbell, 2021). A key theological consideration is the concept of the *imago Dei*, or “image of God” (Genesis 1:27, New International Version), and its relationship to digital interactions. Christian theology asserts that humans, made in God’s image, hold unique dignity and capacity for relationship with both God and others (McGrath, 2012). As digital tools challenge traditional notions of presence and community, theologians are exploring how virtual interactions can reflect the *imago Dei* (Campbell, 2021; McGrath, 2012).

When it comes to AI tools in interpreting the scriptures as modern ministers and theologians do, Ojieabu (2024) believes that the integration of artificial intelligence (AI) into biblical hermeneutics introduces innovative tools for interpreting ancient texts. While AI can enhance human capabilities and provide valuable insights, it cannot replace the nuanced interpretations offered by human scholars. He further states that the collaboration between AI and human interpreters promises a more informed approach to understanding sacred scriptures. However, it is crucial to address the ethical implications of using AI in pastoral care and outreach to ensure responsible and inclusive application. Balancing AI's potential with rigorous scholarship can enrich biblical engagement and foster the exploration of new insights in its interpretation. Bingaman (2018), in his work on digital-age pastoral care, emphasizes the importance of thoughtful theological reflection on digital technologies. He argues that while digital tools can enhance pastoral care, their use must uphold core values of human dignity, compassion, and relationality, thereby balancing technological innovation with theological principles to ensure that digital ministry remains aligned with the essence of the Christian faith.

Digital tools offer diverse practical applications in pastoral care. Social media platforms like Facebook, Twitter, and Instagram enable religious leaders to share messages, post updates, and engage with congregants, providing immediate responses to community needs. Live-streaming services like YouTube and Zoom allow churches to broadcast worship services, Bible studies, and other events globally, fostering a sense of community among dispersed members, particularly during times when physical gatherings are limited, such as the COVID-19 pandemic. Additionally, many churches have developed mobile apps that provide resources like daily devotionals, event calendars, and online giving options, promoting engagement by giving members easy access to spiritual resources. Afolaranmi (2020) suggests that the COVID-19 lockdown significantly accelerated the digital pivot within Christian ministries in Nigeria, demonstrating that rapid adoption of digital platforms was critical for sustaining community engagement and delivering pastoral care during periods of restricted physical interaction. Take for example, Pastor (Dr.) Williams Kumuyi, General Superintendent of the Deeper Christian Life Ministry (DCLM), who introduced a groundbreaking AI technology poised to transform gospel outreach. Dubbed "Ask Kumuyi AI," the innovative platform harnesses artificial intelligence to disseminate the gospel,

according to The Nation. Launched yesterday at the Leadership Strategic Congress 2025 held at the Deeper Life International Conference Centre (DLICC) in Mowe, Ogun State, this high-tech tool will enable people worldwide to access Jesus' message through the pastor's sermons, among other features (The Nation, 2025).

The advantages of digital tools in pastoral care are numerous, with accessibility being a major benefit. Digital platforms allow individuals who may be unable to attend in-person services due to distance, health issues, or other limitations—to participate in worship and community activities, increasing inclusivity by reaching marginalized or isolated individuals. Digital tools also enhance engagement by offering interactive features, such as online discussion forums, live chats during services, and social media comments, which foster a sense of community and belonging in virtual spaces.

Moreover, digital tools provide convenient access to a wide range of resources, including online libraries of sermons, Bible studies, and educational materials, enabling individuals to engage with spiritual content at their own pace. This flexibility is especially helpful for those with busy schedules or in different time zones.

A Brief Historical Overview of Artificial Intelligence (AI)

The concept of artificial intelligence has roots in ancient civilizations, where early thinkers first explored the nature of thought and reasoning (Nilsson, 2009). Philosophers like Aristotle pondered ideas that would later shape investigations into machine intelligence (Cohoe, 2022). In the 17th century, René Descartes proposed that both humans and animals could be seen as complex machines, suggesting a foundation for simulating human thought (Shapiro, 2006).

The mid-20th century is often recognized as the official beginning of AI research. British mathematician and logician Alan Turing introduced the "Turing Test" in his groundbreaking 1950 paper, *Computing Machinery and Intelligence* (Turing, 1950), which proposed a way to assess whether a machine could exhibit behavior indistinguishable from human intelligence. Turing's work laid essential groundwork for AI research. In 1956, the Dartmouth Conference—organized by John McCarthy, Marvin Minsky, Nathaniel Rochester, and Claude Shannon—marked the formal establishment of AI as an academic discipline, bringing together leading

researchers to discuss the potential for machines to simulate human intelligence (McCarthy, 2007).

The 1950s and 1960s saw substantial progress in AI. Early AI programs like the "Logic Theorist," developed by Allen Newell and Herbert A. Simon, demonstrated machines' potential for solving complex problems, including mathematical theorems, marking a breakthrough in symbolic AI (Newell & Simon, 1972). Another milestone was Newell and Simon's development of the "General Problem Solver" (GPS) in 1957, designed to mimic human problem-solving by breaking down problems into smaller sub-problems (Newell & Simon, 1972).

In the 1980s and 1990s, AI research focused on machine learning—specifically, creating algorithms that allow machines to learn from data. Neural networks, inspired by the structure and function of the human brain, gained popularity. Researchers such as Yann LeCun and Geoffrey Hinton made significant contributions to deep learning and neural networks, highlighted by the development of the backpropagation algorithm in 1986 by Hinton, Rumelhart, and Williams (Hinton, Rumelhart, & Williams, 1986). This algorithm, which allows neural networks to adjust weights in response to errors, remains fundamental to modern deep learning.

Despite these early advances, AI faced challenges during the "AI winters" of the 1970s and 1980s, periods marked by reduced funding and interest due to unmet expectations and technical limitations. However, the field revived in the late 1990s and early 2000s, fueled by improved computational power, large datasets, and better algorithms. Notable achievements included IBM's *Deep Blue* defeating world chess champion Garry Kasparov in 1997, demonstrating AI's potential to surpass human performance in specific tasks (Campbell, Hoane, & Hsu, 2002).

In recent years, AI has experienced rapid advancements due to the proliferation of big data, enhanced hardware, and sophisticated algorithms. Today, AI technologies are embedded in numerous industries such as healthcare, finance, transportation, and entertainment. One prominent application is natural language processing (NLP), used by AI-powered virtual assistants like Apple's Siri, Amazon's Alexa, and Google Assistant to understand and respond to human language. AI is also crucial in image and speech recognition, autonomous vehicles, and personalized recommendation systems on platforms such as Netflix and Amazon (Russell & Norvig, 2016).

Integration of AI in Pastoral Care and Counselling

Many pastors and Christian counsellors who want to incorporate technology into their ministry may struggle with the rapid evolution of digital trends (Campbell, 2021). While maintaining the essential human element, AI can be a powerful tool in ministry, serving God's purposes. AI and machine learning are already enhancing pastoral and general care (Campbell, 2021). For instance, an innovative pilot project by the Centre for Theological Inquiry in Princeton, New Jersey, has been reported as utilizing the virtual reality game *Minecraft* to engage youth (Casberg, 2016). According to project coordinator Katharina, the goal is to encourage neurodiverse youth to explore Christian spirituality. By employing AI bots within *Minecraft*, young players can engage with Christian discipleship concepts through collaboration within a familiar digital environment (Campbell, 2021).

In the United States, a data-processing company offers churches tools for targeting mission activities toward individuals most likely to need pastoral care, now or in the future. Katharina highlights how big data analysis can support ministries by identifying groups, such as those facing potential divorce or mental health vulnerabilities. In Italy, as Laura (2023) illustrates, AI robots provide in-home support for the elderly, a model with potential applications in Christian-owned care homes. Additionally, AI-powered chatbots can answer questions about faith for individuals who may prefer a non-human interface. Boettcher (2023) humorously suggests that pastors might even use AI for compatibility testing to help couples determine compatibility before marriage, noting that many couples meet through online platforms.

Future applications could extend to diagnosing and addressing spiritual health. For example, pastors could potentially use AI to select Bible verses for study groups or suggest theological readings. AI-powered speech technologies also support those unable to speak, such as theoretical physicist Stephen Hawking or comedian Lee Ridley, who use voice devices. AI captioning now provides hearing-impaired individuals with greater access to auditory-focused environments. Through these technologies, people with speech or hearing impairments can lead worship, preach, and provide pastoral care, empowering them to participate fully in ministry.

However, the use of AI raises significant privacy and ethical concerns. AI relies on personal data, raising the risk of exploitation through surveillance capitalism, where personal information is commodified and often managed across complex legal jurisdictions. AI assistants, like Alexa or Siri, that

"listen" for activation phrases worry some individuals due to privacy concerns. More concerning would be the potential for private counselling sessions to be streamed to the cloud for AI captioning, posing serious risks to confidentiality.

AI can enhance user independence by reducing reliance on a sign-language interpreter, but it also risks creating new barriers to interpersonal connection. While these technologies can offer vital support, it is essential to ensure that they complement, rather than replace, human relationships. The goal is not to maintain barriers that prevent people with disabilities from participating in social and religious life; rather, it is to approach technology with caution to avoid unintended obstacles and ensure it enhances rather than limits human interaction.

Integrating AI in Outreach Ministry

There is ongoing debate about whether it is appropriate for Christians to use AI in ministry. However, with a thoughtful approach, AI can be a powerful tool for spreading the Gospel and benefiting the church. Artificial intelligence (AI) is already present in our lives, though some church leaders and digital evangelists still have questions about its origins, functionality, and role in ministry.

According to Nelson (2023), AI can be used ethically in evangelism, provided it respects the privacy and autonomy of individuals and avoids tactics that could be perceived as intrusive or coercive. Used responsibly, AI can be a helpful instrument for spreading the gospel, reaching even more people with the message of Christ. AI, which has been in development for many years, involves creating computer programs capable of tasks such as decision-making, problem-solving, and speech recognition—activities traditionally requiring human intelligence. AI is designed to enhance human abilities and streamline operations across industries, including healthcare, finance, transportation, and communication. Its potential is immense, but its effectiveness relies on how well it is programmed and trained. For example, ChatGPT gathers information from a variety of sources, including online databases and human input, continuously learning and adapting based on interactions. To ensure trustworthy operation, it is essential that AI is trained with accurate and unbiased data.

For Christians, there is no inherent reason to avoid using AI, particularly in today's digital age. Christians already interact with AI daily through platforms like YouTube, Google, and Facebook. However, as with any tool,

it is important to use AI in ways that align with biblical values and principles, upholding ethical and responsible use and respecting others' privacy. Thoughtfully applied, AI can help Christians share Christ's message in ways that are impactful and respectful. Nelson notes that while AI lacks the soul to create life-changing messages, it can still be a valuable tool for communicating God's transformative message to people worldwide. AI should not replace the divine inspiration unique to God, but it can function as an instrument—much like a car, calculator, or digital Bible—that helps spread His message more effectively. AI can assist in evangelism by supporting the unique role of preaching and spiritual counseling within the Christian faith. For example, pastors can use ChatGPT to repurpose sermons, making their messages accessible to a wider audience without sacrificing authenticity. By analyzing existing sermons, AI can generate new content while adapting to the pastor's voice and tone. Repurposing sermons in this way allows pastors to extend their message's reach, providing broader access to their insights and teaching.

In addition, AI can generate high-quality images to support sermons or enhance church websites. For instance, an AI tool can create illustrations of biblical characters or scenes, such as Moses parting the Red Sea. This capability saves time, freeing church staff to focus on other aspects of ministry. Additionally, churches can use AI to optimize social media posts for different platforms, reaching audiences more effectively. AI can also support personalized and efficient newsletters, tailoring content to members' interests. Church newsletters can strengthen community ties, provide updates on church events, and offer spiritual guidance. They also create a platform for sharing stories, prayer requests, and volunteer opportunities, fostering open communication within the church. Moreover, AI can help churches create engaging blog articles for their websites, enhancing their online presence and providing valuable information to both members and visitors. AI-generated content is also beneficial for Search engine optimization (SEO), as algorithms can analyze keywords for maximum visibility. However, while AI can generate content quickly, it requires human oversight to ensure accuracy, emotional intelligence, and alignment with the church's message.

Finally, AI can break down language barriers, making it easier for churches to reach global audiences. AI translation tools can help churches communicate with diverse communities, but human editors are essential to maintain cultural and linguistic sensitivity, ensuring that translations

reflect the church's intended message and values. AI is a powerful tool that can support church ministry in numerous ways, yet it is not a substitute for human interaction, inspiration, or oversight. As churches integrate AI into their evangelism strategies, it is crucial to remain grounded in core values, ensuring that AI use aligns with Christian mission and principles.

Theological Challenges of AI in the 21st Century

The impact of AI on our understanding of humanity and the *imago Dei* (image of God) is one of the main theological concerns surrounding its use. Christian theology holds that, because humans are made in God's image (Genesis 1:26-27), they possess unique dignity, moral agency, and the capacity for deep relational connections with both God and one another. This belief informs the ethical considerations surrounding AI as a human invention; AI reflects human creativity and inventiveness, which can be seen as an extension of the *imago Dei*, mirroring human abilities for problem-solving and innovation (Psalm 8:5-6). Yet, the development of AI capable of learning, reasoning, and making decisions—raises questions about what truly sets humans apart in creation.

Xu (2023) argues that, while AI can mimic certain cognitive processes, it lacks the consciousness and moral responsibility intrinsic to humans. This distinction is central to theological discussions, emphasizing that humans, uniquely able to discern and respond to God's will (Psalm 139:13-16), hold a distinct role in creation that AI cannot replicate. Theologians like Xu further argue that AI, as a product of human ingenuity, does not share the moral obligations inherent to human nature. This distinction carries significant implications for AI's use in decision-making in sectors like healthcare, law, and warfare, where ethical considerations must prioritize human dignity and justice (Micah 6:8). Moreover, the ethical use of AI raises concerns about bias, transparency, and accountability.

In addition, Ojjeabu (2024) posits that the rise of artificial intelligence (AI) technology, particularly among young people, has played a role in the erosion of Christian moral values. The accessibility of AI tools and applications has facilitated seamless communication and interaction. While AI offers numerous benefits, including advancements in research and enhanced connectivity, it also exposes users to harmful and immoral influences. These negative experiences can undermine traditional Christian teachings, presenting significant challenges in upholding moral integrity in an increasingly AI-driven world. Also, SpringerLink (2020) highlights that

AI systems, often trained on large datasets, may inadvertently perpetuate biases, resulting in unjust outcomes. Proverbs 11:1 emphasizes God's desire for fairness and just scales, reminding us of the moral imperative to ensure that AI systems are designed and employed in ways that uphold fairness and transparency.

The integration of AI into religious practices brings both potential benefits and theological challenges. AI tools can enhance religious experiences by providing personalized spiritual support, enabling multilingual communication, and managing administrative tasks. For instance, AI chatbots may offer spiritual guidance tailored to individual needs. However, the use of AI in sacred contexts, such as AI-generated sermons or robotic ministers, challenges traditional views on worship and the human role in clergy. Xu's research underscores the importance of human embodiment and consciousness in worship, suggesting that AI cannot fully replace the human experience of spiritual connection, as echoed in Romans 12:1, which calls believers to offer themselves as "living sacrifices."

It is imperative to theologically reflect on the profound societal implications of Artificial Intelligence. As AI has the potential to reshape employment, social interactions, and identity, a robust theological response is necessary, one that upholds the values of human dignity, justice, and the common good (Isaiah 1:17). As theologians engage with AI, they are called not only to address its technical capabilities but also to consider its ethical and cultural implications, particularly how it influences human identity, relationships, and societal structures. Through theological inquiry, the church can provide ethical guidance, ensuring that AI advances human flourishing and respects the divine image within each person (Matthew 22:37-39).

Pros of AI to Christian Ministry

The advent of Artificial Intelligence (AI) has revolutionized various aspects of modern life, including Christian ministry. By leveraging AI-powered tools, churches can enhance their outreach, engagement, and pastoral care, ultimately fulfilling the Great Commission more effectively. This essay explores the benefits of AI in Christian ministry, highlighting its potential to increase accessibility, personalize engagement, streamline administrative tasks, and improve sermon preparation and pastoral care (Dustin, 2024).

1. ***Enhancing Accessibility and Outreach:*** One of the most significant advantages of AI in Christian ministry is its ability to enhance

accessibility and outreach. AI-powered tools like live streaming and social media platforms enable churches to reach a global audience, breaking geographical barriers and allowing people from different parts of the world to participate in services and events (Romans 10:18). This increased accessibility enables churches to fulfill their mission to "go and make disciples of all nations" (Matthew 28:19).

2. ***Personalizing Engagement:*** AI also enables churches to personalize their engagement with congregation members. By analyzing data, AI can provide personalized content and recommendations, helping churches tailor their messages to individual needs and preferences (1 Corinthians 9:22-23). This personalized approach can lead to more effective evangelism, discipleship, and community building (Justin, 2023).
3. ***Streamlining Administrative Tasks:*** In addition to enhancing outreach and engagement, AI can also streamline administrative tasks, freeing up time for pastors and church staff to focus on more meaningful activities. AI-powered tools can automate routine tasks such as scheduling, communication, and data management (1 Corinthians 12:28). This increased efficiency enables churches to allocate more resources to ministry and outreach (Dustin, 2024)
4. ***Improving Sermon Preparation and Pastoral Care:*** AI can also improve sermon preparation and pastoral care. AI-powered research tools can quickly analyze vast amounts of theological texts, commentaries, and historical documents, providing pastors with valuable insights and resources for sermon preparation (2 Timothy 2:15). Additionally, AI-powered editing tools can assist in refining sermon drafts, checking for grammar and style, and ensuring clarity and coherence.
5. ***Enhancing Pastoral Care through Virtual Support:*** AI can enhance pastoral care by providing virtual counseling and support. AI chatbots and virtual assistants can offer a listening ear and direct individuals to appropriate resources or human counselors when needed (Galatians 6:2). AI can also help monitor the well-being of congregation members by analyzing communication patterns and identifying those who may need additional support (Proverbs 11:14).

Hence, the integration of AI in Christian ministry has the potential to revolutionize outreach, engagement, and pastoral care. By leveraging AI-powered tools, churches can increase accessibility, personalize engagement,

streamline administrative tasks, and improve sermon preparation and pastoral care. As churches continue to navigate the complexities of the digital age, embracing AI can help them fulfill their mission to spread the Gospel and make disciples of all nations.

Some of the Cons of AI to Christian Ministry

The integration of Artificial Intelligence (AI) in Christian ministry has been hailed as a revolutionary step forward, enabling churches to reach a wider audience, streamline administrative tasks, and enhance pastoral care. However, beneath the surface of this technological advancement lies a complex web of concerns that threaten the very fabric of Christian community and ministry. This essay delves into the cons of AI in Christian ministry, examining the loss of personal connection, ethical and theological concerns, privacy and security issues, and dependence on technology.

- 1. *Loss of Personal Connection:*** One of the most significant drawbacks of AI in Christian ministry is the loss of personal connection. Relying too heavily on AI for pastoral care and communication can lead to a loss of personal touch, which is crucial in building and maintaining relationships within the church community. As churches increasingly utilize AI-powered chatbots and virtual assistants, the opportunities for face-to-face interactions, essential for fostering a sense of community and belonging, are reduced (Erin, 2023).
- 2. *Ethical and Theological Concerns:*** AI systems can perpetuate biases present in their training data, leading to unfair or discriminatory outcomes. This raises ethical concerns about justice and equality in ministry, highlighting the need for careful consideration and regulation of AI systems in Christian contexts. Theological implications of AI in religious practices also challenge traditional concepts, such as the role of human clergy and the nature of worship (Sterling, 2023).
- 3. *Privacy and Security Issues:*** In addition to these concerns, AI systems pose significant privacy and security risks. The collection and analysis of personal data by AI systems raise concerns about privacy and the potential misuse of sensitive information. Moreover, AI systems are vulnerable to cyberattacks, which can compromise the security of church data and communications (Ron, 2024).
- 4. *Dependence on Technology:*** Finally, the over-reliance on AI and technology can lead to a dependency that may be problematic if

technical issues arise or if there is a lack of access to technology. This digital divide can create a gap in outreach efforts and potentially exclude some individuals from participating in church activities (Erin, 2023).

Hence, while AI has the potential to enhance Christian ministry, it is crucial to acknowledge and address the cons of its integration. By recognizing the loss of personal connection, ethical and theological concerns, privacy and security issues, and dependence on technology, churches can take steps to mitigate these risks and ensure that AI is used in a way that complements and enhances human relationships and ministry.

Conclusion

The integration of digital tools into pastoral care and outreach represents a significant shift in how religious leaders engage with their congregations. While there are challenges to overcome, the benefits of digital ministry are substantial, offering increased accessibility, enhanced engagement, and a wealth of resources. As technology continues to evolve, it is essential for theologians and religious leaders to reflect on the theological and ethical implications of digital tools and ensure that their use aligns with the core values of the Christian faith. By doing so, digital ministry can continue to thrive and serve the needs of the modern church community.

Recommendations

1. **Acknowledge and Address the Risks of AI:** Churches must recognize the challenges AI presents, such as the loss of personal connection, ethical and theological concerns, privacy and security risks, and over-dependence on technology.
2. **Mitigate Risks:** Steps should be taken to address these issues proactively, ensuring that the potential downsides of AI integration are minimized.
3. **Use AI to Complement Human Relationships:** Churches should focus on using AI as a tool to enhance, rather than replace, human relationships and ministry efforts.
4. **Ensure Ethical Implementation of AI:** Churches should carefully consider the ethical implications of AI, ensuring fairness, justice, and equality in its applications within ministry.

5. Safeguard Privacy and Security: Adequate measures must be taken to protect sensitive church and member data from misuse or cyberattacks.
6. Bridge the Digital Divide: Efforts should be made to ensure accessibility to technology so that all members of the community can participate fully, preventing exclusion due to lack of resources or technological access.

References

- Afolaranmi, A. O. (2020). "Effects of Covid-19-Pandemic Lockdown of Churches in Nigeria on Pastoral Ministry: Matters Arising". *EPRA International Journal of Multidisciplinary Research (IJMR)*. 6(6), June 2020. 164-171.
<https://doi.org/10.36713/epra4637>
- Allred, K. (2024). *Embracing the digital shift: Navigating church communications in the AI era*.
[https://www.thechurchnetwork.com/Online/Content/Embracing the Digital Shift Navigating Church Communications in the AI Era.aspx](https://www.thechurchnetwork.com/Online/Content/Embracing_the_Digital_Shift_Navigating_Church_Communications_in_the_AI_Era.aspx)
- Altar Live. (2023). *10 essential tools for pastors in the digital age*.
<https://www.altarlive.com/blog/10-essential-tools-for-pastors-in-the-digital-age>
- Bingaman, K. A. (2018). *Pastoral and spiritual care in a digital age: The future is now*. America Psychological Association (APA). Lexington Books/Rowman & Littlefield
- Borgmann, A. (2003). Holding on to reality: The nature of information at the turn of the millennium, 288. University of Chicago Press.
- Brooks, D. (2024). The Second Mountain: The Quest for a Moral Life. *Sage Journal* 20(3), 346. <https://doi.org/10.1177/07398913241228459g>
- Campbell, H. A., & Tsuria, R. (Eds.). (2021). *Digital religion: Understanding religious practice in digital media* (2nd ed.). Routledge.
- Campbell, M., Hoane, A. J., & Hsu, F. H. (2002). Deep Blue. *Artificial Intelligence*, 134(1-2), 57-83.
- Casberg, C. T. (2016, November 11). Christianity Today: The surprising theological possibilities of virtual reality.
<https://www.christianitytoday.com/2016/11/surprising-theological-possibilities-of-virtual-reality/>
- Cohoe, C. (Ed.). (2022). References. In Aristotle's On the Soul: A Critical Guide (pp. 265-278). ref-list, Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
- Crevier, D. (1993). AI: The Tumultuous History of the Search for Artificial Intelligence. Basic Books. *Scientific Research*.
https://www.researchgate.net/publication/233820788_AI_The_Tumultuous_History_of_the_Search_for_Artificial_Intelligence.

- Deeper Life Bible Church. (2025, January 15). *Ask Kumuyi AI: Transforming digital ministry*. <https://www.deeperlife.org/>
- Eisenstein, E. L. (1980). *The printing revolution in early modern Europe*. Cambridge University Press.
- Erin C. (2023). *The Sermonator: Exploring the Pros and Cons of Using AI Technology in Ministry*. <https://replantbootcamp.com/exploring-using-ai-technology-in-ministry/>
- Gugerty, L. (2006). Newell and Simon's Logic Theorist: Historical Background and Impact on Cognitive Modeling. *Proceedings of the Human Factors and Ergonomics Society Annual Meeting*, 50(9), 880-884. <https://doi.org/10.1177/154193120605000904>
- Hinton, G. E., & LeCun, Y. (1986). Learning representations by back-propagating errors. *Nature*, 323(6088), 533-536.
- Hinton, G. E., Rumelhart, D. E., & Williams, R. J. (1986). Learning representations by back-propagating errors. *Nature*, 323(6088), 533-536. <https://doi.org/10.1038/323533a0>
- Katharina Gellein Viken, Matt Engel, Gloo / Barna Group. Metrotone Media. <https://metrotone-media.com/2020/10/23/matt-engel-gloo-barna-group/>
- Kenny, J. (2024). *Pro's and Con's of using AI for sermon writing: 18 issues to consider*. <https://exponential.org/pros-and-cons-of-using-ai-for-sermon-writing-18-issues-to-consider/>
- Laura Lezza. (2023). Robot looks after residents at Italian care home – in pictures. *The Guardian*. <https://www.theguardian.com/technology/gallery/2015/dec/21/robot-looks-after-residents-at-italian-care-home-in-pictures>
- McCarthy, J. (2007). What is artificial intelligence? <http://www-formal.stanford.edu/jmc/whatisai.html>
- McCarthy, J., Minsky, M. L., Rochester, N., & Shannon, C. E. (1956). A proposal for the Dartmouth Summer Research Project on Artificial Intelligence.
- McGrath, A. E. (2012). *Christian theology: An introduction* (5th ed.). Wiley-Blackwell.
- Moore, J. (2023). The Benefits of AI in the Church. <https://youtu.be/1ZI0KEISOQc>
- Nelson, M. (2023). Six healthy ways to use AI for evangelism. Retrieved 13/10/24, from <https://www.delmethod.com/blog/ai-for-evangelism>.
- Newell, A., & Simon, H. A. (1957). GPS, a program that simulates human thought. *Science*, 134(3495)
- Newell, A., & Simon, H. A. (1972). *Human problem solving*. Prentice-Hall.
- Nilsson, N. J. (2009). *The quest for artificial intelligence: A history of ideas and achievements*. Cambridge University Press.
- O'Donnell, Karen. (2018). "Performing the Imago Dei: Human Enhancement, Artificial Intelligence and Optative Image-Bearing." *International Journal for the Study of the Christian Church* 18(1), 4-15.

- Ojieabu, S. O. (2024). From automation to augmentation: The potential of artificial intelligence in biblical hermeneutics. *Crowther Journal of Arts and Humanities*, 1(4).
- Ojieabu, S. O., & Izilein, A. (2024). The role of religion as a landmark in curbing societal decay caused by technology. *HUMANUS DISCOURSE*, 4(3).
<http://humanusdiscourse.website2.me>
- ResourceUMC. (2023). *Digital parish: Pastoral care in the age of technology*.
<https://www.churchofireland.org/cmsfiles/pdf/Information/CIP/digital.pdf>
- Ron H. (2024). *The Ethics of AI: Navigating the Moral Maze of Artificial Intelligence*. <https://d6family.com/the-ethics-of-ai-navigating-the-moral-maze-of-artificial-intelligence>
- Rumelhart, D. E., Hinton, G. E., & Williams, R. J. (1986). Learning representations by back-propagating errors. *Nature*, 323(6088), 533-536.
- Russell, S., & Norvig, P. (2016). *Artificial intelligence: A modern approach* (3rd ed.). Pearson. 1-29.
- Ryan D. (2024). A Christian's Perspective on Artificial Intelligence.
<https://christooverall.com/article/longform/a-christians-perspective-on-artificial-intelligence/>
- Samson, O. O., Donald A. O. (2023). *Leveraging technology for improved pastoral care and counselling services in Africa*. *Research Journal of Humanities and Cultural Studies*, 10(4)E-ISSN 2579-0528
- Shanen B. (2023). *Artificial intelligence and spirituality: relating religious information and religious knowledge*. St. Andrew's Research Repository: St. Andrew's University. <https://doi.org/10.17630/sta/364>
- Shapiro, L. (2006). Descartes's passions of the soul. *Philosophy Compass*, 1(3), 268–278. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1747-9991.2006.00022.x>
- SpringerLink. (2020). *Religious and spiritual experience in the digital age: Unprecedented evolutionary forces*. *Pastoral Psychol* 69, 291–305
- Sterling M. A. (2023). Theological and Ethical Dangers of AI in Religious Settings. *Firebrand Magazine*. <https://firebrandmag.com/articles/the-theological-and-ethical-dangers-associated-with-using-artificial-intelligence-in-christian-religious-settings>
- The Holy Bible: New King James Version*. (1982). Thomas Nelson Publishers.
- The Holy Bible: New International Version*. (2011). Zondervan Publishes.
- The Nation. (2025, January 15). *Pastor Kumuyi launches Ask Kumuyi AI at Leadership Strategic Congress 2025*. The Nation.
<https://thenationonlineng.net/>
- Turing, A. M. (1950). Computing machinery and intelligence. *Mind*, 59(236), 433-460.
- Turing, A. M. (1950). Computing machinery and intelligence. *Mind*, 59(236), 433–460. <https://doi.org/10.1093/mind/LIX.236.433>

- Xu, S. (2023). *Understanding AI from a theological perspective*. Edinburgh Futures Institute. <https://efi.ed.ac.uk/understanding-ai-from-a-theological-perspective/>
- Young, C. (2024). *The intersection of artificial intelligence and Christian thought: A vision for the future*. <https://ccta.regent.edu/the-intersection-of-artificial-intelligence-and-christian-thought-a-vision-for-the-future/>

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**Reclaiming the Prophetic Mandate:
Integrating the Prophetic Office within
Anglican Priesthood in Ibadan South
Diocese, Nigeria**

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Abstract

The prophetic mandate is an important but frequently disregarded feature of Christian service, particularly among Anglican priests. This study looks at how the prophetic office is integrated within the Anglican clergy in Nigeria's Ibadan South Diocese. The study investigates the theological roots of prophecy in both the Old and New Testaments and assesses its function in modern church leadership. The study also looks into how Anglican priests in the Ibadan South Diocese embrace and carry out prophetic functions as social justice advocacy, spiritual discernment, and pastoral assistance. The study evaluates the problems and prospects for reclaiming the prophetic mandate within Anglican ministry using qualitative research methodologies such as interviews and case studies. The findings indicate a contradiction between established church structures and the dynamic nature of prophetic service, emphasizing the importance of theological education, spiritual renewal, and institutional support. The study recommends that a balanced integration of the prophetic office within the Anglican clergy will strengthen the church's mission, increase spiritual participation, and promote societal development in Nigeria.

Keywords: Prophetic Mandate, Anglican Priesthood, Prophecy, Ibadan South Diocese, Church Leadership, Social Justice

Introduction

Prophecy has long played an important part in Christian ministry, shaping church identity and mission (Adeyemi, 2021). In recent years, there has been a revived interest in regaining the prophetic mission inside existing ecclesiastical organizations, attracting the attention of both scholars and church officials. This study focuses on the integration of the prophetic office within the Anglican priesthood in Nigeria's Ibadan South Diocese—a context enriched by Nigeria's vibrant ecclesiastical history and contemporary challenges that makes it fertile ground for re-examining prophetic ministry (Johnson, 2022; Smith, 2021).

Despite the scriptural imperative for prophecy, which is shown in Isaiah 6:8 and Acts 2:17, the Anglican framework has increasingly marginalized prophetic roles. This marginalization has resulted in a schism between historical theological foundations and contemporary ministry requirements, notably in addressing concerns like social injustice and spiritual malaise (Smith, 2021; Okoro, 2020). The study challenge focuses on understanding the underlying theological and institutional impediments that have contributed to this marginalization, as well as investigating consequences on church leadership and community participation (Johnson, 2022).

This study has three goals in order to address this issue. Its primary goal is to pinpoint and examine the doctrinal and structural barriers that prevent the Anglican clergy from effectively expressing prophetic ministry (Okoro, 2020). Secondly, it looks at how church leadership can be improved and current societal issues can be addressed by reintegrating prophetic roles including pastoral counseling, spiritual discernment, and social justice activism (Williams, 2022). Thirdly, in order to promote ecclesiastical renewal and community transformation, the study aims to create useful suggestions for recovering and institutionalizing the prophetic mandate within the Ibadan South Diocese (Christian, 2020).

This research is important because it has the potential to close the gap between contemporary church practice and past prophetic traditions. In addition to providing practical insights for church leaders looking to address contemporary social injustices and spiritual needs, the project hopes to further theological studies by revitalizing the prophetic mission (Babatunde, 2020). In the end, this study advances a more dynamic and

transformative model of ministry that successfully addresses the issues of the twenty-first century while also reaffirming the applicability of biblical prophetic principles (as repeated in Isaiah 6:8 and Acts 2:17) (Johnson 2022).

Literature Review

By combining current academic discussions with historical viewpoints and real-world case studies, this chapter examines the developing conversation on prophetic ministry, especially in the Nigerian Anglican setting. It looks at how prophetic frameworks can be incorporated into contemporary ministry, the difficulties presented by institutional and educational frameworks, and the transformational potential of theological education in developing prophetic leadership.

Contemporary Perspectives on Prophetic Ministry

Since its incorporation has the ability to revitalize church leadership and address urgent socio-political challenges, scholars have long contested the function of prophecy within established church hierarchies, particularly in Anglican traditions (Adeyemi, 2021). According to recent studies, a more active and socially conscious church can result from regaining the prophetic mission (Smith, 2021). The prophetic voice is often marginalized within official church systems in Nigeria, despite its obvious biblical mandate, as demonstrated in passages such as Acts 2:17 and Joel 2:28–29 (Johnson, 2022). According to Williams (2022), inflexible administrative structures that inhibit creative ways to ministry are mostly to blame for this marginalization. A shift toward prophetic ministry may also spark spiritual rejuvenation and increased social interaction, according to qualitative research from West African contexts (Christian, 2020).

Historical Foundations of Prophetic Ministry in Anglicanism

Biblical traditions are the foundation of Anglicanism's prophetic vocation, which has also been greatly influenced by historical events, especially in Africa. The Anglican notion of prophetic ministry has a strong foundation because to the well-documented role of prophets in ancient Israel as agents of divine intervention, social reform, and ethical correction (Awojobi, 2020). Prophets are seen as divinely chosen people who oppose the current quo and stand up for the underprivileged in the Anglican tradition. This biblical legacy has been continued in Africa, where 19th-century Anglican

missionaries established the foundation for social development through healthcare, education, and other reform programs in addition to sharing the gospel (Adetunmbi et al., 2024). This legacy was further enhanced by indigenous prophetic movements, as seen by the ministry of individuals such as Garrick Braide, whose work was greatly impacted by regional religious customs and cultural expressions (Campbell-Durufflé, 2023). These historical observations highlight the prophetic mandate's ongoing significance as a driving force behind societal transformation and ecclesiastical revitalization (Johnson, 2022).

Integration of Prophetic Frameworks in Contemporary Ministry

Prophetic framework integration in modern ministry requires a multidimensional strategy that takes into account cultural, pedagogical, and theological factors. Prophetic ministry has changed theologically, moving from private church settings to public political discourse. Prophetic ministry is not merely a spiritual pursuit but also a catalyst for public involvement, as seen by the significant roles that prophetic insights have played in the political narratives of nations like Venezuela and even in referendum discussions (Ciangherotti, 2023). According to doctrine, the practical expression of faith is strengthened when prophetic teachings are combined with moral imperatives. This ensures that the prophetic message continues to serve as a guide for moral judgment and social justice (Ciangherotti, 2023).

Pedagogically, contemporary teaching approaches are influenced by historical models, such as the Prophet Muhammad's (PBUH) teachings, which blend practical learning with conventional religious instruction. By fostering inclusive learning environments that honor a range of cultural and theological backgrounds, this synthesis gives aspiring prophetic leaders the skills they need for modern ministry (Fatima and Tasgheer, 2022). Political and cultural issues like syncretism must be addressed during the integration process. One example of the challenges of preserving a distinct biblical basis when African Traditional Religion and Christian prophecy are blended together is the rise of new Prophetic Churches in South Africa. This situation emphasizes how important it is to have a distinct prophetic identity that is based on biblical truth (Matshobane, 2023).

Case Studies on Prophetic Renewal in the Nigerian Anglican Context

Prophetic renewal in the Nigerian Anglican context has been the subject of numerous case studies, which have shown both potential and difficulties. One of the most important solutions to Nigeria's larger leadership problems is thought to be prophetic leadership. Though many church leaders have strayed from these objectives and engaged in behaviors that jeopardize their prophetic function, ideal models based on Prophet Ibrahim's ethical norms have been offered to guide public and ecclesiastical leadership (Fahm 2023; Uroko 2023). In addition, prophecies delivered during politically sensitive times, such as elections, have occasionally resulted in societal upheaval when the outcomes contradict public expectations, highlighting the difficult balance between prophetic insight and political reality (Agara, 2022). The church's prophetic voice is likewise threatened by widespread societal depravities, necessitating a return to ethical foundations and spiritual discernment in order to restore confidence and authority (Oluwatoba et al. 2024).

The changing religious landscape has also had an impact on the (Anglican Communion)'s growth dynamics. Notably, the church has lost members to Pentecostal denominations, sparking questions about its expansion techniques and the veracity of its prophetic claims (McKinnon, 2021). These case studies show that, while there is much potential for prophetic renewal, the process is riddled with difficulties that necessitate thoughtful, context-sensitive measures.

The Role of Theological Education in Prophetic Ministry

Contemporary study emphasizes the importance of revamping theological education to develop prophetic capacities in future clergy. Scholars advocate for curriculum that combine rigorous theological study with experiential learning in prophetic activities, claiming that such a synthesis is required for holistic ministerial development (Babatunde, 2020; Williams, 2022). These educational reforms are critical for preparing clergy to handle the complexity of modern ministry and successfully incorporate the prophetic mission into pastoral practice (Okoro, 2020; Christian, 2020). Future ministers can be prepared to discern and implement prophetic insights in a variety of cultural and societal circumstances by combining traditional theological training with practical, hands-on experiences.

This integrated educational method not only ensures doctrinal soundness, but it also encourages the formation of a prophetic identity that is sensitive to modern concerns. It encourages future leaders to consider both the historical and experiential aspects of prophetic ministry, allowing them to lead with integrity, empathy, and a commitment to social justice. Such reforms are likely to have a revolutionary impact on the church, reinforcing its role as a prophetic voice in an ever-changing world.

The subject matter discussed in this article demonstrates that reclaiming and integrating the prophetic mandate in the Nigerian Anglican setting is a multifaceted enterprise that is firmly based in historical precedent and current exigency. The debates demonstrate that, while prophetic ministry has the potential to transform church renewal and social participation, its effective integration faces major hurdles, including institutional inertia, educational limitations, and ethical failures in leadership. The interaction of these numerous factors emphasizes the necessity for comprehensive reforms that respect cultural legacy while addressing modern socio-religious issues.

Finally, the integration of historical insights, modern theoretical frameworks, and practical case studies given here lays a solid platform for comprehending the problems and opportunities associated with regaining the prophetic mandate. By restructuring theological education and resolving institutional deficiencies, the church may develop prophetic leadership capable of negotiating the challenges of modern ministry, reaffirming its role as a crucial force for ethical leadership and societal development (Okoro, 2020)

Methodology

This study uses a qualitative research design to investigate the incorporation of the prophetic office within the Anglican priesthood in the Ibadan South Diocese. Primary data were gathered through semi-structured interviews with Anglican priests and church officials. Participants were chosen on purpose, with an emphasis on those who were directly involved in or understood prophetic ministry. The data gathering process also included a review of church publications, sermons, and theological training curricula. In addition, case studies were done to document the lived experiences of clergy involved in prophetic activities. The interviews were audiotaped, transcribed, and coded using thematic analysis. The use of this approach meant that repeating patterns and

themes were recognized and thoroughly investigated. To improve study validity, triangulation was used, which involved cross-checking interview data with document analysis and observational notes. Ethical considerations were closely adhered to, including informed permission and participant anonymization. The qualitative design was used to portray the dynamic interplay of tradition and innovation in prophetic ministry. Furthermore, the methodological approach is consistent with current tendencies in theology research, which prioritize narrative and experiential data. As Proverbs 18:13 warns against answering before hearing, this study stresses community voices. In summary, the study methodology provides a solid foundation for investigating how prophetic ministry may be restored within the Anglican tradition in Nigeria.

Findings

According to the interviews and case studies, many Anglican priests in the Ibadan South Diocese appreciate the prophetic mandate's value but have difficulty in fully integrating it. Participants remarked that Anglicanism's historical legacies frequently prioritized administrative rigor over prophetic functions. Many respondents believe that a renewed focus on prophecy could help to address current social justice challenges. The case studies revealed those churches actively engaging in prophetic practices had higher levels of community involvement. One priest argued that prophetic ministry requires a dynamic connection between the church and society concerns, matching the biblical requirement in Acts 2:17. Several interviewees underlined the importance of enhanced theological education that incorporates prophetic insights with established Anglican orthodoxy. The findings indicate that clergy have a lingering desire to reclaim a more holistic approach to service. Furthermore, the study found that institutional support is essential for developing prophetic skills inside the church. Respondents noted that present church organizations, while effective in administrative activities, frequently lack tools to encourage spiritual discernment. The study's findings show that when prophetic ministry is effectively integrated, it revitalizes church outreach programs and community efforts. Furthermore, the accounts collected demonstrate that prophetic ministry can function as a counterpoint to the rigidity of official church structures. In certain situations, priests said that traditional hierarchies first stifled their prophetic voices, which were later acknowledged as critical for community reform. The qualitative research suggests that a reformed understanding of

prophecy can lead to better pastoral care and social advocacy. Overall, the findings confirm that the church must reclaim its prophetic mandate, both spiritually and practically.

Discussion

The incorporation of prophetic ministry into Anglican priesthood puts into question long-held ecclesiastical traditions and necessitates a theological paradigm shift. The study's findings show that, while the prophetic mandate is biblically supported, its practical application within established church structures remains challenging. Many scholars believe that traditional ecclesiastical structures hinder the dynamic nature of prophetic service (Williams, 2022). For example, historical precedents in Anglicanism have frequently ignored the prophetic voice in favor of liturgical conformity (Okoro, 2020). However, present socioeconomic concerns need a more responsive and revolutionary model of church leadership (Christian, 2020). In Ibadan South Diocese, the prophetic call is viewed as a vehicle for social justice, mirroring biblical aspirations for emancipation and transformation. According to the interviews, many clergy see the prophetic mandate as an important instrument for dealing with challenges like poverty, injustice, and corruption. The debate thus centered around the conflict between upholding established ecclesiastical order and accepting new forms of ministry. According to numerous interviewees, a prophetic reorientation does not mean a rejection of tradition but rather an expansion of it. This viewpoint is reinforced by contemporary theology literature, which advocates for an inclusive approach to church leadership. The incorporation of prophecy is proposed as a means of reviving the church's involvement in modern social challenges (Okoro, 2020).

The dynamic interaction between prophetic ministry and institutional structure suggests that a hybrid model could be the most successful approach. In this concept, traditional liturgy and administrative discipline are supplemented by spontaneous and socially engaged parts of prophetic practice (Babatunde, 2020). The biblical narrative, particularly Joel 2:28-29, lends support to the concept of a spirit-filled ministry that goes beyond traditional boundaries. The discussion also suggests that reclaiming prophetic ministry may lead to a broader revision of Anglican identity in Nigeria (Johnson, 2022). It is believed that incorporating prophetic insights into formal ministry can help congregations address both spiritual and temporal demands. This unification requires fundamental reforms in

theology education and church governance (Williams, 2022). In conclusion, the discussion demonstrates that, while problems exist, the potential benefits of a reformed prophetic mandate are significant and far-reaching. This section argues the necessity for a church leadership paradigm that values both tradition and innovation.

Theological Implications

Reclaiming the prophetic responsibility has profound theological ramifications for Nigeria's Anglican Church. It challenges long-held notions about the distinction between ordained ministry and charismatic expression. The prophetic office is not limited to a specific ecclesiastical model, but rather a manifestation of the Spirit's work in the society (Smith, 2021). Scriptural antecedents, such as Isaiah 6:8 and Acts 2:17, confirm prophecy's lasting and transforming role in Christian ministry. Contemporary theologians contend that the prophetic voice is necessary for a comprehensive understanding of salvation and divine justice. The incorporation of prophecy forces the modern church to reexamine its role in society, especially in circumstances marked by socioeconomic inequity (Okoro, 2020). When the prophetic mandate is regained, it serves as a correction to institutional complacency and promotes dynamic service. This viewpoint is supported by contemporary scholarly debates that advocate for the rebirth of charismatic elements within traditional systems (Babatunde, 2020). As a result, theological consequences go beyond liturgical modifications and involve a reimagining of church identity and mission. The revival of prophetic activity is viewed as a catalyst for spiritual regeneration and cultural transformation. It also underscores the church's obligation to promote justice and kindness in accordance with biblical teachings.

Given these conclusions, the study indicates the prophetic mission is an essential component of Anglican ministry in Nigeria. Theological discourse thus converges on the premise that including prophetic ministry can lead to a more inclusive and socially relevant church. While challenging, this integration has the potential to strengthen the church's spiritual and communal life. Finally, the prophetic mandate provides a method for integrating tradition and modernity in a rapidly changing world.

Institutional Challenges and Opportunities

The return of the prophetic mandate within the Anglican priesthood presents both institutional problems and great prospects (Johnson, 2022).

One of the most significant problems is the existing administrative system, which has traditionally promoted liturgical consistency over charismatic expression (Smith 2021). Institutional inertia frequently impedes the adoption of creative ministry practices that are critical for addressing modern concerns (Williams, 2022). Interviews with church leaders revealed that bureaucratic resistance is a significant barrier to prophetic integration (Okoro 2020). However, there is a potential to improve church governance by incorporating prophetic insights into decision-making processes (Christian 2020). Such reforms could potentially decentralize authority and allow local ministries to better respond to community demands (Babatunde 2020). Several participants suggested that embracing prophetic ministry could lead to more collaboration across various church sectors (Johnson 2022). Furthermore, including prophecy is viewed as a strategy of cultivating a more engaged and dynamic ecclesiastical culture (Smith 2021). Institutional reforms are not unprecedented, as evidenced by recent moves in other Nigerian dioceses that have effectively blended charismatic aspects (Williams 2022). These attempts indicate that structural transformation is both feasible and advantageous (Okoro 2020). Prophetic integration provides opportunity for a renewed approach to pastoral care and community engagement (Christian 2020). Furthermore, the prophetic mission has the capacity to solve social justice concerns by offering a theological foundation for activism (Babatunde 2020). As stated in Acts 2:17, the outpouring of the Spirit is intended to prepare the church for transforming action (Bible 2020). This dual dynamic of challenge and opportunity highlights the intricate process of institutional renovation in the face of shifting theological perspectives (Johnson 2022). Finally, the study shows that with the right reforms, the prophetic mandate can be effectively integrated into the existing Anglican ministry structure (Smith 2021).

Educational and Pastoral Reforms

The Anglican Church must undergo considerable educational and pastoral reforms in order to integrate prophetic ministry (Williams 2022). Contemporary theology education must incorporate courses and practical training in prophetic discernment and activity (Okoro 2020). Many seminaries and theological schools in Nigeria are incorporating modules on charismatic ministry into their curricula (Christian 2020). This curriculum change is required to equip future clergy for a traditional and revolutionary

ministry (Babatunde 2020). Furthermore, continuing professional development programs are required to educate present clergy with the abilities necessary to perform prophetic functions successfully (Johnson 2022). Pastoral training should highlight the convergence of spiritual discernment and administrative skills (Smith 2021). Such reforms are supported by scriptural imperatives, such as Ephesians 4:11, which emphasize the church's diversity of ministerial gifts. Furthermore, educational reforms can promote a more comprehensive knowledge of ministry, bridging the divide between institutional rigidity and charismatic fluidity (Williams 2022). Recent studies show that pastoral outcomes improve in organizations that incorporate prophetic aspects (Okoro 2020), emphasizing the need for such reforms. Furthermore, improved educational programs can act as a catalyst for overall ecclesiastical renovation (Christian 2020). By incorporating prophetic training into seminary education and ongoing education for ordained clergy, the church can better confront the problems of modern ministry. Pastoral reforms that highlight the prophetic component promote a more active and responsive congregational life. Finally, educational and pastoral reforms are required to recapture the prophetic mandate and ensure its practical application in today's society.

Implications for Social Justice

The prophetic mandate is intrinsically tied to concerns about social justice and community transformation. Prophetic ministry necessitates active participation with societal inequities, as exemplified by biblical injunctions such as Amos 5:24. In Ibadan South Diocese, clergy that accept prophetic positions are frequently in the vanguard of advocating for the downtrodden. This advocacy is based on a theological notion of social justice as a divine commandment rather than an elective activity. According to recent research, churches that include prophetic ministry are better positioned to confront systemic inequities. Furthermore, the prophetic voice frequently challenges the current quo, encouraging both the church and society to seek radical change. The above approach aligns with the biblical prophetic model, which emphasizes justice, kindness, and humility. This study's interview results show that many clergy see prophetic ministry as a moral necessity that directly challenges social injustice. The restoration of the prophetic mission has far-reaching consequences for community empowerment and social reform. It can be used to mobilize congregations for lobbying,

charitable giving, and revolutionary social action. Furthermore, a prophetic orientation within the church might assist close the gap between spiritual concerns and sociopolitical realities. The juxtaposition of spiritual and social participation represents a biblically based, holistic understanding of ministry. Finally, incorporating prophecy into church leadership provides a compelling framework for advancing social justice and community rejuvenation.

Case Study: A Parish Transformation

A comprehensive case study undertaken in one parish of the Ibadan South Diocese, specifically at St Luke's Anglican Church in Molete, Ibadan, reveals the transforming power of incorporating prophetic ministry into local church practice. In this endeavor, a pilot program was initiated to provide clergy and lay leaders with skills in prophetic discernment and advocacy, using qualitative methodologies to focus on the development of spiritual and practical competences. Participants reported that the program renewed their sense of mission and redirected their ministry focus to greater social engagement. Throughout the program, prophetic messages were interwoven into normal worship services, resulting in a significant increase in congregational involvement. Furthermore, the parish implemented community outreach activities inspired directly by prophetic insights, such as weekly forums on social issues, mirroring the long-standing practice of communal prophetic involvement. The utilization of biblical scriptures, particularly those from Acts 2:17, strengthened the spiritual foundation of these activities. Over the course of a year, St Luke's Anglican Church in Molete saw measurable increases in both community involvement and social advocacy, demonstrating that reclaiming the prophetic mandate can result in profound spiritual renewal and tangible societal impact. Finally, the success of this case study offers as a paradigm for other dioceses looking to revitalize their ministries through prophetic involvement.

Conclusion

This study critically analyzed the complex but hopeful process of integrating the prophetic mandate into the Anglican clergy in the Ibadan South Diocese. It has emphasized the historical marginalization of prophecy within current institutional systems and identified a pressing need for reform. The study reveals that regaining the prophetic mission is both a theological imperative and a practical requirement for resolving modern societal concerns.

Using qualitative research methods, the study gathered nuanced opinions from clergy and church leaders on the problems and opportunities connected with prophetic integration. The frequent use of biblical references from Isaiah, Joel, and Acts reinforces the timeless vocation to prophetic ministry. According to the findings, effective integration of prophetic ministry can result in improved pastoral care, better community engagement, and stronger social advocacy.

Despite the enormous institutional hurdles encountered, the study provides specific proposals for educational and pastoral reforms that could help to successfully integrate prophetic practices. Finally, reclaiming the prophetic mandate provides a unique chance to revive the Anglican Church's mission in Nigeria, making it more responsive to both spiritual and societal imperatives. As the church grows, it must endeavor to combine tradition and innovation, ensuring that prophetic insights continue to influence and improve its mission for the greater good

Synthesis and Recommendations

A synthesis of the findings suggests that regaining the prophetic mandate has significant revolutionary potential for the Anglican priests in the Ibadan South Diocese. According to the complete analysis, incorporating prophetic duties can dramatically reinvigorate church leadership and generate more community participation. Based on these findings, numerous suggestions emerge:

1. **Reforms in Theological Education:** The diocese must implement systematic reforms in theological education. This should involve the implementation of specific modules on prophetic discernment to provide future clergy with the skills required for effective ministry.
2. **Restructure Pastoral Training Programs to Prepare Clergy for Traditional and Prophetic Roles.**
3. **Decentralizing decision-making** through institutional reforms is crucial for prophetic ministry. Such structural flexibility would allow local ministries to respond more effectively to community needs.
4. **Consider creating dedicated venues for prophetic voices.** These platforms would develop and amplify prophetic thoughts, creating a more dynamic ecclesiastical environment.
5. **Balanced Integration of Tradition and Innovation:** The integration process complements existing Anglican practices rather than

replacing them. Embracing both historical traditions and creative ideas will better position the church to handle today's varied concerns. Biblical imperatives, such as those contained in Isaiah 6:8 and Acts 2:17, continue to lend strong support to these reforms. The ideas presented here serve as a strategic road map for diocesan leaders seeking to recapture the prophetic mandate and strengthen the church's mission, highlighting the importance of continual communication between academic knowledge and ecclesiastical practice. Finally, the effective integration of prophetic ministry could become a precedent for dioceses in Nigeria and elsewhere.

References

- Adetunmbi, Kemi, et al. "Historical Perspectives on Anglican Missionary Work in Nigeria." *Nigerian Historical Review*, vol. 18, no. 1, 2024, pp. 30–50.
- Adeoye, Samuel, et al. "Curriculum Reforms in Nigerian Education: Implications for Ministry." *Nigerian Journal of Curriculum Studies*, vol. 10, no. 2, 2023, pp. 77–95.
- Adeyemi, Opeyemi. "Prophetic Traditions in Nigerian Anglicanism." *Journal of African Theology*, vol. 15, no. 2, 2021, pp. 123–45.
- Agara, Ezekiel. "The Impact of Prophecy on Political Dynamics in Nigeria." *Journal of Political Theology*, vol. 6, no. 1, 2022, pp. 90–110.
- Aryeh, Michael. "Evolving Trends in African Prophetic Movements." *African Christianity Review*, vol. 10, no. 1, 2022, pp. 77–93.
- Babatunde, Afolabi. "Integrating Prophetic Ministry in Contemporary Church Leadership." *Nigerian Journal of Religious Studies*, vol. 8, no. 1, 2020, pp. 55–77.
- Campbell-Durufflé, Jane. "Indigenous Prophetic Movements in African Christianity." *Journal of African Religious Studies*, vol. 11, no. 3, 2023, pp. 101–120.
- Chigbo, Emeka, and Nkechi Udezo. "Human Rights and the Prophetic Mandate in the Church." *Journal of Human Rights and Religion*, vol. 2, no. 1, 2020, pp. 38–56.
- Christian, David. "Qualitative Approaches to Church Leadership Studies in Nigeria." *Journal of Qualitative Theology*, vol. 12, no. 3, 2020, pp. 210–230.
- Ciangherotti, Martina. "Prophetic Engagement in Global Political Discourse: Lessons for Nigeria." *Journal of Contemporary Religious Studies*, vol. 7, no. 1, 2023, pp. 33–49.
- Ejenobo, Femi. "Empowering Prophetic Leaders for the Future." *Nigerian Journal of Ministry Studies*, vol. 4, no. 1, 2009, pp. 45–60.
- Fahm, Saad. "Prophetic Leadership in Contemporary Nigeria: Lessons from Prophet Ibrahim." *Journal of Leadership and Ethics*, vol. 3, no. 1, 2023, pp. 44–62.

- Fatima, Noor, and Ahmed Tasgheer. "Islamic Pedagogical Principles in Modern Educational Practices." *Journal of Islamic Education*, vol. 8, no. 1, 2022, pp. 27–42.
- Johnson, Thomas. "The Role of Prophecy in Modern Anglican Practice." *International Journal of Theology*, vol. 10, no. 1, 2022, pp. 98–117.
- Lowery, David. "Prophetic Ecclesiology: Lessons from Archbishop David Gitari." *Journal of African Ecclesiology*, vol. 7, no. 1, 2024, pp. 88–104.
- Matshobane, Thabo. "Syncretism and Identity in New Prophetic Churches in South Africa." *South African Journal of Religious Studies*, vol. 14, no. 2, 2023, pp. 66–81.
- McKinnon, James. "Religious Affiliation Trends in Nigeria: A Comparative Study." *Journal of Nigerian Religious Studies*, vol. 9, no. 3, 2021, pp. 115–133.
- Mohammed, Ali. "Integrating Al-Majiri Education with Modern Curricula." *Nigerian Educational Review*, vol. 12, no. 1, 2024, pp. 35–52.
- Nwokoro, Obi, and James Muasa. "Spiritual Discernment and Prophetic Leadership in Nigeria." *African Journal of Theological Research*, vol. 6, no. 2, 2024, pp. 49–65.
- Okoro, Michael. "Spiritual Renewal and Ecclesiastical Structures in West Africa." *Journal of Church Management*, vol. 14, no. 4, 2020, pp. 150–169.
- Oluwatoba, Samuel, et al. "Spiritual Discernment in Nigerian Prophetic Ministry." *Journal of African Theology and Ministry*, vol. 4, no. 2, 2024, pp. 58–74.
- Opade, Samuel. "The Role of Prophecy in Social Justice Movements." *Journal of Social Theology*, vol. 4, no. 1, 2023, pp. 55–72.
- Smith, Lauren. "Social Justice and the Prophetic Mandate in Contemporary Christianity." *Journal of Faith and Social Action*, vol. 7, no. 2, 2021, pp. 34–56. *The Holy Bible: NIV Study Bible*. Zondervan, 2020.
- Ugwu, Kenneth. "Prophetic Figures in Biblical Narrative and Modern Ministry." *Journal of Biblical Studies*, vol. 5, no. 1, 2009, pp. 22–38.
- Uroko, Chinedu. "Corruption and the Decline of Prophetic Leadership in Nigeria." *Nigerian Journal of Ethics*, vol. 2, no. 2, 2023, pp. 70–85.
- Williams, Richard. "Reclaiming the Prophetic Voice: Challenges and Opportunities." *Theological Review*, vol. 9, no. 1, 2022, pp. 45–68.
- Yahya, Ibrahim, et al. "Challenges and Reforms in the Tsangaya Education System." *Journal of Islamic Education*, vol. 5, no. 2, 2024, pp. 78–94.
- Zink, Peter. "Adaptive Prophetic Ministry in a Changing World." *Global Journal of Prophetic Studies*, vol. 5, no. 2, 2012, pp. 39–55.

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**From Shepherds to Strategists: The
Intersection of Pastoral Ministry and
Human Resource Management**

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Abstract

The study focused on Human Resource Management (HRM) and Pastoral Ministry which share core responsibilities in people management, leadership development, and organisational sustainability. While HRM focuses on workforce optimization, performance management, and talent development, pastoral leadership encompasses guiding, mentoring, and nurturing communities toward growth and purpose. This paper explored the intersection between pastoral ministry and HRM, drawing on Biblical case studies to illustrate key HRM principles such as workforce delegation, employee engagement, conflict resolution, and leadership succession planning. Using a qualitative research methodology, this study employed hermeneutical analysis of Biblical texts alongside comparative leadership studies to extract HRM insights from the leadership of Moses - delegation and leadership development (Exodus 18); Nehemiah - organisational culture and motivation (Nehemiah 2-6), and Paul - talent management and succession planning (II Timothy 2:2). The findings revealed that pastoral ministry served as an early model of HRM, demonstrating strategies for effective leadership, ethical workforce management, and structured talent development. This study concluded that HRM professionals can draw

valuable lessons from Biblical pastoral leadership, particularly in mentorship, organisational culture, and employee well-being.

Keywords: Pastoral Leadership, Human Resource Management, Workforce Delegation, Talent Development, Biblical Case Studies

Introduction

Human Resource Management (HRM) is a fundamental aspect of organisational success, focusing on recruitment, training, leadership development, employee engagement, and workforce management (Armstrong & Taylor, 2020). Traditionally, HRM has been studied within corporate, industrial, and public administration sectors, yet its principles are also deeply embedded within faith-based leadership and pastoral ministry. The role of a pastor extends beyond spiritual guidance to include personnel management, conflict resolution, organisational culture development, and leadership succession planning, aligning closely with contemporary HRM practices (Banks & Ledbetter, 2004).

The Bible provides numerous case studies that illustrate structured leadership principles, talent development strategies, and ethical workforce management, all of which are core elements of HRM today. Leaders like Moses, Nehemiah, and Paul demonstrated effective workforce delegation, organisational vision-setting, and leadership mentoring, paralleling modern HRM concepts (Wright, 2018). Moses, for instance, faced leadership burnout from overburdening himself with administrative and judicial responsibilities until Jethro, his father-in-law, advised him to delegate tasks to capable individuals, a foundational principle of modern HRM (Exodus 18:17-26). Similarly, Nehemiah mobilised and motivated people towards a common organisational goal (rebuilding Jerusalem's walls), implementing structured workforce assignments and strategic resource allocation — a model seen in business leadership today (Nehemiah 2-6). Paul, on the other hand, established a leadership succession framework by training and mentoring younger leaders such as Timothy and Titus, aligning with HRM's emphasis on talent retention and workforce sustainability (2 Timothy 2:2).

The intersection between pastoral ministry and HRM suggests that the Biblical model of shepherd leadership serves as a precursor to modern HRM strategies (Northouse, 2019). Churches and faith-based organizations today operate HRM systems, ensuring structured hiring processes,

employee engagement models, leadership development initiatives, and welfare management (Parratt, 2022). Mega Churches such as - The Redeemed Christian Church of God (RCCG), Hillsong Church, and the Catholic Church employ formal HRM structures to manage their vast workforce of clergy, administrative personnel, and volunteers (Adegbite, 2021).

Despite these overlaps, pastoral ministry is rarely analysed through an HRM lens, leaving a gap in scholarly exploration. This study has tried to bridge this gap by examining Biblical leadership models through HRM frameworks, addressing the following research questions: How does pastoral ministry reflect HRM principles? What Biblical case studies illustrate key HRM functions? How can Biblical HRM principles be applied in corporate settings?

Using a qualitative research methodology, this paper employed hermeneutical analysis of Biblical texts alongside comparative leadership studies to extract HRM insights from pastoral ministry. The findings suggest that pastoral leadership is an early model of workforce management, with lessons applicable to contemporary HRM, especially in ethical leadership, employee engagement, conflict resolution, and succession planning (Van Dierendonck, 2011).

This paper argued that HR professionals can draw valuable lessons from Biblical pastoral leadership, particularly in mentorship, organisational culture, and employee well-being. The study also explored how faith-based organizations implement structured HRM systems and how corporate HRM can adopt Biblical leadership principles to enhance employee engagement and workforce productivity.

By integrating Biblical wisdom with modern HRM theory, this study offered a unique interdisciplinary perspective, positioning pastoral leadership as a viable framework for strategic human resource management in both religious and corporate settings.

Theoretical Framework: Shepherd Leadership Theory

To effectively analyse the connection between pastoral ministry and human resource management (HRM), this paper adopted the Shepherd Leadership Theory, which comprehensively aligns with both Biblical leadership models and modern HRM principles. Shepherd leadership, derived from biblical metaphors of leadership as shepherding, provides a

framework for understanding how leaders guide, develop, and care for their followers (Wright, 2018; Laniak, 2006).

Shepherd leadership is characterized by guidance & direction (leading people toward a shared vision), protection & care (ensuring the well-being of the workforce), nurturing & development (identifying and fostering individual strengths) and strategic delegation (distributing responsibilities for efficiency). The shepherd metaphor is one of the most consistent leadership images in the bible, portraying leaders as caretakers who prioritize the welfare of those under their authority (Laniak, 2006).

In a corporate context, HR professionals assume a similar responsibility by ensuring that employees are properly guided through policies and strategic leadership, well-supported in professional development and workplace well-being and productive and engaged in achieving organisational goals. Like shepherds who tend to their flock, ensuring survival and growth, HR managers develop and sustain the workforce, balancing structure with care (Northouse, 2019).

Biblical Case Studies and HRM Principles

The Bible presents numerous examples of structured leadership, talent management, and workforce organisation, many of which align with modern human resource management (HRM) principles. Three biblical case studies that highlight key HRM concepts are examined:

1. *Moses (Exodus 18)*: Workforce Delegation and Leadership Development
2. *Nehemiah (Nehemiah 2–6)*: Organisational Culture and Workforce Motivation
3. *Paul (2 Timothy 2:2)*: Talent Management and Succession Planning

Each of these figures exemplifies shepherd leadership by prioritising people development, structured delegation, and organisational efficiency, making their models highly relevant to contemporary HRM practices (Northouse, 2021).

Moses: Workforce Delegation and Leadership Development (Exodus 18:17–26)

Moses, as the leader of Israel, initially attempted to manage all governance, legal disputes, and organisational decisions alone. However, Jethro, his father-in-law, observed that this centralised leadership model was unsustainable, leading to inefficiency and burnout. Jethro advised Moses to delegate responsibilities by appointing leaders over thousands, hundreds,

fifties, and tens, ensuring structured management and sustainable leadership (Exodus 18:17–26, New International Version).

The HRM principles reflected in this case are workforce delegation, leadership development, and employee well-being. In modern HRM, effective delegation is considered a fundamental leadership competency (Armstrong & Taylor, 2020). Organisations implement hierarchical management structures to distribute authority, ensuring productivity and reducing executive overload (Yukl, 2013). Multinational corporations, such as Google and General Electric, prioritise leadership coaching and delegation strategies, mirroring Moses' model of structured governance (Goleman et al., 2013).

Effective HR leaders must develop structured delegation systems to optimise workflow, prevent burnout, and create scalable leadership frameworks within organisations. This approach fosters sustainability and ensures that leadership responsibilities are not concentrated at the top, enhancing overall productivity (Ulrich et al., 2017).

Nehemiah: Organisational Culture and Workforce Motivation (Nehemiah 2–6)

Nehemiah faced the daunting task of rebuilding Jerusalem's walls while managing a demotivated workforce and addressing external opposition. His success was driven by three key strategies:

1. ***Casting a Clear Organisational Vision:*** He inspired workers with a shared goal, fostering commitment and alignment.
2. ***Task Specialisation:*** He assigned individuals to specific roles based on their skills and expertise.
3. ***Employee Motivation:*** He encouraged workers despite resistance from external adversaries.

Despite opposition from Sanballat and Tobiah, Nehemiah maintained high morale among his workforce by dividing labour efficiently and ensuring organisational cohesion (Nehemiah 2:17–20; Nehemiah 4:6–23). The HRM principles evident in this case study include visionary leadership, organisational culture, workforce motivation, engagement, task specialisation, and role clarity.

HRM research highlights that organisational culture significantly influences employee motivation and performance (Collins & Porras, 2001). Companies such as Google, Microsoft, and Apple cultivate strong workplace cultures by ensuring that employees understand and align with the

corporate vision (Schein, 2017). Empirical studies indicate that motivated workforces consistently outperform disengaged employees, which is why modern HRM frameworks prioritise team-building strategies, performance incentives, and leadership development programmes (Ulrich, 2016).

HR professionals must foster a positive organisational culture, clearly communicate corporate vision, and ensure employees are aligned with company goals. This enhances engagement, reduces turnover, and drives organisational success (Kotter & Heskett, 2011).

Paul: Talent Management and Succession Planning (2 Timothy 2:2)

Paul's leadership model emphasised structured mentorship and succession planning. He instructed Timothy: "The things you have heard me say in the presence of many witnesses, entrust to reliable people who will also be qualified to teach others" (2 Timothy 2:2, NIV). Paul mentored Timothy, who was, in turn, expected to train others, ensuring a leadership pipeline that sustained Christian ministry across generations. This principle aligns with modern HRM strategies that prioritise leadership development and workforce continuity.

The HRM principles reflected in Paul's approach include:

1. **Mentorship and Talent Development:** High-performing organisations invest in structured mentorship programmes to develop emerging leaders (Goleman et al., 2013).
2. **Succession Planning:** Effective leadership requires continuity beyond the current generation, ensuring seamless organisational transitions (Rothwell, 2020).
3. **Sustainability through Workforce Training:** Developing people ensures long-term organisational success, reinforcing stability and growth (Ulrich et al., 2017).

Corporate HRM recognises talent retention and workforce sustainability as crucial for organisational longevity (Armstrong & Taylor, 2020). Companies such as Deloitte, McKinsey, and Microsoft implement structured leadership training programmes, ensuring seamless leadership transitions. Research indicates that succession planning minimises disruption, enhances organisational continuity, and preserves institutional knowledge (Collins & Porras, 2001). Similarly, Paul's leadership strategy ensured the long-term sustainability of the Christian mission.

These biblical examples demonstrate that pastoral ministry embodies structured workforce management, reinforcing that HRM principles are

deeply embedded in biblical leadership. The application of these principles remains highly relevant in contemporary HRM, providing a foundation for effective organisational leadership and sustainability (Northouse, 2021).

Modern HRM Comparisons: HRM in Churches and Faith-Based Organisations

Modern Human Resource Management (HRM) practices have extended beyond corporate settings into various non-profit and faith-based organizations, where structured systems are implemented to manage talent, engage employees, and foster a positive organisational culture. Many large churches and faith-based organizations have adopted formal HRM systems that parallel those used in modern corporations. This section examines three core areas where these organizations have integrated HRM principles - recruitment and talent management, employee engagement and organisational culture, and conflict resolution coupled with workforce well-being.

Recruitment and Talent Management

Large Churches have developed comprehensive strategies to attract, develop, and retain leadership talent. For example, Hillsong Church implements global leadership training programs designed not only to recruit but also to continuously develop pastoral and administrative talent. These programs emphasize practical skills, ethical leadership, and cross-cultural competence — principles that align closely with contemporary HRM practices in talent management (Adegbite, 2021). Similarly, the Redeemed Christian Church of God (RCCG) employs innovative recruitment techniques, such as their Dove TV recruitment processes, combined with structured workforce development initiatives. These approaches demonstrate a commitment to building robust leadership pipelines and ensuring that the organization's talent is nurtured systematically.

Employee Engagement and Organizational Culture

Employee engagement and the cultivation of a healthy organisational culture are fundamental to both corporate HRM and church administration. Willow Creek Community Church, for instance, has implemented employee engagement models that parallel those found in successful corporations. Through initiatives that promote open

communication, continuous feedback, and participatory decision-making, the church creates an environment where staff feel valued and connected to the mission. Additionally, the Catholic Church's administrative practices — with their clearly defined hierarchical structures and formal succession planning — serve as a model of how strong organisational culture and structured leadership can drive employee satisfaction and operational effectiveness. These examples underline that HRM practices such as clear communication of vision and collaborative work environments are as vital in faith-based settings as they are in corporate contexts (Banks & Ledbetter, 2004).

Conflict Resolution and Workforce Well-being

Effective conflict resolution and a focus on workforce well-being are essential for maintaining a productive environment. Many churches have established dedicated HR departments to handle internal staff issues and disputes — paralleling the conflict resolution mechanisms found in corporate HR. Moreover, faith-based organizations often implement comprehensive welfare systems that include counselling, mentorship programs, and structured work ethics designed to support staff both professionally and personally. These initiatives not only help resolve conflicts swiftly but also contribute to a sustainable work environment that enhances overall job satisfaction and performance. Such practices highlight that when HRM is integrated thoughtfully, it promotes a culture of ethical behaviour and mutual respect (Parratt, 2022).

The examples discussed demonstrate that modern HRM practices are not exclusive to the corporate world. Large Churches and faith-based organizations, such as Hillsong, RCCG, Willow Creek, and the Catholic Church, have successfully embedded HRM principles into their operational frameworks. Their approaches to recruitment, talent development, employee engagement, and conflict resolution provide valuable insights that can be applied in corporate settings. This convergence reinforces the idea that the foundational principles of HRM — structured delegation, ethical leadership, and employee well-being — are universally applicable and can serve as a bridge between pastoral ministry and modern organisational management.

Applying Biblical HRM Principles to Corporate Settings

In today's dynamic corporate landscape, integrating Biblical HRM principles provides a timeless framework for enhancing leadership, employee engagement, and overall organisational effectiveness. By drawing from rich Biblical narratives, corporate HR professionals can adopt strategies that emphasize ethical conduct, purposeful delegation, and sustainable talent development. However, this section illustrated how the models of Paul, Nehemiah, Moses, and Jethro can be adapted to modern HR practices.

Talent Development

The mentorship model exemplified by Paul's training of Timothy (2 Timothy 2:2) is a cornerstone for effective talent development. In the corporate environment, structured mentorship programs are vital for nurturing emerging leaders. Companies should design formal development plans that incorporate

1. **Structured Training:** Regular coaching sessions, workshops, and seminars to build both technical and interpersonal skills.
2. **Continuous Performance Feedback:** Systems for ongoing evaluations that guide professional growth.
3. **Succession Planning:** Clear pathways for career progression, ensuring that critical leadership roles are filled by well-prepared professionals.

For instance, General Electric's leadership development programs, which emphasize mentorship and structured training, demonstrate how Biblical principles of mentorship can translate into a resilient leadership pipeline (Ulrich, 2016).

Employee Engagement and Motivation

Nehemiah's leadership during the rebuilding of Jerusalem's walls (Nehemiah 2-6) offers a powerful model for fostering an inspiring organisational culture. His ability to rally people around a shared vision can be mirrored in corporate settings through:

1. **Vision Communication:** Regularly articulating the company's mission and long-term objectives to ensure alignment.
2. **Engagement Initiatives:** Establishing recognition programs, team-building activities, and participatory decision-making that make employees feel valued.

3. ***Inclusive Work Environment:*** Encouraging diverse perspectives and ensuring every team member sees their role as integral to organisational success.

Corporations like Google have implemented similar engagement strategies to cultivate motivated and innovative teams, underscoring the importance of a shared vision in driving productivity (Collins, 2001).

Ethical Leadership and Integrity

Moses' model of righteous leadership, demonstrated in his commitment to fairness and ethical decision-making (Exodus 18), underscores the critical importance of integrity in leadership. In corporate HR, ethical leadership is essential for building trust and ensuring compliance. Business leaders can apply these principles by:

1. ***Establishing Core Values:*** Developing a set of guiding principles that prioritise transparency, fairness, and accountability.
2. ***Ethics Training:*** Regularly educating employees on ethical practices and decision-making processes.
3. ***Transparent Communication:*** Ensuring open lines of dialogue so that policies are applied consistently and justly.

Organisations such as Patagonia have built their reputations on strong ethical frameworks, reinforcing that values-based leadership, akin to Moses' example, is crucial for sustainable business practices (Northouse, 2019).

Delegation and Productivity

Jethro's advice to Moses to delegate responsibilities (Exodus 18:17-26) is a timeless principle that prevents managerial burnout and fosters efficiency. In modern HRM, effective delegation is achieved by:

1. ***Clear Role Definition:*** Assigning tasks based on individual strengths and ensuring that responsibilities are well understood.
2. ***Empowerment:*** Encouraging a culture where managers trust their teams fostering a sense of ownership.
3. ***Monitoring and Feedback:*** Implementing performance tracking systems that ensure delegated tasks are completed effectively.

Amazon's operational success, largely attributed to its robust delegation practices and efficient team structures, reflects the same principles found in Jethro's counsel (Armstrong & Taylor, 2020). Integrating Biblical HRM principles into corporate settings allows organizations to build a work environment grounded in ethical leadership, continuous talent

development, and effective delegation. By adopting models of mentorship, engagement, integrity, and structured delegation, modern HR professionals can create more resilient, motivated, and productive workforces. These time-tested strategies not only enhance organisational performance but also foster an ethical culture that benefits all stakeholders. As such, the principles of pastoral leadership serve as a powerful foundation for contemporary human resource management practices.

Conclusion

This study has shown that pastoral ministry offered a robust framework for understanding and applying key HRM principles. The Biblical case studies of Moses, Nehemiah, and Paul revealed that concepts such as talent development, employee engagement, ethical leadership, and effective delegation are not only central to pastoral leadership but also directly applicable to modern human resource management.

Pastoral ministry serves as an early HRM framework, offering time-tested models for leadership, talent management, and organisational culture. Modern HR professionals can draw critical insights from Biblical leadership, particularly in the areas of structured mentorship, fostering a positive organisational culture, ethical decision-making, and delegation. These principles, when adapted thoughtfully, can enhance corporate HR practices by creating a more resilient, engaged, and ethically driven workforce.

Recommendations

To strengthen HRM practices in both corporate and faith-based organisations, it is essential to adopt structured strategies that enhance leadership development, employee engagement, and organisational sustainability. The following recommendations draw insights from biblical leadership models and contemporary HRM principles, ensuring long-term effectiveness and strategic growth:

1. **Establishing formal mentorship frameworks** to ensure a continuous pipeline of competent leaders, drawing parallels with Paul's mentorship of Timothy.
2. **Cultivating a robust organisational culture** that inspires employee engagement and aligns individual aspirations with corporate objectives, mirroring Nehemiah's visionary leadership.

3. **Implementing ethical leadership practices** by adopting a model of integrity similar to that exemplified by Moses, thereby promoting transparency and fostering trust and compliance.
4. **Optimising delegation processes** through the effective distribution of responsibilities, as advised by Jethro to Moses, to enhance productivity and empower mid-level management.
5. **Establishing structured performance evaluation systems** that facilitate continuous improvement and accountability, ensuring that employee development is systematically monitored and guided.
6. **Developing a comprehensive talent retention strategy** that promotes career advancement, rewards excellence, and fosters long-term commitment to organisational goals.

By implementing these recommendations, organisations can create a sustainable HRM framework that not only strengthens leadership and workforce engagement but also aligns with ethical and strategic growth objectives.

References

- Adegbite, A. (2021). *Strategic leadership in faith-based organisations: A case study of contemporary church administration*. Routledge.
- Armstrong, M., & Taylor, S. (2020). *Armstrong's handbook of human resource management practice* (15th ed.). Kogan Page.
- Banks, R., & Ledbetter, M. (2004). *Reviewing leadership: A Christian evaluation of leadership theory*. Baker Academic.
- Collins, J. (2001). *Good to great: Why some companies make the leap and others don't*. Harper Business.
- Collins, J., & Porras, J. I. (2001). *Built to last: Successful habits of visionary companies*. Harper Business.
- Goleman, D., Boyatzis, R., & McKee, A. (2013). *Primal leadership: Unleashing the power of emotional intelligence*. Harvard Business Review Press.
- Laniak, M. (2006). *Shepherd leadership: A Biblical perspective on modern leadership*. *Journal of Leadership Studies*, 10(3), 45–55.
- Northouse, P. G. (2021). *Leadership: Theory and practice* (9th ed.). Sage Publications.
- Parratt, S. (2022). *Conflict management in faith-based organisations: Ethical perspectives and leadership strategies*. Palgrave Macmillan.
- Parratt, M. (2022). *Modern HRM in faith-based organizations: Strategies for effective talent management*. *Human Resource Development Review*, 21(3), 287–303.

- Rothwell, W. J. (2020). *Effective succession planning: Ensuring leadership continuity and building talent from within* (6th ed.). AMACOM.
- The Holy Bible, King James Version. (n.d.). (Exodus 18:17–26; Nehemiah 2–6; 2 Timothy 2:2).
- Ulrich, D. (2016). *Human resource champions: The next agenda for adding value and delivering results*. Harvard Business Review Press.
- Ulrich, D., Kryscynski, D., Ulrich, M., & Brockbank, W. (2017). *Victory through organization: Why the war for talent is failing your company and what you can do about it*. McGraw-Hill.
- Wright, P. (2018). *Shepherd leadership: Biblical insights into modern leadership*. *Leadership Quarterly*, 29(4), 545–560

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**Assessment of Socio-economic and Political
Effects of 2020 and 2024 Recessions in
Nigeria and their Implications for
Sustainable Development**

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Abstract

The paper explored the socio-economic and political effects of recessions in Nigeria between 2020 and 2024 and their implications for sustainable development. The purpose of the study was to firstly, identify the socio-economic effects of economic recessions in Nigeria with focus on poverty, unemployment, and inequality, secondly, to appraise the political implications of economic recessions in Nigeria, particularly in terms of governance, public trust, and social unrest, lastly, to ascertain the effectiveness of Nigeria's policy responses to economic recessions and their alignment with sustainable development goals. Moreover, the research was to examine the impacts of recession on various facets of Nigerian society and proposed recommendations to promote

resilience and inclusive growth. The scope of the study encompassed an analysis of key economic indicators, social welfare, and political dynamics during the recession periods between 2020 and 2024 as a result of COVID-19 pandemic leading to lockdown in Nigeria in all facets. The significance of the study focused on its contribution to understanding the complex interplay between economic downturns and sustainable development in emerging economies, particularly in the context of Nigeria's heavy reliance on the oil sector. The study drew on economic and political theories to analyse the relationships between recession, public policy responses, and societal outcomes. Methodologically, the paper employed a combination of secondary data analysis and a review of relevant literature to evaluate the impacts of recession between 2020 and 2024 and assessed policy responses. The findings underscored the importance of diversifying the economy, strengthening social safety nets, improving governance, promoting human capital development, and implementing counter-cyclical fiscal policies to mitigate the adverse effects of recession in Nigeria. The paper concluded with recommendations for future research and implementations, including conducting primary data collection, exploring the role of external factors, and investigating the long-term consequences of recession. Ultimately, the paper aimed to inform evidence-based policymaking and contributed to the pursuit of sustainable and inclusive development in Nigeria, especially in the face of economic volatility.

Keywords: Recession, Nigeria, Sustainable Development, Economic Resilience, Public Policy

Introduction

Economic recessions profoundly affect nation's social, economic, and political landscape, often challenging their sustainability goals. In Nigeria, recurrent economic downturns, particularly the significant recessions of the COVID-19-induced recession of 2020 and 2024 have highlighted structural vulnerabilities. These downturns, driven by factors such as oil price volatility, currency devaluation, and governance inefficiencies, have exacerbated poverty, unemployment, and inequality. According to the World Bank (2023), Nigeria's economic growth has been constrained by dependence on oil revenues and weak fiscal policies, which have intensified the country's exposure to external shocks and domestic inefficiencies. The socio-economic impacts of these recessions are extensive. Rising inflation, a depreciated naira, and reduced household purchasing power have pushed millions of Nigerians into extreme poverty. Politically, these challenges have strained government legitimacy, intensified public dissatisfaction, and prompted demands for reform. For instance, the removal of fuel subsidies in

2023, while a step toward fiscal sustainability, sparked protests due to its immediate hardship on citizens (World Bank, 2023; Central Bank of Nigeria, 2023). The pursuit of sustainable development amid these challenges requires strategic policy interventions. Reforms such as diversifying the economy beyond oil dependence, investing in human capital, and improving governance are essential. These efforts align with Nigeria's commitment to the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), which emphasise reducing inequalities, fostering economic growth, and ensuring political stability.

The Nigerian government's response to economic recessions has been multifaceted, involving fiscal adjustments, monetary policy reforms, and social interventions. However, the outcomes of these efforts have been mixed. While reforms such as subsidy removal and the adoption of a market-determined foreign exchange regime have sought to stabilise the economy, their implementation has led to immediate hardships, including a sharp rise in inflation, which reached 27.3% in October 2023 (World Bank, 2023; International Monetary Fund, 2023). These challenges underscore the need for comprehensive strategies that balance short-term economic adjustments with long-term sustainability goals. The political ramifications of these recessions are equally significant. Recessions often amplify social discontent and weaken trust in governance, as seen in widespread protests against austerity measures. These political tensions have implications for democratic consolidation, as they test the capacity of institutions to mediate conflicts and sustain public confidence (Africa Development Bank, 2023).

Economic recessions in Nigeria have exposed systemic vulnerabilities that hinder sustainable development. For instance, the 2020 recession caused by the COVID-19 pandemic underscored Nigeria's dependency on crude oil, which contributes over 80% of export earnings and 50% of government revenues. The global drop in oil prices during the pandemic reduced government revenue, stalled infrastructure development, and exacerbated public debt challenges (IMF, 2023). As a result, fiscal policies, such as borrowing and subsidy adjustments, became essential tools to navigate the crisis, albeit with significant implications for poverty levels and income inequality. The socio-economic effects of these recessions extend beyond economic indicators. Rising inflation and unemployment rates have deepened the vulnerability of Nigeria's lower-income groups, with over 133 million Nigerians living in multi-dimensional poverty by 2023 (NBS, 2023). These trends have had far-reaching consequences on education, healthcare,

and overall quality of life, hindering progress toward achieving the desired sustainable development goals agenda (SDGs). Addressing these challenges requires targeted interventions that prioritise job creation, affordable healthcare, and equitable access to education.

On the political front, recessions have often tested the resilience of Nigeria's democratic institutions. Policies such as subsidy removals and fiscal austerity measures have triggered public outcry, as seen in the protest following the 2023 fuel subsidy removal. These events highlight the critical need for transparent communication and inclusive governance to maintain public trust during economic transitions (World Bank, 2023). These crises reveal the fragility of social contracts in Nigeria, emphasising the importance of strengthening institutional frameworks to mitigate the political fallout of economic downturns (International Monetary Fund, 2023). Furthermore, the interplay between economic instability and political unrest raises critical questions about Nigeria's resilience and its ability to achieve sustainable development amid persistent challenges. Given Nigeria's strategic importance in Africa, understanding its socio-economic and political responses to recession is crucial for broader regional stability. Against these backdrops, this paper examines the underlying causes and effects of economic recessions in Nigeria, highlighting their impacts on key development indicators. By analysing the nexus between economic policies, social resilience, and political stability, the paper has provided actionable insights into fostering a more inclusive and sustainable pathway for development.

Statement of the Problem

Economic recessions pose significant challenges to the socio-economic and political stability of nations, particularly in developing countries like Nigeria. Despite being Africa's largest economy, Nigeria has faced two major recessions within the last decade, in 2016 and 2020, both of which exposed the fragility of its oil-dependent economy and inadequate diversification efforts. These economic downturns have exacerbated existing problems such as poverty, unemployment, inflation, and income inequality. According to the National Bureau of Statistics (NBS, 2023), over 60% of Nigerians live below the poverty line, a situation worsened by the economic crises. The socio-economic consequences of these recessions are evident in deteriorating living standards, reduced access to essential services, and growing inequality. Furthermore, these economic difficulties have led had significant

political repercussions, leading to widespread public dissatisfaction, social unrest, and declining trust in government institutions.

For instance, policy decisions such as the removal of fuel subsidies in 2023, though aimed at fiscal sustainability, have sparked nationwide protests due to their immediate adverse effects on the populace (World Bank, 2023). Efforts to address these challenges have often been reactive rather than proactive, focusing on short-term stabilization rather than long-term sustainability. The lack of comprehensive policies to tackle structural issues such as economic diversification, governance inefficiencies, and infrastructure deficits continues to hinder Nigeria's progress toward achieving sustainable development goals. However, the paper intended to investigate the multifaceted impacts of economic recessions on Nigeria's socio-economic and political environment and examined the adequacy of existing policy responses. Understanding these dynamics is critical to formulating effective strategies that promote economic resilience, equitable development, and political stability in the face of future economic challenges.

The paper focused on examining the socio-economic and political effects of economic recessions in Nigeria, particularly during the recessions of the COVID-19-induced recession of 2020 and 2024, and how these events impacted sustainable development efforts. The paper covered key socio-economic issues, including poverty, unemployment, inflation, and income inequality, to understand how economic downturns exacerbate these challenges. It also explored the political dimensions of economic recessions, focusing on governance practices, public trust, and instances of social unrest triggered by austerity measures and other policy responses. Geographically, the study was limited to Nigeria, with a focus on national-level impacts and policies while acknowledging regional disparities in the socio-economic consequences of recessions. Temporarily, the paper examined the period from 2015 to 2024 to capture the dynamics of recent economic recessions and the policy interventions implemented during this time. By delineating the boundary of focus, the paper intended to provide a focused analysis of Nigeria's response to economic recessions and offered actionable insights for enhancing resilience and achieving sustainable development.

The paper's significance relied in its potential to provide valuable insights into the socio-economic and political consequences of economic recessions in Nigeria. By focusing on the periods of recessions between 2015 and 2024, the paper, however, contributed to a deeper understanding of how economic

downturns affect the living standards of Nigerian citizens, exacerbate inequality, and disrupt key sectors such as healthcare, education, and employment. According to the World Bank (2023), understanding these impacts is critical for developing more resilient policies aimed at mitigating the adverse effects of future recessions. Politically, the paper sheds light on how economic instability challenges the legitimacy of governance and erodes public trust in government institutions. As evidenced in recent years, public dissatisfaction due to rising poverty and austerity measures has led to widespread protests and social unrest, undermining the stability of democratic processes (UNDP, 2023).

The paper, therefore, offered a timely examination of the intersection between economic policy, governance, and political stability, which is essential for fostering democratic consolidation and maintaining social peace in Nigeria. Furthermore, the study is significant in terms of its contribution to the broader discourse on sustainable development. By examining Nigeria's policy responses to recession, the paper offered insights into how well the country's development strategies align with the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), particularly in the areas of reducing inequality, promoting decent work, and ensuring inclusive economic growth (UNDP, 2023). The findings from the study can guide policymakers in crafting more effective and inclusive economic strategies, ensuring that Nigeria moves toward a more sustainable and equitable future. In essence, the paper is significant not only for its academic contribution but also for its practical implications in shaping future economic and political reforms in Nigeria. By evaluating the past responses to economic crises, the paper will in no small measure offer critical lessons for building a resilient economy that can withstand external shocks while prioritising social well-being and political stability.

Economic recessions are complex phenomena that affect both the socio-economic structure and the political landscape of a nation. In the context of Nigeria, the socio-political consequences of recessions have garnered significant attention from scholars, policymakers, and analysts due to their far-reaching impacts on the nation's development. Recessions often lead to increased poverty, unemployment, inflation, and political instability. This literature review explores existing studies and theoretical perspectives on the socio-economic and political effects of economic recessions in Nigeria, with particular focus on the recessionary periods of 2015 and 2024, and their implications for sustainable development.

The first major socio-economic impact of a recession is the increase in poverty. During periods of economic contraction, economic output declines, businesses close, and jobs are lost. This reduction in national wealth has an immediate and profound impact on the poor. According to Olawale & Oladipo (2020), the 2015 recession pushed millions of Nigerians into deeper poverty, with estimates suggesting that the number of Nigerians living in extreme poverty rose significantly during this period. They argued that the contraction in the economy negatively affected employment, real income levels, and overall social welfare. Similarly, Oladipo & Adefolalu (2021) pointed out that the recession resulted in a sharp increase in the unemployment rate, especially among youth and graduates. The recession exacerbated pre-existing challenges in the labour market, leading to a significant number of lay-offs, especially in sectors such as oil, agriculture, and manufacturing. The unemployment rate reached an alarming 27.1% in 2020, a consequence of the global economic downturn and domestic policy mis-steps that worsened during the recession (National Bureau of Statistics, 2020).

Another critical socio-economic effect is inflation. The 2016 recession was accompanied by a surge in inflation, especially food prices. According to Akinola & Owolabi (2021), the depreciation of the naira and the rising cost of imported goods contributed to skyrocketing inflation rates. This severely impacted household purchasing power and disproportionately affected the poor. Inflation during the recessionary periods caused a dramatic increase in the cost of living, leading to a reduction in real wages and an increase in the number of Nigerians living below the poverty line. Furthermore, Okoro & Olamide (2020) noted that the agricultural sector, a critical part of Nigeria's economy, suffered as a result of both the recession and other structural issues such as insecurity and climate change. The fall in agricultural productivity worsened food insecurity, further exacerbating the poverty and inflation problems.

Recessions do not only affect the economy but also have profound effects on the political environment of a country. One of the key political consequences of recessions is a decrease in public trust in government. As economic conditions worsen, citizens often begin to lose faith in their leaders' ability to manage the economy effectively. Eze (2018) argued that during the 2015 recession, there was a significant erosion of public trust in Nigeria's political leadership. Citizens became increasingly sceptical of government efforts to address the crisis, which led to political discontent and frustration. The

perception of government ineffectiveness in managing economic challenges often translates into public protests, social unrest, and a decline in political participation. Social unrest is another political consequence of recession. Economic hardship creates conditions for public dissatisfaction and mobilisation. In Nigeria, social unrest has been a recurring theme during periods of recession. Ogunleye & Ajayi (2021) observed that the 2015 recession led to an upsurge in protests and strikes, particularly in sectors such as education, labour, and healthcare.

The protests were often a response to rising unemployment, deteriorating public services, and cuts in government spending. Similarly, Ogunyemi (2020) argued that political unrest intensified during the 2020 recession, particularly in the form of the #EndSARS protests, which were partly fuelled by the worsening economic conditions and perceived government inaction. In addition to public protests, recessions can also undermine democratic stability. As Salami & Akinwumi (2021) emphasised, periods of economic hardship can weaken democratic institutions, as governments often resort to authoritarian measures to manage discontent. During the 2015 and 2020 recessions, critics of the Nigerian government argued that the administration's response to the economic crisis was characterised by authoritarian tendencies, including the use of military force and suppression of dissent. This created tensions between the government and civil society, further destabilizing the political environment.

Government responses to recession are critical in shaping the outcomes of an economic downturn. Effective fiscal and monetary policies can help mitigate the negative effects of a recession. Oladipo & Adefolalu (2021) suggested that Nigeria's response to the 2015 recession, including the introduction of the Economic Recovery and Growth Plan (ERGP), had mixed results. While some policy initiatives aimed at boosting infrastructure and agriculture had positive effects, the overall response was insufficient to address the underlying structural issues that triggered the recession. Furthermore, Ogunleye & Ajayi (2021) noted that the lack of a coherent and inclusively policy framework left many vulnerable groups without support during the crisis. Similarly, Eze (2018) pointed that the government's response to the 2020 recession was characterised by ad hoc measures such as cash transfers and social welfare programmes. However, these measures were often perceived as inadequate and failed to reach a large proportion of the population. The delay in implementing a clear response and the limited

scope of the relief programmes exacerbated the social and political instability during the recession.

The literature highlighted that the socio-economic and political effects of recessions are deeply interconnected, with economic downturns triggering both material hardship and political instability. The 2015 and 2020 recessions in Nigeria illustrated the widespread impacts of such economic crises, which include increased poverty, unemployment, inflation, public distrust, and social unrest. While some government policies were implemented to mitigate these effects, the general consensus in the literature is that the responses were insufficient and failed to adequately address the systemic issues facing Nigeria's economy. However, the literature review synthesised recent research on the socio-economic and political effects of economic recessions in Nigeria, emphasising the complex relationship between economic downturns and their impact on poverty, unemployment, inflation, public trust, social unrest, and government response. These findings underscored the need for more effective, inclusive, and long-term strategies for managing economic downturns to ensure sustainable development and political stability in Nigeria.

Theoretical Framework

The paper adopted the political economy theory to explain the reality and suitability of the study. The political economy theory, however, offers a comprehensive lens through which the intersection of economic processes and political power structures can be analysed, particularly in contexts like economic recessions. This theory provides insights into how political institutions, government policies, and economic structures interact to shape national development (Ake, 2000). It highlights the role of the state in managing economic crises and the ways in which political decisions can influence economic outcomes. In the context of Nigeria's recession and its effects on socio-political stability, the political economy theory emphasises the importance of government intervention in economic matters, particularly in times of economic distress. It posits that economic systems do not function in isolation but are deeply embedded within political frameworks (Akinola; & Owolabi, 2021). These frameworks determine the distribution of power and resources, and in turn, the outcomes of economic policies. The theory, therefore, suggests that during periods of recession, government responses are critical not only for economic recovery but also for ensuring political stability (Eze, 2018).

This theory is particularly relevant when considering how recessions in Nigeria have exacerbated existing political and economic inequalities (Ojo, 2017). The theory suggests that the policy decisions made by the Nigerian government during the 2015 and 2020 recessions, including austerity measures, devaluation of the naira, and cuts to public services, directly affected the well-being of citizens, particularly the most vulnerable groups. The way in which these policies were implemented can be understood through the lens of political economy: they reflect the priorities of the political elites and the way in which political institutions are structured to serve their interests (Olawale; & Oladipo, 2020). The political economy theory also highlights how economic crises, such as recessions, can exacerbate social unrest and undermine public trust in government (Fosu, 2007; Sachs; & Warner, 1995; Appelbaum; & Robinson, 2005). The theory suggests that when economic hardships are poorly managed by political institutions, social tensions can rise, leading to protests, strikes, and challenges to political authority. In Nigeria, for example, the #End SARS protests in 2020, which were triggered by police brutality, also reflected broader frustrations with the government's handling of economic issues (Ogunleye; & Ajayi, 2021). The government's inability to effectively address the economic hardships brought on by the recession led to political instability, which can be understood through the political economy framework (Oladipo; & Adefolalu, 2021).

Moreover, the theory underscores the role of international factors in shaping domestic economic outcomes. In Nigeria's case, the country's heavy reliance on oil exports, and the global oil price slump during the severity of the recession. This external economic factor interacted with Nigeria's internal political dynamics, creating a situation where both economic and political systems were under immense pressure (Akinwunmi; & Salami, 2021). However, this theory provides a critical framework for understanding the interconnectedness of political decisions and economic realities. In the context of Nigeria's recession, it offers insights into how governmental policies and political structures influence economic outcomes, the distribution of resources, and the stability of the political system. Understanding these dynamics is key to addressing the socio-political challenges Nigeria faces in times of economic crisis and ensuring that future responses to recession are both effective and equitable.

Research Objectives

The research objectives are:

1. To identify the socio-economic effects of economic recessions in Nigeria.
2. To appraise the political implications of economic recessions in Nigeria.
3. To ascertain the effectiveness of Nigeria's policy responses to economic recessions and their alignment with sustainable development goals.

Research Questions

The following areas were prepared to guide the research questions:

1. What are the socio-economic effects of economic recessions in Nigeria?
2. How have economic recessions influenced political dynamics in Nigeria governance practices?
3. How effective have Nigeria's policy responses been in addressing the challenges posed by economic recessions, and to what extent do these policies align with sustainable development objectives?

Methodology

The paper employed a quantitative research approach to investigate the socio-economic and political effects of economic recessions in Nigeria, focusing on the periods of the COVID-19-induced 2020-2024 recessions. The quantitative method was chosen to allow for an objective and systematic analysis of the relationship between economic recessions and various socio-economic and political variables, such as poverty, unemployment, inflation, governance challenges, and social unrest. This approach enabled the researcher to analyse large-scale data efficiently and draw generalisable conclusions from a sample of the population. The study used a sample population of 200 individuals drawn from various demographic and socio-economic backgrounds in Nigeria. The sample has been selected using stratified random sampling to ensure that the sample reflected the diversity of Nigeria's population, including four different regions, income levels, and educational backgrounds. This method has provided a broad representation of Nigerians who have experienced the effects of economic recessions, allowing for a comprehensive understanding of the impact across different segments of society.

Data has been collected through structured questionnaires designed to gather information on the socio-economic and political effects of the recessions. The questionnaire has included both closed and Likert-scale questions to capture respondents' attitudes, perceptions, and experiences

related to issue such as unemployment, poverty, inflation, government policy responses, and political stability. The questions have been developed based on the research objectives and a review of relevant literature to ensure they address the key issues of the study. The data collected has been analysed using statistical tools such as SPSS (statistical package for the social sciences). Descriptive statistics, including frequency distributions and percentages, have been used to summarise the demographic characteristics of the respondents and their responses to various questions. Inferential statistics, such as chi-square tests and regression analysis, have been used to determine the relationships between different variables, including the impact of the recession on socio-economic outcomes and the political environment in Nigeria.

Regression analysis has helped in assessing how significantly the variables such as poverty, unemployment, and inflation are impacted by the economic recessions. This analysis has also enabled the researcher to determine the extent to which government responses, such as fiscal policies and social interventions, have influenced public perception and political stability. Ethical considerations have been prioritised throughout the study. Informed consent has been obtained from all participants, ensuring that they were aware of the study's purpose, the confidentiality of their responses, and their right to withdraw at any point. The study has also adhered to the ethical guidelines for conducting social research, including maintaining the anonymity and privacy of the participants. This quantitative approach has provided empirical evidence on the socio-economic and political effects of recessions in Nigeria, offering valuable insights for policymakers and scholars. By analysing a representative sample of 200 respondents, the study has provided reliable data on how recessions impacted various aspects of Nigerian society and evaluated the effectiveness of government interventions in promoting sustainable development.

Data Analysis

This section represented tables for data analysis, reflecting various aspects of the study's objectives. These tables have helped organised and presented the data obtained from the 200 sample respondents across four regions in Nigeria.

Table 1: Demographic Characteristics of Respondents

Demographic Variables	Frequency (f)	Percentages (%)
Gender		
Male	120	60%
Female	80	40%
Age Group		
18-25	50	25%
26-35	70	35%
36-45	40	20%
46-and above	40	20%
Region		
North	60	30%
South	80	40%
West	60	30%
Education Level		
Primary School	10	5%
Secondary School	50	25%
Tertiary Education	140	70%

Note: Table 1 provides the demographic profile of the study sample, which has been used to understand the composition of respondents based on gender, age, religion, and education. This is crucial for analysing the diversity of experiences related to the economic recessions.

Research Question 1: What are the socio-economic effects of economic recessions in Nigeria?

Table 2: Socio-economic Effect of Recession on Respondents

Effect Variable	Frequency (f)	Percentage (%)
Poverty		
Increased significantly	150	75%
Stayed the same	30	15%
Decreased significantly	20	10%
Unemployment		
Increased significantly	140	70%

Stayed the same	40	20%
Decreased significantly	20	10%

Note: Table presented the socio-economic effects of the recessions, including poverty, unemployment, and inflation. The table helps to quantify how much these factors worsened as a result of the economic downturns.

Research Question 2: How have economic recessions influenced political dynamics in Nigeria governance practices?

Table 3: Political Effects of Economic Recession (2020-2024)

Political Variable	Frequency (f)	Percentage (%)
Public Trust in Government		
Decreased significantly	170	85%
Stayed the same	20	10%
Increased significantly	10	5%
Social Unrest		
Occurred during recession	140	70%
Did not occur	60	30%
Government Response		
Effective in mitigating effects	90	45%
Ineffective in mitigating effects	110	55%

Note: Table 3 focuses on the political consequences of the recessions, including public trust in government and the occurrence of social unrest. This table provided insights into how Nigerians perceived governance during the economic crises.

Research Question 3: How effective have Nigeria's policy responses been in addressing the challenges posed by economic recessions, and to what extent do these policies align with sustainable development objectives?

Table 4: Relationship between Recession and Governance (Chi-square Analysis)

Variable	Observed Frequency (O)	Expected Frequency (E)	Chi-square Value (χ^2)	Degree of Freedom (df)	p-value
Public Trust in Government					
Social Unrest	40	20	5.1	2	0.027
Government Response Effectiveness	90	100	2.7	1	0.101

Note: A chi-square analysis was used to determine whether there is a significant association between economic variables (e.g., public trust, social unrest, etc.) and the recessions. It tested whether the observed frequencies deviated significantly from what would be expected in the absence of a recession.

Research Question 1: What are the socio-economic effects of economic recessions in Nigeria?

Table 5: Regression Analysis of Socio-economic Factors and Public Trust in Government

Independent Variable	Coefficient (Beta)	Standard Error	t-value	p-value
Poverty Rate	0.512	0.129	3.97	0.000
Unemployment Rate	0.347	0.105	3.31	0.001
Inflation Rate	0.398	0.097	4.10	0.000

Note: Table 5 explored regression analysis that examined the relationship between socio-economic factors (i.e. poverty, unemployment, inflation, etc.) and public trust in government. The table quantified the strength and

significance of the effect of each factor on political stability and governance. However, both the research questions 1 and 2 were answered here. However, the above stated tables have allowed for a detailed and comprehensive quantitative analysis, which has actually helped to answer the three formulated research questions that addressed this study and meeting the objectives of the study all together.

Discussion of Findings

The data analysis involved calculating the frequency counts for each of the variables in the survey. The frequencies represented how many respondents selected a particular response. The demographic characteristics include the gender distribution. This category analyses how many male and female respondents participated in the survey. From the data, we had: 120 males (60% of the total sample population), 80 females (40% of the total sample population). The age group distribution of the data provided an idea of the age demographics of the respondents. 50 respondents were in the 18-25 age group (25%), 70 respondents were in the 26-35 age group (35%), 40 respondents were in the 36-45 age group (20%), 40 respondents were in the 46- and above age group (20%). The region distribution shows where the respondents are located within Nigeria. In line with the figure, 60 respondents were from the North (30%), 80 respondents were from the South (40%), 60 respondents were from the West (30%). The education level distribution background of respondents has provided insights into their perceptions as follows: 10 respondents had only primary school education (5%), 50 respondents had secondary school education (25%), 140 respondents had tertiary education (70%).

The socio-economic impact of the recession shows how the recession affected the respondents in terms of poverty, unemployment, and inflation level. In the area of poverty, 150 respondents (75%) reported an increase in poverty during the recession, while 140 respondents (70%) indicated that unemployment increased as a result of the recession, and 160 respondents (80%) noted that inflation worsened due to the recession. These figures highlighted the seventy of the economic recession on the living conditions of the people. The political effects of the recession looked at the political consequences of the economic downturn. In tandem with this, it has been reported by 170 respondents (85%) that public trust in the government decreased during the recession. However, 140 respondents (70%) reported social unrest as a result of economic hardships. In another way, 90

respondents (45%) felt that the government's response to the recession was not effective. These responses reflected dissatisfaction with government actions during the recessions and indicated how the public's trust in the political system was impacted.

Moreover, in terms of socio-economic impacts, the data strongly indicated that the recession had a severe effect on poverty, unemployment, and inflation, with inflation being the most widely acknowledged consequence. In the interpretation of the results of findings, considering the socio-economic consequences, the high percentage of respondents acknowledging the increase in poverty, unemployment, and inflation confirmed that the economic recession hit the Nigerian population hard. The overall decline in purchasing power and job losses were widespread and deeply felt by many individuals. More so, in line with the political consequences, the decrease in public trust and the occurrence of social unrest demonstrated that the economic hardship led to political dissatisfaction. The relatively low number of respondents believing that the government's response was effective suggested that the government's strategies during these periods were not seen as adequate or helpful. Lastly, from the data analysis, it is clear that the between the periods of the COVID-19-induced pandemic 2020 and 2024 had profound effects on both the socio-economic and political spheres in Nigeria. While the government's actions during these periods may have been well-intentioned, the public perception of these actions pointed to a need for better economic policies, stronger government responses, and increased trust-building initiatives.

Conclusion

In conclusion, the examination of the socio-economic and political effects of recession in Nigeria has revealed significant challenges to the nation's pursuit of sustainable development. The declining economic growth, rising unemployment, and inflation experienced during recessions have severely impacted the livelihoods and well-being of the Nigerian people, exacerbating poverty and inequality. Politically, recessions have the potential to destabilise the government's support base, as citizens' dissatisfaction with their socio-economic circumstances may lead to protests and civil unrest. Furthermore, the government's policy responses to recession, such as austerity measures and structural reforms, often have short-term negative impacts on vulnerable populations, which can fuel political polarisation and undermine social cohesion. In the context of sustainable development,

addressing the root causes of recession and its adverse effects on society is essential to ensure long-term progress in Nigeria. This necessitates a commitment to diversifying the economy, improving governance, and investing in human capital to build resilience against future economic shocks. Additionally promoting inclusive growth and social safety nets can help mitigate the disproportionate impact of recession on the most vulnerable members of society.

While the paper provided valuable insights into the socio-economic and political effects of recession in Nigeria and their implications for sustainable development, it is not without limitations. One potential limitation is the reliance on secondary data sources, which may be subject to measurement errors, inconsistencies, or biases. Additionally, the paper primarily focused on the national level, which may not fully capture the nuanced impacts of recession on sub-national regions or specific sectors of the economy. Another limitation is the omission of in-depth analysis on the role of external factors, such as global economic trends or international policy interventions, in shaping Nigeria's recession experiences. Furthermore, the paper does not account for the potential long-term consequences of recession, such as its impact on generational wealth and social mobility. However, there are several areas for further investigation that could enhance our understanding of the effects of recession in Nigeria and inform policy responses. First, conducting primary research, such as surveys and interviews, would enable a more granular analysis of how recession affects individuals, households, and businesses across different socio-economic strata. Second, a comparative study with other emerging economies could offer insights into how country-specific factors shape the impacts of recession and inform cross-national learning. Lastly, further research could explore the effectiveness of various policy responses to recession, such as counter-cyclical fiscal policies and structural reforms, in promoting sustainable development in the Nigerian context. By addressing these suggested areas of limitations, future investigation can contribute to a more comprehensive understanding of recession's multifaceted impacts and support evidence-based policymaking to foster sustainable and inclusive growth in Nigeria.

Recommendations for Policy Implementation

Based on the findings of the study, three recommendations in line with research objectives and questions have been proposed for implementation to

address the socio-economic and political effects of recession in Nigeria and to promote sustainable development.

1. To enhance economic resilience, the government should continue to invest in sectors such as agriculture, manufacturing, and services. This will create job opportunities, spur innovation, and promote inclusive growth.
2. The government should ensure that there is need to improving fiscal management, combating corruption, and ensuring transparent communication with citizens.
3. Creating a conducive business environment, including access to finance, streamlined regulations, and targeted support for small and medium-sized enterprises, can stimulate economic growth and job creation during and after recessions.

References

- African Development Bank. (2023). Economic Outlook for Nigeria. Retrieved from AfDB.
- Ake, C. (2000). Democracy and development in Africa. Brookings Institution Press.
- Appelbaum, R.P; & Robinson, W.I. (2005). The Political economy of globalisation. Blackwell Publishing.
- Akinola, O., & Owolabi, G. (2021). The impact of inflation on economic stability: A study of Nigeria's recession years. *Journal of Economic Studies*, 56(4), 450-467.
- Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN). (2023). Macroeconomic Indicators and Policy Analysis.
- Eze, S. (2018). Political instability and public trust in government during economic recessions in Nigeria. *African Journal of Political Science*, 30(3), 215-230.
- Fosu, A. k. (2007). The Political Economy of development in Africa. Routledge.
- International Monetary Fund (IMF). (2023). Economic Outlook for Sub-Sahara Africa.
- International Monetary Fund. (2023). Policy Recommendations for sub-Saharan Economies: Case Studies from Nigeria.
- National Bureau of Statistics. (2023). Poverty and Inequality in Nigeria.
- Ogunleye, A., & Ajayi, B. (2021). Social unrest and economic decline: The 2016 recession in Nigeria. *International Journal of African Studies*, 14(2), 98-113.
- Ogunyemi, M. (2020). #End SARS and the nexus between economic hardship and political protests in Nigeria. *African Journal of Social Issues*, 5(4), 122-135.
- Ojo, O. (2017). Nigeria's economic and political landscape: A case of a struggling economy. *African Journal of Political Science*, 8(3), 104-121.

- Oladipo, F., & Adefolalu, A. (2021). Unemployment and economic instability in Nigeria: A response to the 2016 recession. *Nigerian Journal of Economic Policy*, 24(1), 34-47.
- Olawale, A., & Oladipo, O. (2020). The impact of Nigeria's 2016 recession on poverty and employment. *Journal of Development Economics*, 18(2), 150-165.
- Sachs, J.D., & Warner, A.M. (1995). Economic reform and the process of global integration. *Brookings Papers on Economic Activity*, 1-118.
- Salami, S., & Akinwumi, A. (2021). Economic recessions and democratic stability in Nigeria. *Journal of African Political Economy*, 12(3), 89-104.
- World Bank. (2023). Nigeria Development Update: Turning the Corner – From Reforms and Renewed Hope to Results. Retrieved from World Bank.

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**The Sacrificial Death of Jesus Christ and
Its Implications for the Contemporary
Church**

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Abstract

The sacrificial death of Jesus Christ stands as a central tenet of Christian faith, symbolizing the ultimate act of love and redemption. This study explores the profound implications of Christ's sacrifice for the contemporary church, examining how this foundational event continues to shape the beliefs, practices, and mission of Christian communities around the world. Through a comprehensive review of biblical texts, theological writings, and historical perspectives, this research elucidates the multifaceted significance of Christ's death on the cross. It delves into the theological concept of atonement, highlighting the ways in which Jesus' sacrifice is understood to reconcile humanity with God and offer salvation to all who believe. Furthermore, it investigates the ethical dimensions of Christ's sacrifice, emphasizing the call to selflessness, service, and sacrificial love that it embodies for believers. In light of these theological and ethical considerations, this study also examines the practical implications of Christ's sacrificial death for the contemporary church. It explores how the church can embody the values of reconciliation, forgiveness, and compassion in a

world marked by division, injustice, and violence. By reflecting on the example set by Jesus Christ, the church is challenged to engage in acts of social justice, peace making, and solidarity with the marginalized and oppressed. Ultimately, this research argues that a deep understanding of Christ's sacrificial death is essential for the vitality and relevance of the contemporary church. By embracing the transformative power of Christ's sacrifice, the church can embody the values of love, grace, and redemption in a broken world, bearing witness to the enduring significance of the cross in the life of faith.

Keywords: Jesus Christ, Sacrificial Death, Contemporary Church, Salvation, Theological Concept of Atonement

Introduction

The sacrificial death of Jesus Christ stands as a pivotal event in Christian theology, encapsulating the essence of salvation and the nature of divine love. Central to the New Testament narrative, the crucifixion is not merely a historical occurrence but a profound theological construct that has shaped Christian doctrine and practice throughout centuries. N. T. Wright said, "The death of Jesus is not merely an isolated event but the climax of God's redemptive history, transforming how the church understands its identity and mission in the world." (Wright, 2020). This act of self-sacrifice is often interpreted as the fulfilment of Old Testament prophecies and the ultimate expression of God's covenantal faithfulness to humanity. The implications of this sacrificial death extend far beyond the confines of first-century Judea; they reverberate through the teachings, worship, and ethical considerations of the contemporary Church.

In examining the sacrificial death of Jesus, one must consider its theological dimensions, particularly the concepts of atonement, redemption, and grace. Various interpretations, ranging from substitutional atonement to moral influence theories, reveal the rich tapestry of understanding surrounding this event. Each perspective not only informs individual belief systems but also influences communal worship practices and the ethical frameworks within which contemporary Christians operate. Richard B. Hays opined that, "The narrative of Jesus' death echoes the sacrificial themes found throughout Scripture, challenging the church to live out its calling in light of this profound act of love." (Hays, 2021) Furthermore, the sacrificial nature of Christ's death raises critical questions about the nature of sacrifice in the modern context, challenging the Church to reflect on its role in a world marked by violence, injustice, and suffering.

As the Church navigates the complexities of a diverse and pluralistic society, the implications of Jesus' sacrificial death demand rigorous theological inquiry and practical application. This exploration is essential for fostering a community that embodies Christ's love and compassion, advocating for justice and reconciliation in a fractured world. Hays (2021) further explained that. "Thus, a thorough examination of the sacrificial death of Jesus Christ not only enriches theological discourse but also provides a vital framework for understanding the Church's mission and identity in contemporary society." Through this lens, we can explore how the profound truths of the crucifixion can inspire transformative action and a renewed commitment to living out the Gospel in today's context.

Review of Literature

The sacrificial death of Jesus Christ is a central tenet of Christian theology, often interpreted through various doctrinal lenses. This literature review explores scholarly perspectives on the implications of Jesus' sacrifice for the contemporary church, focusing on theological, ecclesiological, and ethical dimensions. The review will draw on works from biblical scholars, theologians, and contemporary church leaders to highlight the multifaceted significance of this doctrine.

Theological Perspectives

The concept of sacrificial atonement is foundational in Christian theology, with many scholars tracing its roots back to the Hebrew Scriptures. According to Anselm of Canterbury (1998), Jesus' death is understood as a necessary satisfaction for humanity's sin, restoring the relationship between God and humankind. This penal substitution theory has been critiqued and reinterpreted in modern scholarship. For instance, Gustaf Aulen (1931) proposed the Christus Victor model, emphasizing the victory of Christ over sin, death, and the devil rather than focusing solely on penal satisfaction. This perspective resonates with contemporary movements that prioritize a holistic understanding of salvation, encouraging the church to embrace a narrative of liberation and hope.

Significance of Jesus Christ's Sacrificial Death in Christian Theology

Jesus Christ crucified is a foundational and fundamental doctrine of the Christian church. The cross is the insignia of Christian faith. Other great men have been valued for their lives, Christ's greatest blessing to men came

through his death. The cross pervades all scriptures. Richard A. Horsley (2022) affirmed that, "The sacrificial nature of Jesus' death reveals a blueprint for the church, urging it to act as a prophetic voice for justice and mercy in a fractured world." The Mosaic instructions foreshadow its meanings. The historical books prove its necessity. The Psalms picture its reality. The prophets describe its coming. The Gospels announce its presence. The Acts proclaim its power. The Epistles explain its purpose. Revelation sees the consummation of its blessings.

Horsley (2022) said, "Cut the Bible anywhere, and it bleeds; it is red with redemption truth." One out of every forty-four verses in the New Testament deals with the sacrificial death of Christ. It is mentioned in all 175 times. While the incarnation divides time, the cross divides eternity. Christ was foreordained as the lamb slain before the foundation of the world (1 Pet. 1:19–20); and as the lamb once slain, he will be the theme of endless praise (Rev. 5:13).

It was unreasonable to expect that crucifixion would be employed for the execution of the Messiah. Stoning was the common method of capital punishment among the Jews (Lev. 20:2; Deut. 13:6–10; 17:2–5), and there are illustrations of its use in the Old Testament (Lev. 24:11–14; Num. 15:32–36; 1 Kings 12:18; 21:13; 2 Chron. 24:20–21). Stoning was especially stipulated in the Mosaic law as punishment for idolatry and blasphemy. The Jews requested that our Lord give them permission to stone a sinful woman (John 8:4–5), and on another occasion they took up stones to hurl at him when he declared that he was equal with God (John 10:30–33).

Crucifixion was unknown to the Jews when the earliest prophecies of our Lord's death were recorded. The Romans, who introduced this barbarous method of capital punishment, were then hardly in existence. But by a circumstance of events that made the Romans the rulers of the world, the Jews in Christ's time, with other conquered nations, were paying tribute to Caesar. As a province of Rome, the right of such a dependent nation to execute its criminals was no longer permitted. Hence the Jews were required to secure the aid of the Roman governor before their prisoners could be put to death. By these strange and unexpected circumstances our Lord was led out to be crucified by the Romans rather than being stoned by the Jews. Darell L. Bock (2022) also opined that, "Jesus' sacrificial death serves as the ultimate lesson in love and humility, calling the church to reflect on its teaching and practices in light of his example."

Some have given their lives for their friends, but think of Christ's amazing love for his enemies. He came down from the heights of heaven to the lowly cross and bowed his sacred head in shameful, agonizing death. His was the great sacrifice for mankind. God gave his dearly beloved Son for this great sacrifice, so that "whosoever believeth in him should not perish, but have everlasting life" (John 3:16). Christ is born as man. This is the purpose of incarnation. The name that Joseph was commanded to give him indicated he was to be the Savior of his people (Matt. 1:21). He himself declared that he had come to give his life as a ransom for many (Matt. 20:28).

A Mystery to the Old Testament Prophets

One of the great proofs of the verbal inspiration of the Bible is that the writers did not always understand the message God gave them to record. It appears that the death of Christ, which was predicted centuries before he appeared, was a great mystery to the prophets (1 Pet. 1:10–12). Even the angels were not fully advised as to the plan and purpose of the world's greatest tragedy, but it was of such significance that they desired further information about it (v. 12). "Understanding the cross in our contemporary context challenges the church to confront social injustices, offering a model of self-giving love that transforms communities" (Hayeon Soo, 2021). More than a third of the Old Testament is prophecy, with Christ its central theme. Note the relationship of the Old Testament to the last book of the New Testament: In the one the Savior and King is prophesied; in the other, the Savior and King is glorified. The work of the Savior was predicted in three ways.

- a. ***By Symbol:*** The office of the high priest was instituted so there would be a representative of the people to offer up sacrifices. As the great High Priest, our Lord offered Himself as the all-sufficient sacrifice for sin.
- b. ***By Type:*** There are said to be 333 striking Old Testament pictures of Christ's sacrificial death. In the beginning of human history, only sacrifices requiring the shedding of blood met with God's approval. Cain's offering did not typify the sacrifice of life and was not acceptable (Heb. 9:22; 11:4). Let us consider two outstanding types:
- c. ***The Passover Lamb:*** The lamb required for the celebration of the Passover (Exod. 12:5–7, 13) was an appropriate type of the great Sacrifice, typifying the sinless Lamb of God whose blood would save from eternal death. In the substitution of the Lord's Supper for the Passover, Christ became the Paschal Lamb.

- d. ***The Brazen Serpent:*** The fiery serpents that invaded the camp of Israel were representative of sin and its fatal consequences. The brazen serpent erected by Moses (Num. 21:9) represented the Sin-bearer who was “made ... sin for us” (2 Cor. 5:21) in order to remove the penalty of sin. Christ indicated that it was a picture of the crucifixion—the uplifted cross (John 3:14–15).
- e. ***By Word:*** Just what experiences our Lord passed through we learn not so much from the Gospel narrators, who wrote what they saw and heard, but from the prophets who recorded the story by divine inspiration centuries before it took place. Prophecy provides another Gospel that is corroborative and supplementary to Matthew, Mark, Luke, and John. In the New Testament we see only glimpses of the terrible conflicts of our Lord on the cross; in the Old Testament we see all his anguish. In the Gospels we have what Christ said and did, and what was said and done to him; in prophecy we see his inner life—what he thought, and how he felt, and how he lived in the presence of his God and Father.

Ecclesiological Implications

The sacrificial death of Jesus has profound implications for the ecclesiology of the contemporary church. The early church understood itself as a community shaped by Christ's sacrifice, fostering an identity rooted in servanthood and self-giving love (Horsley, 1994). In contrast, modern expressions of church often grapple with institutionalism and consumerism. Researchers like Alan Hirsch (2006) argue that the church must return to a missional identity that reflects the sacrificial nature of Christ's death. This involves reimagining church practices to foster community engagement and social justice, allowing the church to serve as a living testament to Christ's love.

- i. ***The Savior Pierced (Ps. 22:16; Zech. 12:10; Luke 24:40; John 19:34):*** What a picture is given us of the mob closing in at the foot of the cross. And there shall come a time when the Jews, who have long rejected Jesus Christ as their Messiah, shall recognize him as the same one they had pierced. When they recognize the awful mistake of the centuries, “they shall mourn for him, as one mourns for his only son.... In that day shall there be a great mourning in Jerusalem” (Zech. 12:10–11).
- ii. ***The Savior Thirsting (Ps. 22:14–15; 69:21; Matt. 27:34, 48; John 19:28–29):*** He did not give vent to his own suffering until he knew that all he

had come to do for man's salvation had been accomplished. And here is recorded both in prophecy and history the one kindness shown to our suffering Lord as he hung on the cross: When he cried of his thirst, someone offered him an opiate that would have lessened the physical pain. But we note that he refused the vinegar, which was mingled with gall. He bore the full penalty of our sins in every respect.

- iii. *The Savior Stripped (Ps. 22:17–18; 34:20; Luke 23:34; John 19:23–24, 32–37)*: Seated in front of the cross, the Roman soldiers, the lowest strata of Roman citizenry, the men whose lives were characterized by violence and sin, gambled for his clothing. Though these men cared not for God or his Word or the dying Son of God upon the cross, they fulfilled that Word that day, for the prophet had declared, "They part my garments among them, and cast lots upon my vesture" (Psalm 22:18). And yet the same unseen power that caused the soldiers to gamble over the Savior's garments later withheld the hammer blows that would have broken his limbs. Not only had the prophet declared that not a bone of his would be broken, but centuries earlier when Israel fled from Egypt, not a bone of the paschal lamb was broken. When the Lamb who was slain from the foundation of the world became Israel's Passover, it was fitting that he should be offered up in the same manner. Here again we see the marvel of God's providence, for if our Lord had been stoned to death or had even suffered bone-breaking bodily injury from one of the boulders with which the Jews had threatened him, he would no longer have been the perfect Lamb for the Passover sacrifice. Thus, in the substitution of crucifixion for stoning, Christ in his death became a perfect antitype of the paschal lamb. Scot Mcknight (2020) said, "The cross must inform our understanding of goodness within the church. It is through the sacrificial love of Christ that we learn to embody a culture of healing and restoration."
- iv. *The Savior Humiliated (Isa. 53:12; Mark 15:27–28; Luke 22:37; 23:34a)*: In Isaiah 53 there are at least ten predictions regarding the humiliation of the King of Glory. The crowning insult was numbering him with the transgressors. What it meant to the absolutely holy Son of God to be crucified between thieves we cannot fathom. It was the outrage of the ages. It was an indignity that this world had never seen before and never will again. But in the midst of his humiliation, he became a Savior of the transgressors with whom he was numbered.

v. *The Provision for the Sacrifice:*

- a. *The Lamb Provided for Abraham:* A bearded patriarch rose early one morning and awakened his son, so they could begin the three-day journey to the mount of which God had spoken (Gen. 22:1–13). God had commanded him to slay his only son as a sacrifice on a mountain altar. Finally, they arrived at the appointed place. Imagine the anguish of the father’s heart when the son broke the silence with his innocent question: “My father...beholds the fire and the wood: but where is the lamb for a burnt offering?”
- b. *The Lamb Provided for the World: Abraham* spoke prophetically (see John 8:56). Abraham’s son was spared in the moment of death. But when God led his only begotten Son to the cross, he could not spare him from death. Can anyone measure the greatness of the love that made the everlasting Father not only place his son on the altar but thrust the sacrificial knife into the heart of his only begotten, beloved Son?
- c. *The Power of the Sacrifice:* It is almost impossible to measure the far-reaching results of the atonement. Every blessing, material or spiritual, that has come to man in the history of the world has been brought about by the death of Christ. Without its God could not have given blessings, for because of his sin man had forfeited every claim to God’s benevolence. It will take eternity to appreciate all that the great sacrifice means.
- d. *It saves us from the Penalty of Sin (Rom. 3:24; 5:1; 8:1; Titus 2:14):* Christ died in our place on Calvary, suffering the just penalty due our sin, in order that we might be delivered from the guilt, defilement, and penalty of sin through faith in him.
- e. *It secures us from the Power of Sin (Rom. 6:6–18; 8:12):* While Satan cannot change the destiny of the believer, he is still able to tempt him with sin. But “there is power in the blood” of Jesus Christ to give every Christian victory over temptation (Heb. 2:18). Sin no longer need have dominion over the believer (Rom. 6:12–18).
- f. *It separates us from the Presence of Sin (Rev. 21:27):* The believer in Christ can look forward to the certainty of an entrance into that holy and happy habitation where no evil can gain entrance. This unmerited, indescribable place has been provided only by the death of Jesus Christ (Hodge, 2004).

Ethical Dimensions

The ethical implications of Jesus' sacrificial death are significant in shaping the moral framework of contemporary Christians. The call to live sacrificially is evident in Pauline theology, particularly in Romans 12:1, which urges believers to present their bodies as living sacrifices. Scholars like N.T. Wright (2006) emphasize that the church is called to embody the values of the kingdom of God, which includes love, justice, and reconciliation. This has led to a renewed focus on social ethics within the church, where issues such as poverty, racial reconciliation, and environmental stewardship are viewed through the lens of Christ's sacrificial love.

i. *The Purpose of the Sacrifice*: Why were Abraham's son spared and God's son sacrificed? Why was it necessary for our Lord Jesus Christ to suffer a painful and shameful death?

1. *The Fulfilment of Scripture (Luke 24:25–26; 1 Cor. 15:3)*: Christ's sacrifice was necessary in order to fulfil scripture. This our Lord declared to the travellers on the road to Emmaus. This Paul wrote to the Corinthians.
2. *The Holiness of God (Ps. 47:8; 24:3–4; Isa. 6:3)*: In a former chapter we considered the perfection of God's holiness. To God, sin of every kind is awful, sullied, degrading. His whole nature turns in utter abhorrence against it. The Scriptures plainly teach that death has been the penalty of sinful creatures who have dared to venture into his holy presence. A righteous God could not possibly ignore sin. To do so would have been contrary to his own holiness and would have resulted in moral chaos in the world.
3. *The Sinfulness of Man (Rom. 3:10-20; Gal. 3:13-14)*: All men have sinned. This is the plain teaching of Scripture. There is original sin, in which all men partake of the transgression of their first parents, who not only fell from the holy estate in which they were created, but by disobeying God brought all their descendants into a state of sin and misery. The sinfulness of man was made evident in the giving of the law. The law God gave did not remove sin but only made it all the more glaring. In view of the holiness of God and the sinfulness of man, the question naturally arises: How is the mercy of God to be manifested so that his holiness will not be compromised by his assuming a merciful attitude toward sinful men in the granting of forgiveness? If God and the sinner are to be brought

together, something must be done to remove sin, for while God loves the sinner, he has and will always continue to have hatred for sin.

4. ***Propitiation through Sacrifice (Rom. 3:25; 1 John 2:2; 4:10):*** Propitiation means “appeasing.” The mercy seat covering the Ark of the Covenant was a type of Christ. The Hebrew word *kaphar* or *kapporeth* was translated in New Testament Greek as *hilasterion*. Both words convey “covering” and are discussed in the context of reconciliation with God, or propitiation (Exod. 25:17, 22; Heb. 9:5; Rom. 3:25). The death of Christ for man’s sin satisfied the demands of God’s holiness and righteousness relative to the sin question and the offending sinner. Therefore, all who come to God through faith on the basis of that gracious cross-work receive the forgiveness of sins and the gift of eternal life and are given a perfect standing in God’s sight (justification). Christ’s death is the righteous ground on which a righteous God can justify sinners without compromising His holiness and righteousness. It must always be remembered that “the carnal mind is enmity against God,” and “to be carnally minded is death” (Rom. 8:6–7). God can have no dealings with man until his sin is removed, and only Christ’s blood is sufficient for this.
5. ***Sufficient for All (Heb. 2:9):*** Christ tasted death for every man, and sinners of all sorts, degrees, and conditions may have a share in the benefits of his redemptive work. The Greeks invited only the cultured, the Romans called the strong, and the Jews believed only the religious were entitled to salvation. Christ bids all to come. No one can deny the ‘whosoever’ of the Gospel. The invitation to partake of the blessings of Christ’s death is universal.
6. ***Efficacious to the Believer:*** A Sovereign God who offers a gracious pardon to an undeserving sinner has a right to lay down conditions for the reception of these benefits. There must be an acceptance of God’s gift. Salvation made possible by Christ’s sacrificial death is unlimited, but only those who believe and accept it can be saved. Only man’s unbelief limits the atonement (John 3:16–18; 5:40).

Implications for the Contemporary Church

Contemporary church leaders are increasingly recognizing the need to translate the theological and ethical implications of Jesus’ sacrifice into practical ministry. For example, the work of theologians like Miroslav Volf (2011) highlights the importance of forgiveness and reconciliation in a world

marked by division and conflict. Many churches are adopting practices that reflect this ethos, such as community outreach programs, peace-making initiatives, and advocacy for marginalized groups. These actions not only honour the sacrificial nature of Christ's death but also serve as a testament to the transformative power of the gospel in the present age.

- i. *A mystery to the disciples:* There is no better proof that the Bible is the Word of God than the sacrifice of our Lord on Calvary, which was clearly described by the psalmists and prophets' centuries before it took place. Our Lord particularly calls attention to this fact (Luke 24:44). The marvel of the mystery is that the disciples failed to understand the passages in the Old Testament that predicted the history of Jesus Christ and yet described with wonderful literalness his sufferings and glory. These passages are remarkable in view of the fact that the Jews did not expect their long looked-for Messiah to be put to death but rather thought he would reign as king. Even the disciples could not comprehend the many references our Lord made to his death. The truth of the matter is that the Old Testament had much to say about a coming King and prophesied about a crucified Savior. The angel who announced to Mary the birth of Jesus said nothing about his premature death but instead predicted, "He shall be great, and shall be called the Son of the Highest: and the Lord shall give unto him the throne of his father David: And he shall reign over the house of Jacob forever; and of his kingdom there shall be no end" (Luke 1:32–33). No wonder Mary pondered these things in her heart, and no wonder that a sword pierced her own perplexed soul (see Luke 2:35) as she stood at the cross and beheld the suffering of her uncrowned Son.
- ii. *Its place in the gospels:* A study of the Gospels impresses one with the silence concerning many years of Christ's life and the emphasis upon the last week of his life. If, as some contend, the life rather than the death of Christ is the important subject, is it not strange that each of the Gospel writers gave the briefest accounts of the events in Jesus' life but described in detail the events connected with his death. "The crucifixion of Christ invites the church to embrace the 'other' in a radical act of reconciliation, demonstrating that sacrificial love overcomes division and estrangement." (Volf, 2021). The atonement was the all-important purpose of Christ's coming is proved by the fact that John, having related incidents and conversations that others omitted, joined with Matthew, Mark, and Luke in making much of our Lord's

last week in Jerusalem. Of the twenty-one chapters in John, ten describe the events leading up to the crucifixion and resurrection. Paul made the cross the theme of his first and many other sermons (see 1 Cor. 15:1- 4).

- iii. *Death of Jesus:* Internal and external evidences attested that both the Gospel of Luke and the Book of Acts are addressed to Theophilus. Who was presumably a Gentile of some social standing, but unfortunately nothing was heard about Theophilus again, not in Scripture nor anywhere else in ancient literature. In Luke 1:3 he is referred to as “most excellent Theophilus,” an appellation which Luke elsewhere reserves only for the Roman governors Felix (Acts 23:26; 24:3) and Festus (Acts 26:25). In his opening line in Acts, Luke reminds Theophilus that in his “former book” he wrote “about all that Jesus began to do and to teach” (Acts 1:1). From this evidence it is not difficult to conclude that the “former book” Luke had in mind is his Gospel. In studying Luke’s view of Jesus’ death, some scholars have tended to concentrate on Luke’s divergence from the theology of Mark or Paul. Observing that, when reworking the passion materials taken over from Mark, Luke omitted Mark 10:45. Specifically, Luke presents the death of Jesus as a substitutionary atonement that brings about the forgiveness of sins (Zehnle, 1996). Atonement plays a fundamental role in Luke’s soteriology such that when this aspect is rejected or minimized, Luke’s presentation of the cross and salvation is distorted. While the books are anonymous, early Christian tradition named the author of Luke and Acts as Luke the physician, Gentile convert and friend of Paul (Col. 4:14; 2 Tim 4:11; Philemon 24). The date is debated, but Luke-Acts was probably written in the late first century, sometime after the fall of Jerusalem in 70AD (Veilhauer, 1996). Luke’s gospel is the longest of the four, and is the only one that comes with a sequel – the Acts of the Apostles. Just from looking at these first few sentences, we can deduce a number of characteristics of Luke’s account of Jesus. Luke’s is a careful and orderly account, using several sources and witnesses. Luke is quite explicit about the fact that he is constructing a narrative to convey the truth about Jesus to Theophilus. (By the way, no-one knows who Theophilus was, but from these verses it seems he was someone important who had recently converted to Christianity) Luke-Acts is beautifully written, with far more skill than Mark’s rough and ready Greek. Luke varies his style to suit different occasions (e.g.

sometimes formal prose, sometimes Semitic idiom), and is a gifted writer (Kasemann, 1994). Although Luke was probably a Gentile, and Luke-Acts seems to have been written for a primarily Gentile audience, he had considerable knowledge of the Hebrew Scriptures and Jewish religion.

- iv. **Key themes and features about the death of Jesus:** They are as follows:
- a. **God's plan:** God's plan of course, at the centre of all the gospels is the question, "Who is Jesus?" Luke, more than the other evangelists, relates this question to the big picture, both theologically and historically. Jesus is the fulfilment and centre of God's redemptive purpose for all humanity. Luke's central (and rather ambitious) goal in his masterpiece seems to be to describe the universal plan of God worked out in human history. That the divine purpose will be unfolding inexorably is made clear in the birth and infancy narratives. Contrast Luke's first chapters with Mark's rather abrupt introduction, where Jesus just immediately gets going. The early chapters of Luke's gospel look back to the Hebrew Scriptures and the time of prophecy, as well as locating Jesus in a particular historical time and place. The end of the gospel looks ahead into the future, moving on into the Acts of the Apostles and out into the Gentile world, and ultimately anticipating the return of the Lord. Salvation for all people, radical inclusiveness should not be overstated as peculiar to Luke, because all the gospels communicate Jesus' concern for all people, regardless of social standing. However, Luke is particularly emphatic about it. Luke shows that the good news of God's mercy is not just for Israel, but for the Gentile world, demonstrated in the stories of Acts as well as in his gospel. There are many scenes in Luke's gospel of Jesus reaching out to sinners, Samaritans, tax collectors, women, and outcasts (Kasemann, 1994).
 - b. **Poverty and Wealth:** Luke refers to poverty and wealth more than any other gospel, and his material includes such memorable passages as the Magnificent (Luke 1:46-55) and the parable of Lazarus and the rich man (Luke 16:19-31). While Luke is kinder to the disciples and the Pharisees than Mark is, he is hard on the rich and powerful.
 - c. **Table fellowship:** A commentator quipped that in Luke's gospel "Jesus is either going to a meal, at a meal, or coming from a meal." Meal scenes provide the setting for much of Jesus' ministry. They are places where Jesus crosses social boundaries (e.g. Luke 5:29-32; 7:36-50).

Several parables use the motif of a meal (Luke 14:15-24). Breaching boundaries at table is bound up with Jesus' death and resurrection. Breaking bread together is tied to Jesus' body broken for humanity, in the Last Supper (Luke 22:14-20). And the bread broken together is also the place where the risen Lord is present with the community, in the meal at Emmaus (Luke 24:13-35).

- d. ***Prayer, Joy, and the Holy Spirit:*** Luke emphasizes true prayer, joyful praise, and the importance of empowerment by the Holy Spirit. Some of Luke's unique material is concerned with persistence and humility in prayer (e.g. the Friend at Midnight 11:5-8; the Pharisee and the Tax Collector 18:9-14). Prayer is connected to openness to God's Spirit. The Holy Spirit of God is the one who initiates and empowers the whole story as it unfolds. Luke refers to the Holy Spirit far more often than Mark or Matthew, and the Holy Spirit is central to the story of Acts. The responses of those who see God's power at work in history are characteristically joyful praise (e.g. 1:47; 10:21; 24:52-53), and a sense of joy runs throughout Luke-Acts.
- e. ***Luke's Gospel and the Acts of the Apostles:*** Luke's story of Jesus, like all good blockbusters, comes with a sequel. Luke and Acts are two volumes of the one great work of literature. Luke connects the life, death and resurrection of Jesus with the beginnings of the church. Luke's orderly account isn't just about some things that happened because of a one man named Jesus some decades before. For Luke, the story of Jesus is the centre of the big story about God's plan for creation and for all humanity, both Jew and Gentile. Luke calls us to respond to his story with both joy and serious commitment. He reminds the Christian community to embody Jesus' concern for all people, especially the poor, oppressed, and marginalized. And Luke invites us to be open to the work of the Holy Spirit as God's plan continues to unfold today.
- f. ***The New Covenant Sacrifice:*** The breaking of bread at Emmaus in the resolution of Luke's Gospel indicates that Jesus' sacrificial death was at the essence of his messianic task to redeem God's people. The breaking of bread in remembrance of Jesus' saving death is identified as one of the essential characteristics of the church in Acts, demonstrating its ongoing significance for the new community of believers. Paul's charge to the future leaders of the church, located within a farewell speech that serves as a literary parallel to that given

by Jesus at the Last Supper, is grounded in the fact that God acquired the church through Jesus' atoning blood. As a result, not only does Luke present the death of Jesus as an atoning sacrifice, he also identifies this atonement as the foundational event for establishing the church as God's redeemed community.

Conclusion

In conclusion, the sacrificial death of Jesus Christ is not merely a historical event but a living reality that shapes the identity, mission, and ethical framework of the contemporary Church. As believers reflect on the implications of the cross, they are called to embody the principles of sacrificial love, justice, and unity in a world that often conflicts with these values. The Church stands as a beacon of hope, a community committed to living out the transformative power of Christ's sacrifice in every aspect of life. In doing so, it not only honours the profound mystery of the cross but also fulfils its mission to be an agent of change, embodying the love and grace that Christ so willingly offered. Thus, the sacrificial death of Jesus remains a vital source of inspiration and challenge for the Church, urging it to engage meaningfully with the world while remaining steadfast in its commitment to the gospel.

Recommendations

The sacrificial death of Jesus Christ is a foundational aspect of Christian theology, and its implications for the contemporary Church are multifaceted. The sacrificial death of Jesus Christ remains a profound source of inspiration and guidance for the contemporary Church. By reflecting on its theological, ethical, and practical implications, churches can foster a deeper understanding of their mission and identity in today's world. Here are some recommendations:

1. *Theological Reflection*

- i. *Atonement Theories*: study the different theories of atonement to understand how they shape contemporary beliefs about Jesus' death.
- ii. *Grace and Forgiveness*: Emphasize the concepts of grace and forgiveness that arise from the sacrificial death. These ideas can transform congregational life and relationships.

2. *Worship Practices*

- i. *Communion*: This can highlight the importance of the Eucharist or Communion as a celebration of Jesus' sacrifice. This practice can

deepen congregational understanding and appreciation of Jesus' death.

- ii. **Liturgy:** It integrates reflections on the sacrificial death into worship services, particularly during Easter, this will help to reinforce its significance.

3. Ethical Implications

- i. **Christian Living:** Encourage discussions on how the sacrificial nature of Jesus' death calls Christians to live sacrificially for others, promoting service, compassion, and social justice.
- ii. **Community Engagement:** Develop outreach programs that reflect the sacrificial love of Christ, such as feeding the hungry, supporting the marginalized, and advocating for justice.

4. Discipleship and Spiritual Growth

- i. **Teaching ministry:** One can organize teaching series or small group studies focused on the implications of Jesus' sacrifice for personal faith and communal life.
- ii. **Personal Reflection:** Encourage church members to engage in personal reflection and prayer regarding what Jesus' sacrifice means for their lives.

5. Ecumenical Dialogue

- i. **Interdenominational Conversations:** Facilitate discussions with other Christian denominations to explore varying perspectives on the significance of the sacrificial death of Christ.
- ii. **Common Ground:** Identify shared beliefs that can foster unity among different Christian traditions, focusing on the centrality of Christ's sacrifice.

6. Social Justice and Advocacy

- i. **Mission Initiatives:** Connect the understanding of Jesus' sacrificial death to contemporary issues, such as poverty, racial injustice, and environmental stewardship, emphasizing a call to action rooted in love and sacrifice.

References

- Bock, Darrell L. *Jesus: The Ultimate Teacher*. Nashville: B&H Publishing Group, 2022.
- Cadbury, Henry J. *The Making of Luke-Acts* (New York: Macmillan, 1997), 280.
- Dodd, C. H. *The Apostolic Preaching and Its Developments* (2nd ed.; London: Hodder & Stoughton, 1994), 25.

- Ernst Käsemann, *Ministry and Community in the New Testament, in Essays on New Testament Themes* (trans. W. J. Montague; Naperville, IL: Allenson, 1994), 92.
- Hays, Richard B. *Echoes of Scripture in the Gospels*. Grand Rapids: Eerdmans, 2021.
- Hodge's outlines of Theology and *The One True God* Copyright © 2004 by Evangelical Training Association Published by Crossway Books a division of Good News Publishers 1300 Crescent Street Wheaton, Illinois 60187. Previously published as *The Triune God* by the Evangelical Training Association, 1949, 1962, 1964, 1970.
- Horsley, Richard A. *The Prophet Jesus and the Renewal of the People of God*. Philadelphia: Trinity Press International, 2022.
- Kim, Hyeon Soo. *The Cross in Context: Theological Reflections on the Cross and Contemporary Issues*. Eugene: Wipf and Stock, 2021.
- McKnight, Scot. *A Church Called Tov: Forming a Goodness Culture that Resists Abuses of Power and Promotes Healing*. Nashville: Zondervan, 2020.
- Nolland, John. *Luke 18:35-24:53* (Word Biblical Commentary 35c. Dallas: Word, 1993), 42.
- Philipp Vielhauer, *On the 'Paulinism' of Acts,*" in *Studies in Luke-Acts* (ed. Leander E. Keck and J. Louis Martyn; trans. Wm. C. Robinson, Jr., and Victor P. (Furnish; Nashville: Abingdon, 1996), 44-45.
- Richard Zehnle, *The Salvific Character of Jesus' Death in Lucan Soteriology*. *Theological Studies* 30 1996, 438-444.
- Volf, Miroslav. *Exclusion and Embrace: A Theological Exploration of Identity, Otherness, and Reconciliation*. New York: Abingdon Press, 2021.
- Wall, Robert W. "The Acts of the Apostles: Introduction, Commentary, and Reflections." Pages 1-368 in *New Interpreter's Bible*. Edited by Leander E. Keck et.al., Nashville: Abingdon, 2002.
- Wright, N.T. *The New Testament and the People of God*. Minneapolis: Fortress Press, 2020.

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**Pentecostal Pastors' English
Pronunciation Proficiency during Sermon
Delivery: Youths Disposition and
Engagement in Saki, Oyo State Nigeria**

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Abstract

This study examines the English pronunciation proficiency of Pentecostal pastors during sermon delivery and its impact on youth engagement in Saki, Oyo State, Nigeria. With the increasing influence of Pentecostal churches among young congregants, effective communication plays a crucial role in sustaining interest and participation. The study focuses on 25 youths from selected Pentecostal churches in Saki town, exploring their perceptions of pastoral pronunciation accuracy, clarity, and its effect on their engagement during sermons. Data were collected through questionnaires. Findings reveal that pronunciation proficiency significantly influences youths' comprehension, interest, and retention of sermon messages. While some youths demonstrate tolerance for minor pronunciation lapses, frequent errors contribute to disengagement and reduced comprehension. The study underscores the importance of linguistic competence in religious discourse and suggests targeted training for pastors to enhance sermon delivery effectiveness.

Keywords: Pentecostal pastors, English pronunciation, sermon delivery, youth engagement, linguistic competence.

Introduction

Effective communication is crucial in religious settings, especially during sermons where the primary goal is to convey spiritual truths and inspire action. For many Nigerian youths, English serves as a lingua franca, bridging diverse ethnic and linguistic backgrounds. However, the proficiency of pastors in English can significantly influence how their messages are received and understood. This review examines the existing literature on youths' disposition to pastors' English proficiency in the Nigerian context, exploring the intersection of language, culture, and spiritual engagement. Youth are very pertinent to the growth of many churches and should be well equipped to grow spiritually, connect to Christ, as well as serve Christ.

Language serves as a powerful medium for communication, particularly in the dissemination of religious messages. In Nigeria, where a multiplicity of ethnic groups coexists, English often functions as a lingua franca, enabling pastors to reach a wider audience during sermon delivery. However, the effectiveness of this communication relies heavily on the pastor's English pronunciation proficiency. Clear, accurate, and engaging pronunciation can enhance comprehension and connection, while poor pronunciation may lead to misinterpretations or disengagement, particularly among the youth.

Nigerian youth, shaped by their exposure to formal education, global media, and technology, have developed a sensitivity to linguistic accuracy and fluency. Their engagement with religious sermons often depends on how relatable and comprehensible the message is. The pastor's proficiency in English pronunciation is not merely a linguistic matter but also a tool for effective ministry. A mispronounced word or an unclear expression can detract from the intended spiritual message, leading to a potential loss of interest among younger congregants.

Despite the importance of this issue, there is limited scholarly exploration of the intersection between English pronunciation proficiency and youth engagement within Nigerian religious settings. This gap underscores the need to investigate how Nigerian pastors' English pronunciation proficiency impacts youth disposition and engagement during sermons, and whether linguistic barriers hinder the transmission of religious teachings.

Statement of the Problem

A great deal has been written in recent years regarding the number of young people who 'leave the church' after graduating from high school. Regardless

of which study we use, the numbers are depressing at best and staggering at worst... Research is ongoing, and books, articles, blogs, seminars, websites, and the like continue to wrestle with ways in which we can enhance the likelihood that young people will remain committed to the church when they move out and head into their adult journey – (Chap Clark, 2016).

This lack of engagement affects the spiritual formation of many youths; according to Josh McDowell (2003), “We need a spiritual revolution because there’s little transformation in the moral. Despite the efforts of many churches to engage, attract, and retain youth, there is still a lack of youth participation, involvement, and interest in the local church. Daniel Burke (2016) opines that “Christianity in the United States hasn’t done a good job of engaging serious Christian. Youth are engaged in the church if the church engages the youth. Church engagement of the youth is impactful and contingent upon the church mission and purposeful method. The church’s method of engagement influences the perceptions of church held by students.

Religious sermons are a cornerstone of Christian worship, serving as a channel for spiritual enlightenment and moral guidance. However, among Nigerian youths, a growing disengagement from traditional religious activities has been noted, raising concerns about the factors contributing to this phenomenon. One potential factor is the pastor’s pronunciation proficiency during sermon delivery.

While some pastors may be well-versed in theological content, their ability to articulate this knowledge in comprehensible and engaging English often varies. Mispronunciations or accents that hinder clarity can alienate younger audiences who are accustomed to standard or globally influenced English through their education and media consumption. Consequently, this linguistic disconnect may lead to reduced attentiveness, misinterpretation of messages, or complete disengagement from the sermon. The problem lies in understanding the extent to which English pronunciation proficiency affects youth disposition and engagement during sermons. Are young people more likely to connect with sermons delivered in clear and proficient English? What specific pronunciation challenges do pastors face, and how do these impact the perceived quality of the sermon? Addressing these questions is vital to enhancing sermon delivery and sustaining youth participation in Christian worship.

Aim and Objectives

The aim of this study is to investigate the effects of Pastors' English Pronunciation Proficiency During Sermon Delivery on Youths Disposition and Engagement in order to bridge the gap between linguistic proficiency and effective religious communication, offering insights that could foster a more inclusive and engaging worship experience for Nigerian youths. The specific objectives are to:

1. examine the general disposition of Christian youths towards pastors' English pronunciation during sermon delivery;
2. assess the level of engagement of Nigerian youths with sermons delivered by pastors with varying levels of English pronunciation proficiency;
3. identify specific pronunciation challenges faced by Nigerian pastors during sermon delivery; and
4. explore the relationship between pastors' English pronunciation proficiency and youth engagement.

Literature Review

The Role of Language in Religious Communication

The interplay between language proficiency and audience engagement is a critical area of study, particularly within religious contexts where effective communication is paramount. In Nigeria, a nation characterized by linguistic diversity, English often serves as the lingua franca, especially in urban and inter-ethnic religious gatherings. This literature review explores the relationship between Nigerian pastors' English pronunciation proficiency and youth engagement during sermon delivery. Language is a powerful tool for conveying meaning and shaping perceptions. Scholars such as Halliday (1978) highlight the functional role of language in facilitating understanding and fostering connections. In religious communication, clear and proficient language use ensures that complex theological concepts are accessible to the audience (Adeboye, 2015). For Nigerian youths, whose educational and social experiences are largely influenced by English, pastors' ability to deliver sermons in grammatically correct and fluent English plays a pivotal role in retaining their attention and ensuring comprehension.

English, introduced during colonial times, has evolved into a distinct Nigerian English (NE) variant, influenced by indigenous languages and local speech patterns. Studies have identified unique phonetic and

phonological features in NE, such as the substitution of certain sounds and tonal variations, which distinguish it from Standard British English (SBE). These variations can affect intelligibility, particularly among listeners accustomed to SBE norms.

Pronunciation significantly impacts comprehension. Mispronunciations or heavy accents can lead to misunderstandings, reducing the effectiveness of communication. In religious settings, where sermons are central to spiritual instruction, clear pronunciation is essential to convey messages accurately and maintain congregational engagement.

Youth Engagement in Religious Activities

Nigerian youths are increasingly exposed to global cultures and languages through education and media, shaping their linguistic preferences and expectations. This exposure influences their engagement with religious activities, including sermon comprehension and participation. Pastors who align their communication styles with the linguistic expectations of the youth may foster greater engagement

Pastoral Communication Strategies

Effective pastors often employ strategic communication techniques to connect with their congregations. This includes adapting language use, incorporating relatable examples, and addressing contemporary issues relevant to the youth. However, the role of pronunciation proficiency in these strategies is less explored, indicating a gap in the literature.

Challenges in Pronunciation Proficiency

Nigerian pastors face challenges in achieving pronunciation proficiency due to factors such as limited access to formal language training and the influence of mother tongues. These challenges can affect sermon delivery and, consequently, congregational engagement.

Implications for Youth Engagement

The alignment between a pastor's pronunciation proficiency and the linguistic expectations of the youth can influence engagement levels. Clear and relatable communication may enhance comprehension and participation, while significant pronunciation deviations might lead to disengagement.

The literature suggests a complex relationship between pastors' English pronunciation proficiency and youth engagement in Nigerian religious contexts. While clear pronunciation is important for comprehension, other factors such as cultural relevance, content delivery, and the use of relatable language also play significant roles. Further empirical research is needed to explore these dynamics and develop strategies to enhance effective communication between pastors and youth congregants.

For youths, especially those in urban areas, English is not only a medium of instruction in schools but also a marker of social identity. Consequently, pastors' command of English can impact their perceived authority and relevance, especially among English-speaking youths. Nigerians disposition to English language is positive and great prestige is accorded to it in every sphere. Youths in Nigeria, like any other part of the globe are favourably disposed to anyone who has a good command of language and could communicate with fluency and accuracy. Such pastors are followed online and in their physical location. The power of language or English proficiency is a marketable phenomenon in the modern among the youths

Youths' Disposition to Sermon Delivery

Nigerian youths are increasingly exposed to global trends and high standards of communication, thanks to advancements in technology and social media. As a result, their expectations of sermon delivery have evolved. Studies (e.g., Ezeh, 2017) suggest that clear articulation, appropriate vocabulary, and grammatical accuracy in English are essential for engaging youth audiences. Poor proficiency may lead to disengagement, misunderstanding, or even ridicule, which could undermine the pastor's credibility.

Cultural and Contextual Sensitivity

While English proficiency is valued, Nigerian youths also appreciate cultural relevance in sermons. Akintoye (2019) argues that effective sermon delivery requires a balance between linguistic competence and contextual understanding. Pastors who incorporate local idioms, proverbs, and examples within their English sermons tend to resonate more with their audience. This hybrid approach can enhance relatability and foster deeper connections with youths.

Impact of English Proficiency on Comprehension and Engagement

Research highlights a direct link between a speaker's language proficiency and audience comprehension. For instance, a study by Olaniyan (2020) found that pastors who demonstrated high proficiency in English were more likely to convey their messages effectively, leading to better audience engagement and retention. Conversely, frequent grammatical errors or unclear expressions may distract youths, reducing the overall impact of the sermon.

Challenges Faced by Nigerian Pastors in English Pronunciation Proficiency

Many pastors in Nigeria face challenges in achieving high levels of English proficiency. These challenges include limited access to quality education, regional linguistic diversity, and a reliance on local languages for day-to-day communication (Ajayi, 2016). As a result, some pastors struggle to meet the expectations of English-speaking youths, creating a gap in communication that may affect spiritual growth and church attendance.

Youths' Expectations of Pastors' Communication Skills

Youths often associate proficiency in English with professionalism and intellectual depth. According to a survey conducted by Adekunle (2021), 72% of Nigerian youths believe that a pastor's ability to communicate effectively in English enhances their respect for the pastor and increases their likelihood of implementing sermon teachings. However, the same study revealed that youths also value authenticity and emotional connection, which suggests that proficiency alone is insufficient without genuine passion and relatable content.

Theological Implications of Language Proficiency

Beyond the practical aspects of communication, English proficiency in sermon delivery carries theological implications. The Bible emphasizes the importance of clarity in teaching (1 Corinthians 14:9). For Nigerian youths, sermons that are difficult to understand due to language barriers may hinder their spiritual growth and relationship with God. Therefore, pastors are encouraged to invest in improving their language skills to fulfill their divine calling effectively.

Methodology

The research is a descriptive survey, the sample size of the study comprises of 25 Christian youths in Oyo town purposively drawn from Pentecostal churches through Pentecostal Fellowship of Nigeria (PFN) Youth Wing platform. A self developed questionnaire was administered to them and the responses were analysed in simple percentage and discussion was made as well as recommendations.

Data Analysis and Discussion

Age Distribution of the Respondents

Figure 1

Figure 1 above shows that all the respondents are from 18 to 30 years of age with 73.3% falling between 18 and 25 years while 26 to 30 years are 26.7%. This shows that the respondents are the future of the church. Their need should be catered for if the church will not go into natural extinction.

Gender Distribution of the Respondents

Figure 2

Figure 2 presented the gender distribution of the respondents. About 86.7% of the respondents were female while only 13.3% were male. This is true of the picture of many pentecostal churches today, only female sing in the choir apart from playing instrument that many male do as a job collecting money from church to church.

Educational Level of the Respondent

Educational Level:

15 responses

Figure 3

Figure 3 presented the educational qualification of the respondents, 60% are undergraduates, 33.3% are post graduates while about 6.7% have other qualifications. This shows that majority of them have been or are being exposed to university education.

Number of Respondents who have changed church

Have you changed church before:

14 responses

Figure 4

Figure showed that 78.6% of the respondents have changed their churches at one time or the other for different reasons. Only 21.4% have not changed their churches. This implies that youths are easily pieced off when they see

anything they do not like in any church. The reasons why youths changed churches need to be studied in order to retain them in the church because they are the church of tomorrow.

Reason for Changing Church

Figure 5

27.3% of youths who have left a church any point in time said they left because of pastor's level of exposure and language proficiency. Others left for other reasons. This implies that more than one out of four who left a church for another church did so because of the better exposure and linguistic prowess of the new church pastor.

Importance of Good Pronunciation to Understanding

How important is a pastor's English pronunciation in your understanding?

15 responses

Figure 6

In figure 6 above, it was seen that 53.3% agreed that pastor's pronunciation is important to their understanding of sermons. This means, when a pastor

has deficiency in pronunciation, it hinders the message he is passing across to the congregation.

Youths are Attracted to Pronunciation Proficiency

Pastors with more youths their churches and as followers online have good command of English and Pronunciation proficiency

15 responses

Figure 7

Figure 7 above showed that 80% of the pastors who have many youths in their churches and as followers online have good command of English and pronunciation proficiency. By implication, pastors should develop their delivery skill as far as command and pronunciation of English is concerned. 64.3% of the youths that responded to the question of whether only sound biblical knowledge is needed to attract and retain the youths in a church disagreed. This means not only sound biblical knowledge is needed to attract and retain the youths in a Pentecostal church.

In another vein, 86.7% agreed that good communication and pronunciation proficiency of the pastor attract youths to a church.

Also, 80% of the youths responded in the affirmative that they are engaged when the pastor speaks fluently and pronounce words very well.

The study found that certain aspects of the pastor's pronunciation make the youths engaged during sermon delivery. These include clarity of words, correct pronunciation of key terms, absence of distracting accent, intelligible pronunciation.

Discussion

From the foregoing, it is observed that youths are attracted, retained and engaged in a particular church not because of sound biblical knowledge of the pastor alone but a lot of other factors. One of such factors is pastor's

exposure and pronunciation proficiency. The youths formed the largest percentage of the Nigerian population, hence any church that wants to be relevant in the next few years must develop a way of knowing how to attract, retain and engage this teaming population. The church must be intentional about her drive for the youth involvement in the mainstream of things in the church.

This study has conducted a survey among youths from Pentecostal churches in Saki and discovered that majority of them have changed their church at one time or the other for different reasons. This implied that they have their taste and what they are looking for in the church that will attract, retain and engage them. If those things are not in place, it is a matter of time, they will leave that church. The onus therefore, lies on the church to know what are the things that will attract, retain and engage the youths.

Also, the major fulcrum of this study is to investigate the nexus pastor's pronunciation proficiency and youth attraction, retention and engagement. Any church where many youths are attracted to, retained and engaged, physically or virtually, it is not because such pastors are indulgent but because the youths see what they want including exposure, good command of English and pronunciation proficiency.

Many of the youths believed that not only sound biblical knowledge can attract, retain and engage the youths. They believed that good communication and pronunciation proficiency of the pastor attract youths to a church.

Conclusion

The disposition of Nigerian youths toward pastors' English proficiency during sermon delivery is shaped by a combination of linguistic, cultural, and spiritual factors. While proficiency in English enhances comprehension and engagement, it must be complemented by cultural sensitivity, emotional connection, and theological depth.

Future research should explore strategies for equipping pastors with the necessary language skills to meet the evolving expectations of youth congregants in Nigeria.

Recommendations

1. The study recommends that further study be carried out on other factors that can help to attract, retain and engage the youths apart from the one investigated here.

2. The study recommends that pastors should be intentional about developing their linguistic competence and pronunciation proficiency in order to attract, retain and engage younger generation in their churches.
3. The study recommends that the New Covenant Bible College should introduce a course on English communication proficiency this will help to attract, retain and engage the youths in our various centres.

References

- Adeboye, O. (2015). *The Role of Language in Religious Communication*. Lagos University Press.
- Akintoye, T. (2019). *Cultural Contexts in Sermon Delivery*. Ibadan: Heritage Publications.
- Bamgbose, A. (2000). *Language and the Nation: The Language Question in Sub-Saharan Africa*. Edinburgh: Edinburgh University Press.
- Ezeh, C. (2017). Youth Engagement in Contemporary Church Sermons. *Nigerian Journal of Religious Studies*, 12(3), 45-59.
- Halliday, M. A. K. (1978). *Language as Social Semiotic*. Edward Arnold.
- Gbadegesin M. (2019) *Introduction to Phonetics and Phonology*
- Olaniyan, K. (2020). *Communication Effectiveness in Nigerian Churches*. Abuja: Covenant Publishers.
- Adekunle, R. (2021). "Youth Perceptions of Pastoral Communication." *African Journal of Theology*, 18(2), 101-120.
- Ajayi, S. (2016). *Language Challenges in Multilingual Societies*. Ibadan: Spectrum Books.
- Chap Clark, *Adoptive Youth Ministry: Integrating Emerging Generations into the Family of Faith* (Grand Rapids: Baker Academic, a division of Baker Publishing Group, 2016), 180.
- Josh McDowell and Ron Luce, (2003), "It's Time for a Revolution in Youth Ministry," *Group*, May, 52,
<http://exproxy.liberty.edu/login?url=https://searchproquestcom.ezproxy.liberty.edu/docview/231990550?accountid=12085.1>.
- Daniel Burke (2020), "Millennials leaving church in droves, study finds," *CNN Religion*, May 14, 2015, accessed May 16, 2025, <https://www.cnn.com/2015/05/12/living/pew-religion-study/index.html>.